

TERRA VISION

Integrated Earth Observation Based Platform, for Novel Services
to Enhance the Mining Life Cycle of Critical Raw Materials

D14.3

Standardization landscape and TERRAVISION contribution to
standardization (initial report)

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interfaces
CEN	European Committee for Standardization
CENELEC	European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization
COPANT	Pan American Standards Commission
CRM	Critical Raw Material
CWA	CEN or CENELEC Workshop Agreement
EN	European Standard
EOTA	European Organisation for Technical Assessment
ESO	European Standardisation Organisation
ETAG	European Technical Approval Guideline
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EU	European Union
hEN	Harmonised European Standard
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
ISO	International Organization for Standardization; International Standard
ITU	International Telecommunications Union
JTC	Join Technical Committee
LCA	Life Cycle assessment
NMC	National Mirror Committee
NGO	Nongovernmental Organizations

NSB	National Standardization Body
SC	Subcommittee
TC	Technical Committee
TR	Technical Report
TS	Technical Specification
UNE	Spanish Association for Standardization
WG	Working Group
WI	Work Item
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package
WTO	World Trade Organization

H1 – EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document presents the standardization activities relevant for the TERRAVISION project . In order to structure the research, a list of key concepts was elaborated by UNE to act as a starting point for the identification of standardization areas :

- Mining
- Materials
- Production and processing
- Analysis and testing
- Safety aspects
- Geo-information and data management
- Application
- Environment
- Market analysis
- Waste Management

The study covers European standards developed by the European Committee for Standardization (CEN), the European Committee for electrotechnical Standardization (CENELEC) and the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI). It also covers the International standards developed by the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) and the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC).

The study is structured in standardization areas for which relevant standardization Technical Committees (TCs) (including other technical bodies), published standards and standards under development.

H2 – GOAL/OBJECTIVES

The goal of this deliverable is to provide standards references which could help and accompany the work of “technical” Work Packages (WP) of the TERRAVISION project by avoiding double work in their researches and incorporate previous technical developments agreed by the identified sectors which could impact TERRAVISION.

H3 – METHODOLOGY

This deliverable used a standard methodology developed in the SCIMIN project (Grant Agreement number: 101177746), following EU recommendations. Ad hoc modifications were added to comply with the Grant Agreement conditions for TERRAVISION (Grant Agreement number: 101138643).

H4 – OUTCOMES/CONCLUSIONS

Key outcomes/conclusions in bullet points

- Several TCs identified related to the scope of TERRAVISION
- The majority is remarkable for Geo-information and data management
- Others also related included
- Possibility of support TERRAVISION with specific standards under justification
- First step for identification of gaps in standardization and the definition of standardization strategy to be developed in the next WP related to standardization

1. Introduction

1.1 Deliverable Description

This deliverable provides an overview of the standardization landscape related to the TERRAVISION-project.

1.2 Purpose of the Deliverable

The main objective of this deliverable is to analyze the applicable standardization landscape and, afterwards in the upcoming Standardization WP, develop a strategy for an effective contribution to standardization. During this second phase we will interact with relevant TCs and contribute to the development of new standards in topics related to the innovative platform.

1.3 Deliverable structure

The deliverable is structured in five Chapters where the first is introductory and contains the aim of the deliverable and its structure, the second and third provide brief information on the standardization context and how the relevant standardization TCs and their standards have been identified. Chapter 4 contains the core of the deliverable, hence information on TCs and the standards and projects which could benefit the project and partners. And finally, Chapter 5 includes the conclusions of the deliverable and the next steps forward in the standardization activity of the project.

2. Short introduction on standardization

2.1 General

Standards are voluntary technical documents that set out requirements for a specific item, material, component, system or service, or describe in detail a particular method, procedure, or best practice. Standards are developed and defined through a process of sharing knowledge and building consensus among technical experts nominated by interested parties and other stakeholders - including companies, consumers and environmental groups, among others. These experts are organized into TCs, which are subdivided into Subcommittees (SCs) or Working Groups (WGs). These TCs are included in the structure of the Standardization Organizations (National, European and International, with the respective mirror committees) and work following their internal regulations.

The standards are developed by teams of experts who have knowledge of the specific sector or topic that is being addressed. The members of TCs as well as sub-committees and working groups are nominated by the National Standardization bodies (NSB).

2.2 International Standardization Organizations

International Standardization Organizations develop worldwide applicable, market-driven standards, in a multi-stakeholder environment which ensures that a wide range of technical views are represented, including those relating to social and economic interests.

Although not governed by any specific jurisdiction, international standards play a crucial role in facilitating global trade. This significance has been acknowledged by the World Trade Organization (WTO). The organizations listed below adhere to the WTO Agreement on Technical Barriers to Trade's Code of Good Practice for the Preparation, Adoption, and Application of Standards.

The three International Standardization Organizations are:

- **ISO – International Standardization Organization**

ISO is an independent, non-governmental international organization with a membership of 164 national standards bodies. ISO develops standards mainly in fields not related to electrotechnology or telecommunications.

- **IEC – International Electrotechnical Commission**

IEC is a not-for-profit, non-governmental organization with membership of 86 national standards bodies. IEC develops standards in fields related to electrotechnology.

- **ITU – International Telecommunication Union**

ITU is the United Nations specialized agency for information and communication technologies. It is based on public-private partnerships and currently has memberships from 193 countries and almost 800 private-sector entities and academic institutions.

2.3 European Standardization Organizations

The European Standardization system plays a major role in the EU Single Market, enabling the free circulation of goods among countries. The European standardization system relies on a single standard model. European standards are identically adopted by all their National Members. Consequently, any conflicting national standards are withdrawn

European standards facilitate compliance with EU harmonization legislation, hence the entry and free circulation of goods in the EU Single Market, based on a set of requirements which are equally applicable in all Member States of the European Union.

European Standardization Organizations work closely with their international level counterparts, to avoid duplication of efforts and promote global relevance of standards.

CEN, CENELEC and ETSI are officially recognized by the European Union and by the European Free Trade Association (EFTA) as theresponsible for developing standards at the European level.

- **CEN – European Committee for Standardization**

CEN is a non-profit association whose members are the national standards bodies of 34 European countries. It develops standards in fields not related to electrotechnology or telecommunications. It is the counterpart at the European level of ISO.

- **CENELEC – European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization**

CENELEC is a non-profit association whose members are the national standards bodies of 34 European countries. It develops standards in fields related to electrotechnology. It is the counterpart at European level of IEC.

- **ETSI – European Telecommunications Standards Institute**

ETSI is a non-profit organization with more than 850 member organizations worldwide. It develops standards for Information and Communications Technologies (ICT).

2.4 National Standardization Organizations

The national standardization organizations are the organizations officially recognized at national level as being able to represent all standardization interests at the country level. They are responsible for developing national standards, and as such they are member of ISO, IEC, CEN and CENELEC (note that ITU and ETSI have different membership policies). National stakeholders interested in standardization activities can take part in the process at European or International level through their national standardization organization.

The legal status of national standardization organizations varies from one country to another. The most typical status is a private non-profit organization whose members are national business associations and companies. However, sometimes the national standardization organization is a part of the public administration.

As mentioned above, for the European level, the European Standardization System guarantees that European Standards are identically adopted by all the national standardization organizations, and any national conflicting standard is withdrawn. This means the national catalogues of standards have a big level of coherence across Europe.

The national standardization organizations of the countries of the TERRAVISION partners are shown below.

Table 1. National standards bodies from TERRAVISION project partner's countries.

Country	Logo	Name
Belgium		Bureau voor Normalisatie/Bureau de Normalisation
Greece		Hellenic Organization for Standardization

Germany		Deutsches Institut für Normung
Italy		Ente Italiano di Normazione
Norway		Standard Norge
Spain		Asociación Española de Normalización - UNE

2.5 Standardization documents

Standardization organizations develop different types of documents, which have different levels of consensus and drafting timeframes.

The most widespread document is the “Standard”, a normative document developed and approved by the members of the organization according to strict consensus procedures. Other types of documents are Technical Specifications (TS), Technical Reports (TR) and Workshop Agreements (WA), which have lower level of consensus and a faster drafting timeframe. The latter kinds of documents can be further processed to become an International Standard if the market has reached a suitable level of consensus.

It is worth mentioning that many European Standards are also adopted as identical national standards by CEN-CENELEC Affiliates, which are the National Standards Bodies of 17 neighboring countries.

Table 2 shows the different kinds of documents developed by international, European and national standardization organizations and the main characteristics of them.

Table 2. Characteristics of different standardization documents.

Type	International code	European code	National code	Main characteristics
Standard	ISO IEC	EN	UNE, NF, BS, DIN, UNI, etc. When adopting: UNE-EN, NF-EN, UNE-ISO, NF-ISO etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Elaboration: between 18 and 36 months 2 (CEN/CENELEC) or 3 (ISO/IEC) steps of member approval European: compulsory national adoption Review: every 5 years Revision: whenever needed and as result from a systematic review
Technical Specification	ISO/TS IEC/TS	CEN/TS CLC/TS	When adopting: UNE-CEN/TS, NF-	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Elaboration: 21 months

Type	International code	European code	National code	Main characteristics
			CEN/TS, UNE-ISO/TS, NF-ISO/TS, etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 step of member approval or internal approval in TC • European: optional national adoption Review: after 3 years (upgrading to EN or deletion)
Technical Report	ISO/TR IEC/TR	CEN/TR CLC/TR	When adopting: UNE-CEN/TR, NF-CEN/TR, UNE-ISO/TR, NF-ISO/TR, etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Elaboration: free timeframe • Internal approval in TC • European: optional national adoption No review required
Workshop Agreement	IWA	CWA	Variable	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Elaboration: free timeframe (usually few months) • Internal approval in the Workshop • European: optional national adoption Review: after 3 years (upgrading to EN or deletion)

There is also an agreement established between European and International Organizations¹ to avoid duplication of efforts and promote global relevance of standards, which allows to adopt or develop in parallel each other's standards with the same content and code.

National standards can also be proposed as a base for new European or International standards. Figure 1 shows possible tracks of standards adoption.

¹ Between CEN and ISO it is called Vienna Agreement (VA); between CENELEC and IEC it is called Frankfurt Agreement (FA).

Figure 1. Possible tracks of standards adoption.

Regarding the nature of information covered by a standard, four types are defined:

- **Fundamental standards** - which concern terminology, conventions, signs and symbols, etc.
- **Test methods and analysis standards** - which measure characteristics such as temperature and chemical composition.
- **Specification standards** - which define characteristics of a product (product standards), or a service (service activities standards) and their performance thresholds such as fitness for use, interface and interoperability, health and safety, environmental protection, etc.
- **Organization standards** - which describe the functions and relationships of a company, as well as elements such as quality management and assurance, maintenance, value analysis, logistics, project or system management, production management, etc.

The analysis made to present the relevant standards/ standard under developments in this deliverable, include the four types of standards but with special focus on test methods and analysis standards and specification standards for the products covered by TERRAVISION project.

3. Methodology for the identification of relevant standardization areas

The approach followed in this report to identify the relevant standardization committees and applicable standards has been the following:

3.1 Identification of the relevant Technical Committees within European and International Standardization Organizations

Standardization is done by TCs which have a specific scope for their activities, i.e., the standards they can develop. The scope of the TCs is clearly defined so that there is no overlap with other TCs within the European or the international standardization organizations. However, there are European and international TCs with a similar scope. Agreements between these organizations avoid duplication as far as possible and organize cooperation.

TCs consist of working groups (WG) and/or subcommittees (SC) with own working groups (WG), respectively. Standardization work is developed within the working groups by experts being representatives of the industry, public administrations, NGOs, laboratories/test facilities as well as end users and other stakeholders. These experts are delegated by their national mirror committees or by external organizations with liaison status with the respective TC to participate in the technical work.

The first step has been the identification of those TCs with a scope related to the objectives and tasks of the TERRAVISION project.

3.2 Identification of applicable standards within the relevant European and International technical committees.

Although the scope of a TC may be related to the activities of the TERRAVISION project, the whole standards catalogue of the TC won't be applicable since the scope of the TCs is usually wider than the scope of the project activities.

Relevant standards, i.e., standards, technical specifications, and technical reports, within each identified TC were identified based on the objectives and tasks of TERRAVISION.

As stated above, TCs on European and international level having a similar scope of activities may develop standards together. It is also possible that a European technical committee adopted an international standard after its development and publication by an international standardization organization. Those standards can be identified by their code starting with "EN ISO" or "EN IEC".

European equivalents to international standards have been identified as well as purely European standards.

4. Relevant committees, standards and projects of standards for TERRAVISION

4.1 Overview on relevant standardization landscape

4.1.1 Relevant technical committees

A total of 45 technical standardization committees were identified, being TCs from CEN, CENELEC, ISO and IEC, see Table 3. To provide a better overview, the TCs were clustered into the following 10 areas:

- Mining
- Materials
- Production and processing
- Analysis and testing
- Safety aspects
- Geo-information and data management
- Application
- Environment
- Market analysis
- Waste Management

This categorization is only for the sake of clarity and does not provide any information or specifications as to how the standards of the respective TCs are to be used.

Table 3. Overview on relevant TCs.

Area	Technical committees
Mining	ISO/TC 82 "Mining"
	ISO/TC 182 "Geotechnics"
	ISO/TC 127 "Earth-moving machinery"
	CEN/TC 341 "Geotechnical Investigation and Testing" (Parallel work with ISO/TC 182)
	CEN/TC 288 "Execution of special geotechnical works"
Materials	IEC/TC 68 "Magnetic alloys and steels"
	ISO/TC 79 "Light metals and their alloys"
	ISO/TC 102 "Iron ore and direct reduced iron"
	ISO/TC 132 "Ferroalloys"
	ISO/TC 298 "Rare earth"
	ISO/PC 348 "Sustainable raw materials"
	CEN/TC 472 "Rare earth"
	CEN/TC 477 "Sustainable production of mineral and metal raw materials from mining and recycling"
Production processing and	ISO/TC 119 "Powder metallurgy"
	ISO/TC 195 "Building construction machinery and equipment"
	ISO/TC 127 "Earth-moving machinery"
	CEN/TC 151 "Construction equipment and building material machines – Safety"
	CEN/TC 458 "Industrial rotating mixing systems"
	IEC/TC 65 "Industrial-process measurement, control and automation"
	IEC/TC 27 "Industrial electroheating and electromagnetic processing"
Analysis and testing	ISO/TC 24 "Particle characterization including sieving"
	IEC/TC 85 "Measuring equipment for electrical and electromagnetic quantities"
	ISO/TC 164 "Mechanical testing of metals"
	ISO/TC 156 "Corrosion of metals and alloys"
Safety aspects	ISO/TC 199 "Safety of Machinery"
	CEN/TC 114 "Safety of Machinery"
	CEN/TC 305 "Potentially explosive atmospheres"
	IEC/TC 31 "Equipment for explosive atmospheres"
	IEC/TC 106 "Methods for the assessment of electric, magnetic and electromagnetic fields associated with human exposure"
	CEN/TC 186 "Industrial thermoprocessing – Safety"
Geo-information and data management and	ISO/TC 211 "Geographic information/Geomatics"
	CEN/TC 287 "Geographic Information"
	CEN/CLC/JTC 25 "Data management, Dataspaces, Cloud and Edge"
	ISO/TC 46/SC 11 "Archives/records management"
	ISO/TC 20/SC 13 "Space data and information transfer systems"
	CEN/TC 471 "Unmanned aircraft systems"
	ISO/TC 20/SC 16 "Uncrewed aircraft system"
Application	IEC/TC 51 "Magnetic components, ferrite & magnetic powder"
Environment	ISO/TC 323 "Circular economy"
	CEN/TC 473 "Circular economy"
	CEN/TC 406 "Mechanical products – Ecodesign methodology"
	IEC/TC 111 "Environmental standardization for electrical and electronic products and systems"
	CEN/CLC JTC 10 "Material efficiency aspects for products in scope of Ecodesign legislation "

	ISO/TC 207 "Environmental management"
Market analysis	ISO/TC 225 "Market, opinion and social research"
Waste Management	CLC/TC 111X "Environment"

4.2 Areas and Relevant technical committees

4.2.1 Mining

4.2.1.1 ISO/TC 82 "Mining"

The objective of ISO TC 82 is to develop standards for the following fields in mining activities:

- specifications relating to specialized mining machinery and equipment used in opencast mines (e.g. conveyors, high wall miners, rock drill rigs and continuous surface miners) and all underground mining machinery and equipment for the extraction of solid mineral substances [e.g. road headers, continuous miners, rock drill rigs, raise boring machines, high wall miners, LHDs, mining auger boring machines, RMDSs (rapid mine development systems);
- recommended practice in the presentation of plans and drawings used in mine surveying;
- methods of calculation of mineral reserves;
- sustainable mining and mine closure;
- design of structures for mining industry;
- special refuge/rescue chambers;
- shaft boring machines.

The following aspects are excluded:

- foundation machines [e.g. piling, diaphragm walling, earth boring, jetting, grouting, drill rigs for soil and rock mixture (ISO/TC 195)];
- aggregate processing machines (e.g. screening, crushing);
- equipment and protective systems to be used in explosive atmospheres (IEC/TC 31);
- hand-held rock drills (ISO/TC 118);
- earth-moving machinery (by ISO/TC 127);
- geotechnics (ISO/TC 182);
- tunnel boring machines (TBMs) and associated machines and equipment (ISO/TC 195).

The standards apply to mining activities and include the following topics:

- Sustainable mining and mine closure (ISO/TC 82 SC7)
- Advanced automated mining systems (ISO/TC 82 SC8)
- Remote stop function for mining equipment, Reference framework and architecture for advanced automation and autonomy, specification of interoperability of teleoperated, autonomous, and manned mining equipment, Rock drill rigs ISO/TC 82 JWG (ISO/TC 82 — ISO/TC 127)
- Structures for mine shafts ISO/TC 82 WG 4
- Terminology ISO/TC 82 WG 8

- Operator enclosures ISO/TC 82 WG 9
- Mine hoists and mine winders ISO/TC 82 WG 10
- Mining methods ISO/TC 82 WG 11
- Mine Cable Hook (ISO/TC 82 WG 12)

4.2.1.2 ISO/TC 182 “Geotechnics”

The objective of ISO/TC 182 is to develop standards of geotechnical aspects in the field of building and civil engineering, including (related) properties of soil and rock.

More precisely the objective of ISO/TC 182 is elaboration of standards on:

- Monitoring in Geotechnical Engineering (ISO/TC 182 WG 2)
- Drilling and sampling methods and groundwater measurements (ISO/TC 182 WG 4)
- Cone and piezocone penetration tests (ISO/TC 182 WG 7)
- Borehole expansion tests (ISO/TC 182 WG 8)
- Geotechnical aspects of geophysical methods (ISO/TC 182 WG 9)
- Laboratory testing of rocks (ISO/TC 182 WG 10)
- Static testing of geotechnical structures (ISO/TC 182 WG 11)
- Standardization in geophysics (ISO/TC 182 WG 12)
- Laboratory testing of soils (ISO/TC 182 WG 13)

4.2.1.3 ISO/TC 127 “Earth-moving machinery”

The work of TC 127 is important because to achieve full global trade with limited volumes of machines it is absolutely imperative to have global standards. The basic objectives of TC 127 are to provide the portfolio of standards for earth-moving machinery to support the manufacturers need for global trade, this committee develop standards of nomenclature, use classification, ratings, technical requirements and test methods, safety requirements, operation, maintenance manual format for earth-moving and related machinery.

The standards apply to earth-moving machinery and include the following topics:

- Test methods relating to safety and machine performance (ISO/TC 127SC 1)
- Safety, ergonomics and general requirements (ISO/TC 127SC 2)
- Machine characteristics, electrical and electronic systems, operation and maintenance (ISO/TC 127SC 3)
- Terminology, commercial nomenclature, classification and ratings (ISO/TC 127SC 4)
- Overlap and differences in the work for traction batteries between TC 127 and TC 82
- ISO Off-Road Mobile Work Machine (ISO/TC 127 SG 1)
- Sustainability (ISO/TC 127 WG8)
- Rechargeable Energy Storage System (RESS) application for EMM (ISO/TC 127 WG17)
- Joint ISO/TC 82 — ISO/TC 127 WG : Rock drill rigs

4.2.1.4 CEN/TC 341 “Geotechnical Investigation and Testing” (Parallel work with ISO/TC 182)

The aim of this committee is standardisation in the field of geotechnical investigation and testing relates to equipment and methods used for drilling, sampling, field and laboratory testing of rock and soil as well as groundwater measurements as part of the ground and site investigation services industry.

The goal of standardisation work is to harmonise the requirements for equipment and methods to achieve comparable results whenever standardised equipment is used and standardised methods are applied, ensuring high quality of the results is achieved.

Manufacturers and users of equipment and methods for geotechnical investigation and testing should find European standards valuable for common use as they enable comparable results to be obtained and should reduce the variability of the results of geotechnical data which are the basis for the geotechnical design according to EN 1997 "Eurocode 7: Geotechnical Design".

European standards for investigation and testing are important for the safety of all structures from houses to high rise buildings, for roads, bridges, canals, railways, airfields, harbours, tunnels, sewers and communication lines and other structures such as dams and earthworks.

These European standards also facilitate the development of a common European market for the trade of services and equipment for geotechnical investigation and testing. The standardisation in the field of geotechnical investigation and testing will also lead to the potential for cost reduction in the building market.

4.2.1.5 CEN/TC 288 “Execution of special geotechnical works”

CEN/TC 288 is responsible for standardization in the field of special geotechnical works of procedure and control methods and for the required material properties for execution only.

Executions of special geotechnical works represent an important market in Europe and worldwide. The need of common normative references rose from the beginning of the 1990s to improve cooperation and harmonization between all parties involved and to ensure their correct application for the safety and the lasting quality of the foundations of Building and civil Engineering works.

The additional technics and technologies were included in the scope of the technical committee in order to reflect all in ground construction techniques.

CEN/TC 288 works in accordance with the evolution of design standards such as Eurocodes and testing standards from the field.

4.2.2 Materials

4.2.2.1 IEC/TC 86 “Magnetic alloys and steels “

The objective of IEC/TC 68 is to prepare international standards relating to the magnetic and other physical properties of alloys and steels which are relevant to their electrotechnical usage.

The fields covered for this IEC TC 86 are:

- Classification of magnetic materials and specifications for electrical steels and iron-based amorphous materials WG 1
- Measurement methods for soft and feebly magnetic materials WG 2
- Magnetic alloys of iron-nickel, iron-cobalt, iron-aluminium and iron-aluminium-silicon WG 4
- Specifications and measurement methods for hard magnetic materials WG 5
- Pulse-Field-Magnetometry measurement method for permanent magnets AHG6

4.2.2.2 ISO/TC 79 “Light metals and their alloys“

The main activity of ISO/TC 79 “Light metals and their alloys”, is the standardization for the various products forms of aluminium, magnesium, titanium and their respective alloys. This standardization covers:

- The designations for aluminium and aluminium alloys;
- The temper designations for aluminium and aluminium alloys;
- Terms and definitions;
- Material specifications;
- Technical conditions of delivery;
- Tolerances on dimensions and form;
- Methods of testing specific to aluminium.
- ISO/TC 79 is organized by Sub-Committee:
- ISO/TC 79/SC 2 Organic and anodic oxidation coatings on aluminium
- ISO/TC 79/SC 4 Unalloyed (refined) aluminium ingots
- ISO/TC 79/SC 5 Magnesium and alloys of cast or wrought magnesium
- ISO/TC 79/SC 6 Wrought aluminium and aluminium alloys
- ISO/TC 79/SC 7 Aluminium and cast aluminium alloys
- ISO/TC 79/SC 9 Symbolization
- ISO/TC 79/SC 11 Titanium
- ISO/TC 79/SC 12 Aluminium ores

4.2.2.3 ISO/TC 102 “Iron ore and direct reduced iron “

The primary mission of TC102 is to provide international standards that are equitable and practical for the many countries involved in the international trade of iron ores and DRI, including terminology and methods of sampling, preparation of samples, moisture determination, size determination, chemical analysis and physical testing.

The main fields covered by this TC are sampling, chemical analysis and physical testing (ISO/TC102/SC 1)

4.2.2.4 ISO/TC 132 “Ferroalloys “

ISO/TC132 covers standardization in the field of ferroalloys and other alloying additives used in the relevant. Excluded: standardization of ferronickels which devolves upon ISO / TC 155.

The current main subject in the development of ISO standards in ISO/TC132 is to improve the market relevancy of ISO standards developed or to be developed within ISO/TC132 and to promote the application of ISO

standards in the international trade. The benefits of standardization, such as cost reduction and a speedier distribution of products, is expected.

More precisely the objective of ISO/TC 132 is elaboration of standards on:

- Vanadium-nitrogen — Specification and conditions of delivery (ISO/TC 132/SG 1)
- Chromium ores and concentrates — Determination of chromium content — Titrimetric method (ISO/TC 132/WG3)
- Ferrotitanium— Determination of titanium content— Titrimetric method (ISO/TC 132/WG4)

4.2.2.5 ISO/TC 298 “Rare earth“

ISO/TC 298 aims to establish standards in the field of rare earth mining, concentration, extraction, separation and conversion to useful rare earth compounds/materials (including oxides, salts, metals, master alloys, etc.) which are key inputs to manufacturing and further production process in a safe and environmentally sustainable manner.

The following fields are covered by this TC 298:

- Sustainability (ISO/TC 298/JWG6)
- Elements recycling (ISO/TC 298/WG2)
- Traceability, Packaging and Labelling (ISO/TC 298/WG3)
- Testing and Analysis (ISO/TC 298/WG4)

4.2.2.6 ISO/PC 348 “Sustainable raw materials “

ISO TC 348 is developed a document to stablish criteria for sustainable raw materials along industry best practices and is intended to be used for mineral-, raw iron- and non-iron-metals. It is applicable to the full value chain of all raw materials, from extraction (mining) to processing, to refining, to final product manufacturing, thereby including the full upstream and downstream value chain. It does not apply to the mine closure and/or mine reclamation stage activities as these stages are not considered integral parts of the value chain.

This International committee currently has no work programme.

4.2.2.7 CEN/TC 472 “Rare earth elements “

CEN TC 472 aims to establish standards in the field of REE mining, concentration, extraction, separation and conversion to useful REE compounds/materials (including oxides, salts, metals, master alloys, etc.) which are key inputs to manufacturing and further production process.

In addition to test methods and terminology, aspects such as sustainability, traceability, and recycling are covered.

This European committee currently does not have its own working programme working program, as it monitors the activities being conducted by ISO/TC 298.

4.2.2.8 CEN/TC 477 "Sustainable production of mineral and metal raw materials from mining and recycling"

CEN TC 477 aims to stablish All aspects of standardization for sustainability in:

- the production of mineral and metal raw materials from primary and secondary sources;
- the value chain from extraction or recycling, treatment, smelting, to refining;
- the mine life cycle from exploration, construction, operation to mine closure, reclamation, and post-closure.

Sustainability aspects include environmental, social, economic and governance issues, and may also include carbon- and environmental footprint, circularity, material efficiency and traceability.

Excluded: – Energy raw materials, i.e. coal, oil and gas – Aspects covered by CEN/TC 472 ‘Rare earth’,

This European committee currently has no work programme,

4.2.3 Production and processing

4.2.3.1 ISO/TC 119 “Powder metallurgy“

The scope of ISO/TC 119 is the standardization of Powder Metallurgical materials concerning terms and definitions, sampling, testing methods and materials specifications. The objective of ISO/TC 119 is to facilitate the timely development and maintenance of quality, market relevant, material test methods and standards for the global powder metallurgical industry.

4.2.3.2 CEN/TC 458 “Industrial rotating mixing systems“

CEN TC 458 aims to stablish standards in the field of industrial rotating mixing systems, where the continuous phase is a liquid, excluding domestic equipment, static mixers, submersible mixers, agitators used for kneading, aerators and pumps.

4.2.3.3 IEC/TC 65 “Industrial-process measurement, control and automation“

IEC/TC 65 aims to establish standards for systems and elements used for industrial process measurement, control and automation. To coordinate standardization activities which affect integration of components and functions into such systems including safety and security aspects. This work of standardization is to be carried out in the international fields for equipment and systems.

TC 65 has a Cybersecurity horizontal function in accordance with IEC Guide 108, defined as follows: Cybersecurity for Operational Technologies which includes:

- The whole lifecycle from design to disposal (including supply chain, etc.).
- Technical, organizational and procedural requirements.
- Components, subsystems and systems.

4.2.3.4 IEC/TC 27 “Industrial electroheating and electromagnetic processing”

This committee develops standards in the field of industrial equipment and installations intended for electroheating, electromagnetic processing of materials and electroheat based treatment technologies.

The scope of interest covers industrial installations with the use of the following equipment:

- equipment for direct and indirect resistance heating;
- equipment for electric resistance trace heating; - equipment for induction heating;
- equipment using the effect of EM forces on materials;
- equipment for arc heating, including submerged arc heating;
- equipment for electroslag remelting;
- equipment for plasma heating;
- equipment for microwave heating;
- equipment for dielectric heating;
- equipment for electron beam heating;
- equipment for laser heating;
- equipment for infrared radiation heating.

The list presents typical examples of equipment and its applications and is not exhaustive.

4.2.4 Analysis and testing

4.2.4.1 ISO/TC 24 “Particle characterization including sieving”

The scope of ISO/TC 24 covers standardization pertaining to equipment and methods used in characterization or size classification of particulate material, where particles may be considered to include grains, flakes, fibres, droplets, bubbles or pores from the nanometer to the millimeter scale.

Covering the following:

- Particle and particle ensemble characterization, mainly by determination of physical properties of the particles including, for example, size distribution, particle shape and morphology, weight, density, surface area or porosity, and mobility.
- Particle systems characterization comprises particle-fluid and particle-particle interactions in suspensions, emulsions, aerosols or powders by determining their properties including concentration, electric charge, zeta potential, state of agglomeration, stability and rheology.
- Test sieves, sieving methods and industrial screens.

Each of the above areas will comprise standardization in the field of laboratory or process environment including terminology, reference materials, guidance for sampling, sample preparation, interpretation of results and uncertainty determination.

There is no work in CEN, but CEN is referring to standards prepared by ISO/TC 24. In the field of nanotechnologies SC 4 supports standardization coordination within the liaison to ISO/TC 229 and to CEN/TC 352, e. g. concerning mandate M/461 of the European Commission.

4.2.4.2 IEC/TC 85 “Measuring equipment for electrical and electromagnetic quantities “

The objective of IEC TC 85 is to develop standards for equipment, systems, and methods used in the fields of measurement, test, recurrent test, monitoring, evaluation, generation and analysis of steady state and dynamic (including temporary and transients) electrical and electromagnetic quantities, as well as their calibrators.

Such equipment includes devices for testing the safety of power distribution systems and connected equipment, devices for monitoring the power distribution systems, electrical measuring transducers, signal generators, recorders together with their accessories.

4.2.4.3 ISO/TC 164 “Mechanical testing of metals“

The aim of TC 164 is to develop unique international standard testing methods that can provide rational and reliable mechanical property data in order to facilitate clear and easy technical judgement and business decision-making in international trade through the provision of a common international scale. The scope covers standardization of methods for mechanical testing, including the verification and calibration of equipment, that are used to determine the properties of metallic materials.

Excluded :

- the responsibility for application of the method and for the results obtained.

4.2.4.4 ISO/TC 156 “Corrosion of metals and alloys“

ISO/TC 156 is responsible for standardization in the field of corrosion of metals and alloys including corrosion test methods, corrosion prevention methods and corrosion control engineering life cycle. General coordination of activities in these fields within ISO.

4.2.5 Safety aspects

4.2.5.1 ISO/TC 199 “Safety of machinery“

The main activity of ISO/TC 199 is standardisation of general principles for safety of machinery incorporating terminology and methodology. This ISO TC 199 develops standards of basic concepts and general principles for safety of machinery incorporating terminology, methodology, guards and safety devices within the framework of ISO / IEC Guide 51 and in cooperation with other ISO and IEC TCs.

Excluded:

- product safety standards, as defined in ISO / IEC Guide 51, and which are explicitly covered by the work of other ISO or IEC TCs.
- The main objectives and priorities in the work of the committee are to elaborate International Documents related to:
 - basic concepts and general principles for design of machinery;
 - principles for risk assessment and risk reduction;
 - fundamental safety issues regarding e.g. safety distances, whole body access, two-hand controls, emergency stops, interlocking devices and guards;
 - hygiene requirements for the design of machinery.

4.2.5.2 CEN/TC 114 “Safety of machinery“

The main aim of work of CEN/TC 114 is to develop basic and group machinery safety standards related to general principles for safety of machinery incorporating terminology and methodology.

4.2.5.3 CEN/TC 305 “Potentially explosive atmospheres — Explosion prevention and protection“

The main goal of TC 305 is developing standards where necessary in the fields of:

- test methods for determining the flammability characteristics (ignition, propagation, explosion effects, etc.) of substances;
- equipment and protective systems for use in potentially explosive atmospheres and equipment and systems for explosion prevention and protection.

4.2.5.4 IEC/TC31 “Equipment for explosive atmospheres“

The main objective of TC 31 is to prepare and maintain international standards relating to equipment for use where there is a hazard due to the possible presence of explosive atmospheres of gases, vapours, mists or combustible dusts.

4.2.5.5 IEC/TC 106 “Methods for the assessment of electric, magnetic and electromagnetic fields associated with human exposure“

The main objective of TC 106 is to prepare international standards on measurement and calculation methods to assess human exposure to electric, magnetic and electromagnetic fields.

The task includes: characterisation of the electromagnetic environments with regard to human exposure; – measurement methods, instrumentation and procedures; – calculation methods; – assessment methods for the exposure produced by specific sources (in so far as this task is not carried out by specific product committees); – basic standards for other sources; – assessment of uncertainties. It covers the whole frequency range from 0 Hz to 300 GHz. It applies to basic restrictions and reference levels.

Excluded are: – the establishment of exposure limits (see AC/38/2009 of 2009-11-27); – mitigation methods which have to be dealt with by the relevant product committees; – electrical safety (however, the issue of contact current related to the indirect effect of human exposure to electromagnetic fields is included).

4.2.5.6 CEN/TC 186 “Industrial thermoprocessing — Safety“

Standardization in the field of safety of equipment for industrial thermoprocessing equipment (for example industrial furnaces or kilns and industrial heating equipment) in the field such as: -Metallurgical and metal working plant; in the fields of: 1. Thermal Production; 2. Melting, Pouring; 3. Heating; 4. Heat treatment; 5. Surface treatment; 6. Coating; 7. Joining; 8. Surface treatment. — Glass making plant; — Ceramic manufacturing plant; — Chemical plant; — Waste incineration equipment. And heated by: — Gaseous fuels; — Liquid fuels; — Mixed fuels; — Electricity. Blast furnaces, converters (in steel plants) , boilers, welding machines and food processing equipment are excluded.

4.2.6 Geo-information and data management

4.2.6.1 ISO/TC 211 “Geographic information/Geomatics”

Geospatial or location technology has been going mainstream for some years now. Maps, geographic information, and related content are becoming more pervasive and embedded in everyday life. Continued major investments from large players like Google, Microsoft, Apple and Amazon are making consumer-based mapping, location-based service applications and image-based maps truly ubiquitous. As the consumerization of technology increases, the focus will be more on providing value and return on investment to users. Major international organisations such as the United Nations increasingly recognise the value of standards based geographic information to equip nations to improve sustainability, resilience, and wellbeing.

The scope of ISO/TC 211 is very wide targeting several key segments:

- modelling and documentation of geographic information,
- making geographic information easier to find, access, and integrate through web services

- embedding of geographic information in everyday life – ubiquitous geographic information,
- some specific subject domains where geographic information is an important component and where multiple disciplines are involved.

The standards developed by ISO/TC 211 actively contribute to authoritative, evidence-based decisions in any field involving geographic or location content. Standards provide a platform for innovation.

The plan for the coming years includes delivering:

- a sustainable maintenance of the ISO geodetic registry (with the United Nations and the International Association of Geodesy),
- a coherent multi-part standard for different aspects of land and marine administration (with Open Geospatial Consortium, the International Federation of Surveyors, International Hydrographic Organization, and others),
- a revised classification meta language to facilitate merging land cover and land use data from different national systems (with UN Food and Agriculture Organization),
- ontologies to support our standards that are published more in line with web good practice,
- in total between 10 and 15 geographic information technology standards which will have been revised.

Furthermore, the plan is to initiate:

- work on calibration and validation of remote sensing data and derived products, which e.g. will help government design data quality policy and regulation to achieve high quality data and products (WG 6),
- revision of further web service standards based upon contemporary API design principles, in close cooperation with OGC,
- further work in support of specific domains such as digital twins, in collaboration with relevant ISO and ISO/IEC committees.

4.2.6.2 CEN/TC 287 “Geographic Information”

This committee covers the standardisation in the field of digital geographic information for Europe. The committee produces a structured framework of standards and guidelines, which specify a methodology to define, describe and transfer geographic data and services.

This work is being carried out in close co-operation with ISO/TC 211 in order to avoid duplication of work. The standards support the consistent use of geographic information throughout Europe in a manner that is compatible with international usage. They also support a spatial data infrastructure at all levels in Europe.

4.2.6.3 CEN/CLC/JTC 25 “Data management, Dataspaces, Cloud and Edge”

CEN/CLC JTC 25 develops deliverables for Data Management, Dataspaces, Cloud and Edge in conjunction with the European Trusted Data Framework, based on but not limited to standards on:

- Management of data rights;
- access rights management, information;
- interoperability (technical, semantic, behaviour, policy);
- data processing, data exchange protocols, and data formats;
- data processing in the cloud and on the edge;
- Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) for interoperability of data assets and data products management and searchability; and
- data sharing system while ensuring cross-sectoral and cross-system interoperability.

Sector-specific standards are excluded and will be made in the respective TCs (CEN-CENELEC, ISO-IEC- ITU TCs) covering the sectors . Further exclusions include deliverables already covered by the scope of other CEN and CENELEC TCs and the definition of the content of data belonging to different product types or segments.

JTC 25 aims to support standardisation needs of the European data economy given their strategic importance in EU digital single market

4.2.6.4 ISO/TC 46/SC 11 “Archives/records management”

The ISO Subcommittee ISO TC 46/SC 11, responsible for standards related to managing records, information and archives, has published several products related to our work. The main publication is ISO 15489 Records management - Principles and concepts.

In addition, ISO TC 46/SC 11 has developed the ISO 30300 series, which focuses on records management systems. This series includes ISO 30301, ISO 30302, and ISO 30303. They provide guidance on implementing a records management system, managing metadata for records, and implementing digital records management systems, respectively.

The Subcommittee has also created other technical reports, such as ISO/TR 26122, which guides the management of metadata for records, and ISO/TR 18128, which offers guidance on managing electronic records.

The Subcommittee's working groups are currently involved in several ongoing projects. One notable project focuses on exploring the potential applications of blockchain technology in records management. It aims to address aspects like authenticity, integrity, and long-term preservation of records.

Another project aims to develop a new ISO standard for risk assessment in records of processes and systems. This standard will replace the existing Technical Report and adopt some text from ISO/TR 18128-2014.

There is also a project that focuses on determining retention and disposition requirements for records. It will identify and address issues related to the disposition of records and propose a technical specification.

A working group is reviewing issues and considerations for managing records in structured data environments. This project will provide an overview of records management in structured environments and suggest recommendations for addressing problems.

Furthermore, ISO TC 46/SC 11 is working on a project that focuses on managing records in cloud computing environments. It aims to develop guidelines and recommendations for effectively managing records in cloud-based systems, considering the unique challenges and opportunities associated with cloud computing.

4.2.6.5 ISO/TC 20/SC 13 “Space data and information transfer systems”

ISO/TC 20 is a technical committee of the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) responsible for developing internationally accepted standards for aircraft and space vehicles. This covers standards for the materials, components and equipment used to both develop and maintain them, including:

- Design
- Construction
- Test and evaluation
- Operation
- Air traffic management
- Maintenance
- Disposal/end of life
- Safety, reliability and environmental considerations

4.2.6.6 CEN/TC 471 "Unmanned aircraft systems"

The objective of this technical committee is the standardization in the field of unmanned aircraft systems (UAS) including, but not limited to, classification, design, manufacture, operation and safety management of UAS operations, with the exclusion of those fields of activities covered by CEN/TCs 274, 377 and 436

4.2.6.7 ISO/TC 20/SC 16, Uncrewed aircraft system

This subcommittee of ISO/TC 20, covers the standardization in the field of advanced air mobility and uncrewed aircraft systems (UAS), including but not limited to classification, design, manufacture, operation (including maintenance), and safety management.

4.2.7 Application

4.2.7.1 IEC/TC 51 “Magnetic components, ferrite and magnetic powder materials”

The objective of this TC is to prepare standards relating to:

- parts and components displaying magnetic properties and intended for electronics in a wide range of application areas, including telecommunications, computers, automotive, aircraft, audio-visual, digital camera, lighting, solar and wind power systems, welding, inductive heating, power conditioning (UPS), wireless charging, RFID and medical;
- parts associated with such components;
- measuring methods and tests, and specifications for transformers and inductors using such components;
- ferrite and magnetic powder materials.

4.2.8 Environment

4.2.8.1 ISO/TC 323 “Circular economy“

This committee works on standardization in the field of Circular Economy to develop frameworks, guidance, supporting tools and requirements for the implementation of activities of all involved organizations, to maximize the contribution to Sustainable Development.

The 5 objectives of the TC and strategies for their achievements are:

- Objective 1: To develop standards that support and encourage organizations to adopt circular economy through a time-efficiency process
- Objective 2: To promote an alternative and collaborative economic model that is more sustainable and facilitate the transition towards circular economy
- Objective 3: To promote a broad and effective participation from countries all around the world and encourage organizations and its representatives to adopt a circular mindset
- Objective 4: To maximize the contribution to Sustainable Development
- Objective 5: To develop high quality standard for all types of stakeholders

4.2.8.2 CEN/TC 473 “Circular economy“

The main objective of CEN/TC 473 is to develop standards in the field of Circular Economy to develop horizontal standards that address European specific prerequisites, legislation, and policy. The standards aim to provide guidance, recommendations, requirements, methodologies and tools to implement, support and measure transition towards a Circular Economy at an organizational level. The deliverables aim to complement international and European standardization in the advancement in the transition towards a Circular Economy, while contributing to sustainable development. The work aligns with, but does not duplicate, activities falling into the scope of other TCs*. The Technical Committee will promote and maintain open communication and active collaboration with all relevant committees.

This committee covers the following fields of activity:

- Circular Economy Terminology, Framework & Principles (TC 473/WG 1)
- Information sharing (CEN/TC 473/WG 2)
- Extended Producer Responsibility (CEN/TC 473/WG 3)

- Circular Business Models (CEN/TC 473/WG 4)

4.2.8.3 CEN/TC 406 “Mechanical products — Eco-design methodology”

This committee works on Eco-design methodology for Industrial machinery excluding Machinery for the production and use of mechanical power

4.2.8.4 EC/TC 111 “Environmental standardization for electrical and electronic products and systems”

IEC Technical Committee (TC) 111 prepares horizontal International Standards which are key in helping to ensure electrical and electronic products are designed with the environment in mind. The main objective is develop standards of environmental aspects concerns:

- To prepare the necessary guidelines, basic and horizontal standards, including technical reports, in the environmental area, in close cooperation with product committees of IEC, which remain autonomous in dealing with the environmental aspects relevant to their products;
- To liaise with product committees in the elaboration of environmental requirements of product standards in order to foster common technical approaches and solutions for similar problems and thus assure consistency in IEC standards;
- To liaise with ACEA and ISO/TC 207;
- To monitor closely the corresponding regional standardization activities worldwide in order to become a focal point for discussions concerning standardization;
- EMC and EMF aspects are excluded from the scope.

4.2.8.5 CEN/CLC JTC 10 “Material efficiency aspects for products in scope of Ecodesign legislation”

This TC works on material efficiency aspects for products in scope of the Ecodesign Directive 2009/125/EC and its future revisions.

Producing generic and horizontal CEN-CENELEC publications covering aspects such as assessment methods, design rules, dematerialization, digitalization and transfer of information on a variety of material efficiency topics, in particular (but not limited to):

- Extending product lifetime
- Ability to reuse components or recycle materials* from products at End-of-Life
- Use of reused components and/or recycled materials* in products

* Includes coverage of the European Commission defined list of Critical Raw Materials (CRM).

In this context, CEN-CENELEC Joint Technical Committee 10 on Energy-related products - Material Efficiency Aspects for Ecodesign (CEN-CLC/JTC 10) developed a group of eight standards containing generic principles to consider when addressing the material efficiency of energy-related products, such as extending product lifetime, ability to reuse components or recycle materials from products at end-of-life, and use of reused components and/or recycled materials in products.

These horizontal standards developed by CEN-CLC/JTC 10 can be used by product-specific TCs when developing product-specific or product group standards addressing material efficiency aspects.

4.2.8.6 ISO/TC 207 “Environmental management“

ISO/TC 207 develops International Standards that respond to global environmental challenges and support achievement of a sustainable future. ISO/TC 207 has a key role to play in ensuring there are robust approaches to managing environmental impacts by supporting sustainability with widely used standards such as the overarching ISO 14001 framework that can be applied by topic and combined with a life-cycle approach (ISO 14040 series).

The main objective is to develop standards to address environmental and climate impacts, including related social and economic aspects, in support of sustainable development.

Excluded: test methods of pollutants, setting limit values and levels of environmental performance, and standardization of products.

The work of the six subcommittees of ISO/TC 207 is generally organized by themes, although there is some overlap between the work of the various subcommittees and their standards. As an example, ISO 14067 – Greenhouse gases – Carbon footprint of products – Requirements and guidelines for quantification, developed under SC 7 is a specific application case of the ISO 14040/14044 standards on life cycle assessment developed under SC 5.

4.2.9 Market analysis

4.2.9.1 ISO/TC 225 “Market, opinion and social research“

ISO/TC 225’s main objective is to support and encourage higher and more consistent levels of quality in the research carried out in the market, opinion and social research (MOSR) sector, by maintaining and promoting comprehensive quality standards, so this TC develop standards related requirements for organizations and professionals conducting market, opinion and social research.

4.2.10 Waste management

4.2.10.1 CLC/TC 111X “Environment“

The main goal of this committee is to deal with environmental aspects for electrical and electronic products and systems. To promote activities in CENELEC relevant to reducing detrimental impacts of electrotechnical activities/products/systems on the natural environment (In this context "reducing" means a process of continual environment improvement aimed towards an optimum balance with social, economic, safety and performance requirements). To enhance CENELEC's environmental links with the European legal framework, particularly in the context of standardization aspects of EU environmental regulations and directives. To improve energy and resource efficiency of electrotechnical products and systems as important aspects in order to reduce impacts on the environment (for example climate changes and resource depletion) To prepare the necessary standards

framework and in co-operation with other CENELEC Technical Bodies co-ordinate the development of, or when necessary, produce the needed standardization deliverables. Product TCs remain autonomous in dealing with environmental aspects relevant to the products included in their scope. To assist product committees in the elaboration of environmental requirements of product standards in order to foster common technical approaches and solutions for similar problems and thus promote consistency in CENELEC standards. To cooperate with recognized standardization bodies and other relevant organizations on matters of common environmental interest. To communicate with and to give advice to CENELEC BT and TCs on questions related to work on environmental issues. EMC and EMF aspects are excluded, but relevant developments will be noted.

4.3 Applicable standards and projects

4.3.1 General

In this clause, the various TCs and standards published to date with relevance to TERRAVISION's activities, as well as those under development (so-called projects), are presented.

In principle, the identification of standards was based on a broad understanding in order not to inadvertently discard possibly relevant standards.

The scopes of application of the individual standards are not indicated, as the titles of the documents in relation to the scope of application of the technical committee are already considered sufficient. For further information, please refer to the homepage of each committee. On request, UNE also provides the standards as full texts.

Table 4 lists the tables where applicable standards and projects for each technical committee could be found.

Table 4. STANDARDS and PROJECTS for each TC.

Table 5	<i>Standards from ISO/TC 82</i>
Table 6	<i>ISO/TC 82 Projects under development</i>
Table 7	<i>Standards from ISO/TC 182</i>
Table 8	<i>ISO/TC 182 Projects under development</i>
Table 9	<i>Standards from ISO/TC 127/SC 2</i>
Table 10	<i>ISO/TC 127SC 2 Projects under development</i>
Table 11	<i>Standards from CEN/TC 341</i>
Table 12	<i>CEN/TC 341 Projects under development</i>

Table 13	<i>Standards from CEN/TC 288</i>
Table 14	<i>CEN/TC 288 Projects under development</i>
Table 15	<i>Standards from IEC/TC 68</i>
Table 16	<i>IEC/TC 68 Projects under development</i>
Table 17	<i>Standards from ISO/TC 79</i>
Table 18	<i>ISO/TC 79 Projects under development</i>
Table 19	<i>Standards from ISO/TC 102</i>
Table 20	<i>ISO/TC 102 Projects under development</i>
Table 21	<i>Standards from ISO/TC 132</i>
Table 22	<i>ISO/TC 132 Projects under development</i>
Table 23	<i>Standards from ISO/TC 298</i>
Table 24	<i>ISO/TC 298 Projects under development</i>
Table 25	<i>Standards from ISO/TC 119</i>
Table 26	<i>ISO/TC 119 Projects under development</i>
Table 27	<i>Standards from CEN/TC 458</i>
Table 28	<i>Standards from IEC/TC 65</i>
Table 29	<i>IEC/TC 65 Projects under development</i>
Table 30	<i>Standards from IEC/TC 27</i>
Table 31	<i>IEC/TC 27 Projects under development</i>
Table 32	<i>Standards from ISO/TC 24</i>
Table 33	<i>ISO/TC 24 Projects under development</i>
Table 34	<i>Standards from IEC/TC 85</i>
Table 35	<i>IEC/TC 85 Projects under development</i>
Table 36	<i>Standards from ISO/TC 164</i>
Table 37	<i>ISO/TC 164 Projects under development</i>
Table 38	<i>Standards from ISO/TC 156</i>
Table 39	<i>ISO/TC 156 Projects under development</i>
Table 40	<i>Standards from ISO/TC 199</i>

Table 41	<i>ISO/TC 199 Projects under development</i>
Table 42	<i>Standards from CEN/TC 114</i>
Table 43	<i>CEN/TC 114 Projects under development</i>
Table 44	<i>Standards from CEN/TC 305</i>
Table 45	<i>CEN/TC 305 Projects under development</i>
Table 46	<i>Standards from IEC/TC 31</i>
Table 47	<i>IEC/TC 31 Projects under development</i>
Table 48	<i>Standards from IEC/TC 106</i>
Table 49	<i>IEC/TC 106 Projects under development</i>
Table 50	<i>Standards from CEN/TC 186</i>
Table 51	<i>CEN/TC 186 Projects under development</i>
Table 52	<i>Standards from IEC/TC 51</i>
Table 53	<i>IEC/TC 51 Projects under development</i>
Table 54	<i>Standards from ISO/TC 211</i>
Table 55	<i>ISO/TC 211 Projects under development</i>
Table 56	<i>Standards from CEN/TC 287</i>
Table 57	<i>CEN/TC 287 Projects under development</i>
Table 58	<i>CEN/CLC/JTC 25 Projects under development</i>
Table 59	<i>Standards from ISO/TC 46/SC 11</i>
Table 60	<i>ISO/TC 46/SC 11 Projects under development</i>
Table 61	<i>Standards from ISO/TC 20/SC 13</i>
Table 62	<i>CEN/TC 471 Projects under development</i>
Table 63	<i>Standards from ISO/TC 20/SC 16</i>
Table 64	<i>ISO/TC 20/SC 16 Projects under development</i>
Table 65	<i>Standards from ISO/TC 323</i>
Table 66	<i>ISO/TC 323 Projects under development</i>
Table 67	<i>Standards from CEN/TC 406</i>
Table 68	<i>CEN/TC 406 Projects under development</i>

Table 69	<i>Standards from IEC/TC 111</i>
Table 70	<i>IEC/TC 111 Projects under development</i>
Table 71	<i>Standards from CEN/CLC JTC10</i>
Table 72	<i>CEN/CLC JTC10 Projects under development</i>
Table 73	<i>Standards from ISO/TC 207</i>
Table 74	<i>ISO/TC 207 Projects under development</i>
Table 75	<i>Standards from ISO/TC 225</i>
Table 76	<i>ISO/TC 225 Projects under development</i>
Table 77	<i>Standards from CLC/TC 111X</i>
Table 78	<i>CLC/TC 111X Projects under development</i>

A full list of International (IEC, ISO) and European (CENELEC, CEN, ETSI) mature standards and coming standards (drafts) identified by UNE as relevant to TERRAVISION project can be found in Annex 1.

5. Conclusion

After the analysis of the current standardization context at European and international levels, the following conclusion may be drawn.

There are a large number of European and international TCs, as well as standards and project standards related to TERRAVISION project that may be useful for its development and also for its future dissemination. Although a specific standardization technical committee whose activity impacts directly on the TERRAVISION project has not been found, specific tasks to be addressed in the project are related to standardization works.

Depending on the assessment by TERRAVISION partners of the impact of the identified standardization committees on their tasks and the level of contribution that their results can represent for these committees, several actions can be performed.

With respect to the dissemination activities, all the TCs of this report are related to the TERRAVISION project, although probably the most relevant are those related to Geo-information and data management. Hence:

- ISO/TC 211 "Geographic information/Geomatics"
- CEN/TC 287 "Geographic Information"
- CEN/CLC/JTC 25 "Data management, Dataspaces, Cloud and Edge"
- ISO/TC 46/SC 11 "Archives/records management"
- ISO/TC 20/SC 13 "Space data and information transfer systems"
- CEN/TC 471 "Unmanned aircraft systems"
- ISO/TC 20/SC 16 "Uncrewed aircraft system"

Additionally, standards related to "Geotechnical Investigation and Testing" (CEN/TC 341 and ISO/TC 182), "Execution of special geotechnical works" (CEN/TC 288) and "Sustainable production of mineral and metal raw materials from mining and recycling (CEN/TC 477), could have impact and benefits to the project development.

The authors believe that the content of the report could be useful for TERRAVISION partners' profile and fields of work, but the above are considered as the most relevant.

UNE may provide specific standards of this report (or others needed), which could be useful for the development of TERRAVISION with appropriate justification.

Finally, this report represents the first step on the identification of gaps in standardization which the outputs of TERRAVISION could cover, and for the definition of standardization strategy to be developed in the next WP related to standardization.

6. Annex 1 – List of standards and projects relevant to TERRAVISION project

A full list of International (IEC, ISO) and European (CENELEC, CEN, ETSI) mature standards and coming standards (drafts) identified by UNE as relevant to TERRAVISION project can be found in the following.

Table 5. Standards from ISO/TC 82.

Reference	Title
ISO 610:1990	High-tensile steel chains (round link) for chain conveyors and coal ploughs
ISO 710-1:1974	Graphical symbols for use on detailed maps, plans and geological cross-sections — Part 1: General rules of representation
ISO 710-2:1974	Graphical symbols for use on detailed maps, plans and geological cross-sections — Part 2: Representation of sedimentary rocks
ISO 710-3:1974	Graphical symbols for use on detailed maps, plans and geological cross-sections — Part 3: Representation of magmatic rocks
ISO 710-4:1982	Graphical symbols for use on detailed maps, plans and geological cross-sections — Part 4: Representation of metamorphic rocks
ISO 710-5:1989	Graphical symbols for use on detailed maps, plans and geological cross-sections — Part 5: Representation of minerals
ISO 710-6:1984	Graphical symbols for use on detailed maps, plans and geological cross-sections — Part 6: Representation of contact rocks and rocks which have undergone metasomatic, pneumatolytic or hydrothermal transformation or transformation by weathering
ISO 710-7:1984	Graphical symbols for use on detailed maps, plans and geological cross-sections — Part 7: Tectonic symbols
ISO 721:1991	Rock drilling equipment — Integral stems
ISO 722:1991	Rock drilling equipment — Hollow drill steels in bar form, hexagonal and round
ISO 723:1991	Rock drilling equipment — Forged collared shanks and corresponding chuck bushings for hollow hexagonal drill steels
ISO 1082:1990	Mining — Shackle type connector units for chain conveyors
ISO 1717:1974	Rock drilling — Rotary drill-rods and rotary drill-bits for dry drilling — Connecting dimensions
ISO 1718:1991	Rock drilling equipment — Drill rods with tapered connection for percussive drilling
ISO 1721:1974	Rock drilling — Extension drill-steel equipment for percussive long-hole drilling — Reverse-buttress-threaded equipments 1 1/16 and 1 1/4 in (27 and 32 mm)
ISO 1722:1974	Rock drilling — Extension drill-steel equipment for percussive long-hole drilling — Reverse-buttress-threaded equipments 1 1/2 to 2 1/2 in (38 to 64 mm)
ISO 3154:1988	Stranded wire ropes for mine hoisting — Technical delivery requirements
ISO 3155:1976	Stranded wire ropes for mine hoisting — Fibre components — Characteristics and tests
ISO 3156:1976	Stranded wire ropes for mine hoisting — Impregnating compounds, lubricants and service dressings — Characteristics and tests
ISO 3551-1:1992	Rotary core diamond drilling equipment — System A — Part 1: Metric units
ISO 3551-2:1992	Rotary core diamond drilling equipment — System A — Part 2: Inch units
ISO 3552-1:1992	Rotary core diamond drilling equipment — System B — Part 1: Metric units
ISO 3552-2:1992	Rotary core diamond drilling equipment — System B — Part 2: Inch units
ISO 5612:1990	Mining — Scraper bars for chain conveyors
ISO 5613:1984	Mining — Drive sprocket assemblies for chain conveyors
ISO 5614:1988	Locked coil wire ropes for mine hoisting — Technical delivery requirements
ISO/TR 8865:1990	Mining — Guidance on methods of verifying dimensions of sprocket assemblies for chain conveyors
ISO 8866:1991	Rotary core diamond drilling equipment — System C
ISO 8866:1991/ Cor 2:1992	Rotary core diamond drilling equipment — System C — Technical Corrigendum 2
ISO 8866:1991/ Cor 1:1991	Rotary core diamond drilling equipment — System C — Technical Corrigendum 1
ISO 10097-1:1999	Wireline diamond core drilling equipment — System A — Part 1: Metric units
ISO 10097-2:1999	Wireline diamond core drilling equipment — System A — Part 2: Inch units
ISO 10098:1992	Wireline diamond core drilling equipment — System CSSK

ISO 10207:1991	Rock drilling equipment — Rope threaded drill steel equipment for percussive drilling, nominal sizes 22 mm to 38 mm
ISO 10207:1991/ Cor 1:1991	Rock drilling equipment — Rope threaded drill steel equipment for percussive drilling, nominal sizes 22 mm to 38 mm — Technical Corrigendum 1
ISO 10208:1991	Rock drilling equipment — Left-hand rope threads
ISO 18758-1:2018	Mining and earth-moving machinery — Rock drill rigs and rock reinforcement rigs — Part 1: Vocabulary
ISO 18758-2:2018	Mining and earth-moving machinery — Rock drill rigs and rock reinforcement rigs — Part 2: Safety requirements
ISO 19224:2017	Continuous surface miners (CSM) — Safety requirements
ISO 19225:2017	Underground mining machines — Mobile extracting machines at the face — Safety requirements for shearer loaders and plough systems
ISO 19225:2017/ Amd 1:2019	Underground mining machines — Mobile extracting machines at the face — Safety requirements for shearer loaders and plough systems — Amendment 1
ISO 19296:2018	Mining — Mobile machines working underground — Machine safety
ISO 19426-1:2018	Structures for mine shafts — Part 1: Vocabulary
ISO 19426-2:2018	Structures for mine shafts — Part 2: Headframe structures
ISO 19426-3:2018	Structures for mine shafts — Part 3: Sinking stages
ISO 19426-4:2018	Structures for mine shafts — Part 4: Conveyances
ISO 19426-5:2018	Structures for mine shafts — Part 5: Shaft system structures
ISO 19426-7:2021	Structures for mine shafts — Part 7: Rope guides
ISO 19434:2017	Mining — Classification of mine accidents
ISO 19434:2017/ Amd 1:2019	Mining — Classification of mine accidents — Amendment 1
ISO 20305:2020	Mine closure and reclamation — Vocabulary
ISO 21795-1:2021	Mine closure and reclamation planning — Part 1: Requirements
ISO 21795-2:2021	Mine closure and reclamation planning — Part 2: Guidance
ISO 22932-1:2020	Mining — Vocabulary — Part 1: Planning and surveying
ISO 22932-2:2020	Mining — Vocabulary — Part 2: Geology
ISO 22932-3:2023	Mining – Vocabulary — Part 3: Rock mechanics
ISO 22932-4:2023	Mining — Vocabulary — Part 4: Prospecting and exploration
ISO 22932-5:2023	Mining — Vocabulary — Part 5: Drilling and blasting
ISO 23725:2024	Autonomous system and fleet management system interoperability
ISO 23872:2021	Mining structures — Underground structures
ISO 23875:2021/ Amd 1:2022	Mining — Air quality control systems for operator enclosures — Performance requirements and test methods — Amendment 1
ISO 23875:2021	Mining — Air quality control systems for operator enclosures — Performance requirements and test methods
ISO 24419-1:2023	Mine closure and reclamation – Managing mining legacies — Part 1: Requirements and recommendations
ISO/TR 24419-2:2023	Mine closure and reclamation – Managing mining legacies — Part 2: Case studies and bibliography

Table 6. ISO/TC 82 Projects under development.

Project Reference	Title
ISO/CD TR 3502	Reference framework and architecture for advanced automation and autonomy
ISO/PWI 3510	Specification of interoperability of teleoperated, autonomous, and manned mining equipment
ISO/AWI 8238	Mine closure and reclamation — Social aspects
ISO/PWI 12848	Mine hoisting systems – Safety requirement
ISO/DIS 18758	Mining and earth-moving machinery — Rock drill rigs and rock reinforcement rigs — Safety requirements
ISO/CD 19426-1	Structures for mine shafts — Part 1: Vocabulary
ISO/CD 19426-2	Structures for mine shafts — Part 2: Headframe structures
ISO/CD 19426-3	Structures for mine shafts — Part 3: Sinking stages
ISO/WD 19426-4	Structures for mine shafts — Part 4: Conveyances
ISO/CD 19426-5	Structures for mine shafts — Part 5: Shaft system structures
ISO/WD 19426-6	Structures for mine shafts — Part 6: Design of shaft lining
ISO/AWI TS 20268	Inspection and Maintenance of Mine Shaft and Associated Structures
ISO/DIS 20305	Mine closure and reclamation — Vocabulary

ISO/AWI 21208	Mining — Operator enclosures — Performance requirements, testing, and operational integration of gas filtration
ISO/DIS 21557	Mining — Mining methods — Classification and Specification
ISO/DIS 22932-5	Mining — Vocabulary — Part 5: Drilling and blasting
ISO/PWI 22932-6	Mining — Vocabulary — Part 6: Mine hoisting systems
ISO/FDIS 22932-7	Mining — Vocabulary — Part 7: Ventilation
ISO/FDIS 22932-8	Mining — Vocabulary — Part 8: Extraction
ISO/FDIS 22932-9	Mining — Vocabulary — Part 9: Drainage
ISO/DIS 22932-10	Mining — Vocabulary — Part 10: Haulage
ISO/PWI 24171	Mobile machines — Vocabulary and classification/identification
ISO/PWI 24176	Roadheader – Safety Requirement
ISO/PWI 24177	Shaft borer – Safety requirements
ISO/PWI 24446	Blasthole drilling machinery- Electronic operation interface specification – Machine control interface
ISO/PWI 25412	Determination of the value of discarded natural materials in mining
ISO/AWI 25572	General technical requirements for mine cable hooks
ISO/PWI 25602	Guidance for maintenance of tailings storage facilities
ISO/NP 25603	Underground mine tailings backfill guidance
ISO/PWI 25604	Mine wastewater monitoring and assessment

Table 7. Standards from ISO/TC 182.

Reference	Title
ISO 14688-1:2017	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Identification and classification of soil — Part 1: Identification and description
ISO 14688-2:2017	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Identification and classification of soil — Part 2: Principles for a classification
ISO 14689:2017	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Identification, description and classification of rock
ISO 16383-1:2025	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Laboratory testing of rock — Part 1: Determination of water content
ISO 17628:2015	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Geothermal testing — Determination of thermal conductivity of soil and rock using a borehole heat exchanger
ISO 17892-1:2014	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Laboratory testing of soil — Part 1: Determination of water content
ISO 17892-1:2014/ Amd 1:2022	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Laboratory testing of soil — Part 1: Determination of water content — Amendment 1
ISO 17892-2:2014	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Laboratory testing of soil — Part 2: Determination of bulk density
ISO 17892-3:2015	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Laboratory testing of soil — Part 3: Determination of particle density
ISO 17892-4:2016	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Laboratory testing of soil — Part 4: Determination of particle size distribution
ISO 17892-5:2017	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Laboratory testing of soil — Part 5: Incremental loading oedometer test
ISO 17892-6:2017	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Laboratory testing of soil — Part 6: Fall cone test
ISO 17892-7:2017	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Laboratory testing of soil — Part 7: Unconfined compression test
ISO 17892-8:2018	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Laboratory testing of soil — Part 8: Unconsolidated undrained triaxial test
ISO 17892-9:2018	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Laboratory testing of soil — Part 9: Consolidated triaxial compression tests on water saturated soils
ISO 17892-10:2018	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Laboratory testing of soil — Part 10: Direct shear tests
ISO 17892-11:2019	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Laboratory testing of soil — Part 11: Permeability tests
ISO 17892-12:2018	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Laboratory testing of soil — Part 12: Determination of liquid and plastic limits
ISO 17892-12:2018/ Amd 2:2022	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Laboratory testing of soil — Part 12: Determination of liquid and plastic limits — Amendment 2
ISO 17892-12:2018/ Amd 1:2021	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Laboratory testing of soil — Part 12: Determination of liquid and plastic limits — Amendment 1

ISO 18674-1:2015	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Geotechnical monitoring by field instrumentation — Part 1: General rules
ISO 18674-2:2016	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Geotechnical monitoring by field instrumentation — Part 2: Measurement of displacements along a line: Extensometers
ISO 18674-3:2017	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Geotechnical monitoring by field instrumentation — Part 3: Measurement of displacements across a line: Inclinometers
ISO 18674-3:2017/ Amd 1:2020	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Geotechnical monitoring by field instrumentation — Part 3: Measurement of displacements across a line: Inclinometers — Amendment 1
ISO 18674-4:2020	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Geotechnical monitoring by field instrumentation — Part 4: Measurement of pore water pressure: Piezometers
ISO 18674-5:2019	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Geotechnical monitoring by field instrumentation — Part 5: Stress change measurements by total pressure cells (TPC)
ISO 18674-8:2023	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Geotechnical monitoring by field instrumentation — Part 8: Measurement of loads: Load cells
ISO 22282-1:2012	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Geohydraulic testing — Part 1: General rules
ISO 22282-2:2012	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Geohydraulic testing — Part 2: Water permeability tests in a borehole using open systems
ISO 22282-3:2012	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Geohydraulic testing — Part 3: Water pressure tests in rock
ISO 22282-4:2021	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Geohydraulic testing — Part 4: Pumping tests
ISO 22282-5:2012	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Geohydraulic testing — Part 5: Infiltrimeter tests
ISO 22282-6:2012	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Geohydraulic testing — Part 6: Water permeability tests in a borehole using closed systems
ISO 22475-1:2021	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Sampling methods and groundwater measurements — Part 1: Technical principles for the sampling of soil, rock and groundwater
ISO 22476-1:2022	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Field testing — Part 1: Electrical cone and piezocone penetration test
ISO 22476-2:2005	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Field testing — Part 2: Dynamic probing
ISO 22476-2:2005/ Amd 1:2011	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Field testing — Part 2: Dynamic probing — Amendment 1
ISO 22476-3:2005	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Field testing — Part 3: Standard penetration test
ISO 22476-3:2005/ Amd 1:2011	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Field testing — Part 3: Standard penetration test — Amendment 1
ISO 22476-4:2021	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Field testing — Part 4: Prebored pressuremeter test by Ménard procedure
ISO 22476-5:2023	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Field testing — Part 5: Prebored pressuremeter test
ISO 22476-6:2018	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Field testing — Part 6: Self-boring pressuremeter test
ISO 22476-7:2012	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Field testing — Part 7: Borehole jack test
ISO 22476-8:2018	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Field testing — Part 8: Full displacement pressuremeter test
ISO 22476-9:2020	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Field testing — Part 9: Field vane test (FVT and FVT-F)
ISO 22476-10:2017	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Field testing — Part 10: Weight sounding test
ISO 22476-11:2017	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Field testing — Part 11: Flat dilatometer test
ISO 22476-12:2009	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Field testing — Part 12: Mechanical cone penetration test (CPTM)
ISO 22476-14:2020	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Field testing — Part 14: Borehole dynamic probing
ISO 22476-15:2016	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Field testing — Part 15: Measuring while drilling
ISO 22476-16:2024	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Field testing — Part 16: Borehole shear test
ISO 22477-1:2018	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Testing of geotechnical structures — Part 1: Testing of piles: static compression load testing
ISO 22477-2:2023	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Testing of geotechnical structures — Part 2: Testing of piles: Static tension load testing
ISO 22477-4:2018	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Testing of geotechnical structures — Part 4: Testing of piles: dynamic load testing
ISO 22477-5:2018	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Testing of geotechnical structures — Part 5: Testing of grouted anchors
ISO 22477-10:2016	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Testing of geotechnical structures — Part 10: Testing of piles: rapid load testing
ISO 24057:2022	Geotechnics — Array measurement of microtremors to estimate shear wave velocity profile
ISO/TS 24283-1:2022	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Qualification criteria and assessment — Part 1: Qualified technician and qualified operator
ISO/TS 24283-2:2022	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Qualification criteria and assessment — Part 2: Responsible expert

ISO/TS 24283-3:2022	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Qualification criteria and assessment — Part 3: Qualified enterprise
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Table 8. ISO/TC 182 Projects under development.

Project Reference	Title
ISO/WD 16383-2	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Laboratory testing of rock — Part 2: Determination of bulk density
ISO/WD 16383-3	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Laboratory testing of rock — Part 3: Determination of the uniaxial compressive strength and deformability
ISO/AWI 16383-4	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Laboratory testing of rock — Part 4: Determination of the basic friction angle of flat rock surfaces
ISO/AWI 17892-13	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Laboratory testing of soil — Part 13: Swelling test for Soils, Hard Soils and Soft Rocks — Procedure with cycles on a single specimen
ISO/CD 18674-6	Geotechnical investigation and testing -Geotechnical monitoring by field instrumentation — Part 6: Measurement of settlement: Hydraulic settlement systems
ISO/FDIS 18674-7	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Geotechnical monitoring by field instrumentation — Part 7: Measurement of strains: Strain gauges
ISO/CD 18674-9	Geotechnical investigation and testing -Geotechnical monitoring by field instrumentation — Part 9: Measurement of displacements by geodetic means
ISO 22476-1:2022/AWI Amd 1	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Field testing — Part 1: Electrical cone and piezocone penetration test — Amendment 1
ISO/DIS 22477-6	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Testing of geotechnical structures — Part 6: Load testing of soil nails and rock bolts
ISO/AWI 25764	Multi-channel active measurement of the surface wave to estimate shear wave velocity profile

Table 9. Standards from ISO/TC 127/SC2.

Reference	Title
ISO 2860:1992	Earth-moving machinery — Minimum access dimensions
ISO 2867:2011	Earth-moving machinery — Access systems
ISO 3164:2013/ Amd 1:2024	Earth-moving machinery — Laboratory evaluations of protective structures — Specifications for deflection-limiting volume — Amendment 1
ISO 3164:2013	Earth-moving machinery — Laboratory evaluations of protective structures — Specifications for deflection-limiting volume
ISO 3411:2007	Earth-moving machinery — Physical dimensions of operators and minimum operator space envelope
ISO 3449:2005	Earth-moving machinery — Falling-object protective structures — Laboratory tests and performance requirements
ISO 3450:2011	Earth-moving machinery — Wheeled or high-speed rubber-tracked machines — Performance requirements and test procedures for brake systems
ISO 3457:2003	Earth-moving machinery — Guards — Definitions and requirements
ISO 3471:2008	Earth-moving machinery — Roll-over protective structures — Laboratory tests and performance requirements
ISO 5010:2019	Earth-moving machinery — Wheeled machines — Steering requirements
ISO 5353:1995	Earth-moving machinery, and tractors and machinery for agriculture and forestry — Seat index point
ISO 6393:2008	Earth-moving machinery — Determination of sound power level — Stationary test conditions
ISO 6394:2008	Earth-moving machinery — Determination of emission sound pressure level at operator's position — Stationary test conditions
ISO 6394:2008/ Cor 1:2009	Earth-moving machinery — Determination of emission sound pressure level at operator's position — Stationary test conditions — Technical Corrigendum 1
ISO 6395:2008	Earth-moving machinery — Determination of sound power level — Dynamic test conditions
ISO 6396:2008	Earth-moving machinery — Determination of emission sound pressure level at operator's position — Dynamic test conditions
ISO 6396:2008/ Cor 1:2009	Earth-moving machinery — Determination of emission sound pressure level at operator's position — Dynamic test conditions — Technical Corrigendum 1
ISO 6682:1986	Earth-moving machinery — Zones of comfort and reach for controls
ISO 6682:1986/ Amd 1	Earth-moving machinery — Zones of comfort and reach for controls — Amendment 1

Amd 1:1989	
ISO 6683:2005	Earth-moving machinery — Seat belts and seat belt anchorages — Performance requirements and tests
ISO 7021:2023	Earth-moving machinery and machinery for forestry — Operator protective structures — Material performance requirements
ISO 7096:2020	Earth-moving machinery — Laboratory evaluation of operator seat vibration
ISO 9244:2008	Earth-moving machinery — Machine safety labels — General principles
ISO 9244:2008/ Amd 1:2016	Earth-moving machinery — Machine safety labels — General principles — Amendment 1
ISO 9533:2010	Earth-moving machinery — Machine-mounted audible travel alarms and forward horns — Test methods and performance criteria
ISO 10262:1998	Earth-moving machinery — Hydraulic excavators — Laboratory tests and performance requirements for operator protective guards
ISO 10262:1998/ Cor 1:2009	Earth-moving machinery — Hydraulic excavators — Laboratory tests and performance requirements for operator protective guards — Technical Corrigendum 1
ISO 10263-1:2009	Earth-moving machinery — Operator enclosure environment — Part 1: Terms and definitions
ISO 10263-2:2009	Earth-moving machinery — Operator enclosure environment — Part 2: Air filter element test method
ISO 10263-3:2009	Earth-moving machinery — Operator enclosure environment — Part 3: Pressurization test method
ISO 10263-4:2009	Earth-moving machinery — Operator enclosure environment — Part 4: Heating, ventilating and air conditioning (HVAC) test method and performance
ISO 10263-5:2009	Earth-moving machinery — Operator enclosure environment — Part 5: Windscreen defrosting system test method
ISO 10263-6:2009	Earth-moving machinery — Operator enclosure environment — Part 6: Determination of effect of solar heating
ISO 10264:1990	Earth-moving machinery — Key-locked starting systems
ISO 10533:1993	Earth-moving machinery — Lift-arm support devices
ISO 10533:1993/ Amd 1:2005	Earth-moving machinery — Lift-arm support devices — Amendment 1
ISO 10968:2020	Earth-moving machinery — Operator's controls
ISO 11112:1995	Earth-moving machinery — Operator's seat — Dimensions and requirements
ISO 11112:1995/ Amd 1:2001	Earth-moving machinery — Operator's seat — Dimensions and requirements — Amendment 1
ISO 12117:1997	Earth-moving machinery — Tip-over protection structure (TOPS) for compact excavators — Laboratory tests and performance requirements
ISO 12117:1997/ Cor 1:2000	Earth-moving machinery — Tip-over protection structure (TOPS) for compact excavators — Laboratory tests and performance requirements — Technical Corrigendum 1
ISO 12117-2:2008	Earth-moving machinery — Laboratory tests and performance requirements for protective structures of excavators — Part 2: Roll-over protective structures (ROPS) for excavators of over 6 t
ISO 12117-2:2008/ Amd 1:2016	Earth-moving machinery — Laboratory tests and performance requirements for protective structures of excavators — Part 2: Roll-over protective structures (ROPS) for excavators of over 6 t — Amendment 1
ISO 12117-2:2008/ Cor 1:2010	Earth-moving machinery — Laboratory tests and performance requirements for protective structures of excavators — Part 2: Roll-over protective structures (ROPS) for excavators of over 6 t — Technical Corrigendum 1
ISO 12508:1994	Earth-moving machinery — Operator station and maintenance areas — Bluntness of edges
ISO 13031:2016/ Amd 1:2025	Earth-moving machinery — Quick couplers — Safety — Amendment 1
ISO 13031:2016	Earth-moving machinery — Quick couplers — Safety
ISO 13333:1994	Earth-moving machinery — Dumper body support and operator's cab tilt support devices
ISO 13459:2012	Earth-moving machinery — Trainer seat — Deflection limiting volume, space envelope and performance requirements
ISO 13459:2012/ Amd 1:2022	Earth-moving machinery — Trainer seat — Deflection limiting volume, space envelope and performance requirements — Amendment 1
ISO 13649:2024	Earth-moving machinery — Fire prevention guidance
ISO 13766-1:2018	Earth-moving and building construction machinery — Electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) of machines with internal electrical power supply — Part 1: General EMC requirements under typical electromagnetic environmental conditions
ISO 13766-2:2018	Earth-moving and building construction machinery — Electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) of machines with internal electrical power supply — Part 2: Additional EMC requirements for functional safety
ISO 15817:2012	Earth-moving machinery — Safety requirements for remote operator control systems
ISO 17063:2003	Earth-moving machinery — Braking systems of pedestrian-controlled machines — Performance requirements and test procedures
ISO 17757:2019	Earth-moving machinery and mining — Autonomous and semi-autonomous machine system safety

ISO 19014-1:2018	Earth-moving machinery — Functional safety — Part 1: Methodology to determine safety-related parts of the control system and performance requirements
ISO 19014-2:2022	Earth-moving machinery — Functional safety — Part 2: Design and evaluation of hardware and architecture requirements for safety-related parts of the control system
ISO 19014-3:2018	Earth-moving machinery — Functional safety — Part 3: Environmental performance and test requirements of electronic and electrical components used in safety-related parts of the control system
ISO 19014-4:2020	Earth-moving machinery — Functional safety — Part 4: Design and evaluation of software and data transmission for safety-related parts of the control system
ISO/TS 19014-5:2021	Earth-moving machinery — Functional safety — Part 5: Tables of performance levels
ISO 20474-1:2017	Earth-moving machinery — Safety — Part 1: General requirements
ISO 20474-2:2017	Earth-moving machinery — Safety — Part 2: Requirements for dozers
ISO 20474-3:2017	Earth-moving machinery — Safety — Part 3: Requirements for loaders
ISO 20474-4:2017	Earth-moving machinery — Safety — Part 4: Requirements for backhoe loaders
ISO 20474-5:2017	Earth-moving machinery — Safety — Part 5: Requirements for hydraulic excavators
ISO 20474-6:2017	Earth-moving machinery — Safety — Part 6: Requirements for dumpers
ISO 20474-7:2017	Earth-moving machinery — Safety — Part 7: Requirements for scrapers
ISO 20474-8:2017	Earth-moving machinery — Safety — Part 8: Requirements for graders
ISO 20474-9:2017	Earth-moving machinery — Safety — Part 9: Requirements for pipelayers
ISO 20474-10:2017	Earth-moving machinery — Safety — Part 10: Requirements for trenchers
ISO 20474-11:2017	Earth-moving machinery — Safety — Part 11: Requirements for landfill compactors
ISO 20474-12:2017	Earth-moving machinery — Safety — Part 12: Requirements for cable excavators
ISO 20474-13:2017	Earth-moving machinery — Safety — Part 13: Requirements for rollers
ISO 20474-15:2019	Earth-moving machinery — Safety — Part 15: Requirements for compact tool carriers
ISO 21815-1:2022	Earth-moving machinery — Collision warning and avoidance — Part 1: General requirements
ISO/TS 21815-2:2021	Earth-moving machinery — Collision warning and avoidance — Part 2: On-board J1939 communication interface
ISO 21815-3:2023	Earth-moving machinery — Collision warning and avoidance — Part 3: Risk area and risk level for forward/reverse motion
ISO 24410:2020	Earth-moving machinery — Coupling of attachments to skid steer loaders
ISO/TR 25398:2006	Earth-moving machinery — Guidelines for assessment of exposure to whole-body vibration of ride-on machines — Use of harmonized data measured by international institutes, organizations and manufacturers

Table 10. ISO/TC 127/SC 2 Projects under development.

Project Reference	Title
ISO/AWI 6135	Earth moving machinery — Safety of the intended functionality
ISO/FDIS 6683	Earth-moving machinery — Seat-belt assemblies and seat-belt anchorages — Performance requirements and tests
ISO/DIS 19014-1	Earth-moving machinery — Functional safety — Part 1: Methodology to determine safety-related parts of the control system and performance requirements
ISO/DIS 19014-2	Earth-moving machinery — Functional safety — Part 2: Design and evaluation of hardware and architecture requirements for safety-related parts of the control system
ISO/DIS 19014-3	Earth-moving machinery — Functional safety — Part 3: Environmental performance and test requirements of electronic and electrical components used in safety-related parts of the control system
ISO/DIS 19014-4	Earth-moving machinery — Functional safety — Part 4: Design and evaluation of software and data transmission for safety-related parts of the control system
ISO/DIS 19014-5	Earth-moving machinery — Functional safety — Part 5: Tables of performance levels
ISO/DIS 21815-4	Earth-moving machinery — Collision warning and avoidance — Part 4: Risk area and risk level for swing/rotation motion
ISO/CD 21815-5	Earth-moving machinery — Collision warning and avoidance — Part 5: Part 5: Risk area and risk level for other forms of motion
ISO/CD 22543	Earth-moving machinery — Bystander awareness

Table 11. Standards from CEN/TC 341.

Reference	Title
EN ISO 14688-1:2018	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Identification and classification of soil - Part 1: Identification and description (ISO 14688-1:2017)

EN ISO 14688-2:2018	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Identification and classification of soil - Part 2: Principles for a classification (ISO 14688-2:2017)
EN ISO 14689:2018	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Identification, description and classification of rock (ISO 14689:2017)
EN ISO 17628:2015	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Geothermal testing - Determination of thermal conductivity of soil and rock using a borehole heat exchanger (ISO 17628:2015)
EN ISO 17892-1:2014/A1:2022	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Laboratory testing of soil - Part 1: Determination of water content - Amendment 1 (ISO 17892-1:2014/Amd 1:2022)
EN ISO 17892-1:2014	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Laboratory testing of soil - Part 1: Determination of water content (ISO 17892-1:2014)
EN ISO 17892-2:2014	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Laboratory testing of soil - Part 2: Determination of bulk density (ISO 17892-2:2014)
EN ISO 17892-3:2015	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Laboratory testing of soil - Part 3: Determination of particle density (ISO 17892-3:2015, Corrected version 2015-12-15)
EN ISO 17892-4:2016	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Laboratory testing of soil - Part 4: Determination of particle size distribution (ISO 17892-4:2016)
EN ISO 17892-5:2017	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Laboratory testing of soil - Part 5: Incremental loading oedometer test (ISO 17892-5:2017)
EN ISO 17892-6:2017	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Laboratory testing of soil - Part 6: Fall cone test (ISO 17892-6:2017)
EN ISO 17892-7:2018	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Laboratory testing of soil - Part 7: Unconfined compression test (ISO 17892-7:2017)
EN ISO 17892-8:2018	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Laboratory testing of soil - Part 8: Unconsolidated undrained triaxial test (ISO 17892-8:2018)
EN ISO 17892-9:2018	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Laboratory testing of soil - Part 9: Consolidated triaxial compression tests on water saturated soils (ISO 17892-9:2018)
EN ISO 17892-10:2018	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Laboratory testing of soil - Part 10: Direct shear tests (ISO 17892-10:2018)
EN ISO 17892-11:2019	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Laboratory testing of soil - Part 11: Permeability tests (ISO 17892-11:2019)
EN ISO 17892-12:2018/A2:2022	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Laboratory testing of soil - Part 12: Determination of liquid and plastic limits - Amendment 2 (ISO 17892-12:2018/Amd 2:2022)
EN ISO 17892-12:2018/A1:2021	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Laboratory testing of soil - Part 12: Determination of liquid and plastic limits - Amendment 1 (ISO 17892-12:2018/Amd 1:2021)
EN ISO 17892-12:2018	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Laboratory testing of soil - Part 12: Determination of liquid and plastic limits (ISO 17892-12:2018)
EN ISO 18674-1:2015	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Geotechnical monitoring by field instrumentation - Part 1: General rules (ISO 18674-1:2015)
EN ISO 18674-2:2016	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Geotechnical monitoring by field instrumentation - Part 2: Measurement of displacements along a line: Extensometers (ISO 18674-2:2016)
EN ISO 18674-3:2017/A1:2020	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Geotechnical monitoring by field instrumentation - Part 3: Measurement of displacements across a line: Inclinometers - Amendment 1 (ISO 18674-3:2017/Amd 1:2020)
EN ISO 18674-3:2017	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Geotechnical monitoring by field instrumentation - Part 3: Measurement of displacements across a line: Inclinometers (ISO 18674-3:2017)
EN ISO 18674-4:2020	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Geotechnical monitoring by field instrumentation - Part 4: Measurement of pore water pressure: Piezometers (ISO 18674-4:2020)
EN ISO 18674-5:2019	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Geotechnical monitoring by field instrumentation - Part 5: Stress change measurements by total pressure cells (TPC) (ISO 18674-5:2019)
EN ISO 18674-8:2023	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Geotechnical monitoring by field instrumentation - Part 8: Measurement of loads: Load cells (ISO 18674-8:2023)
EN ISO 22282-1:2012	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Geohydraulic testing - Part 1: General rules (ISO 22282-1:2012)
EN ISO 22282-2:2012	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Geohydraulic testing - Part 2: Water permeability tests in a borehole using open systems (ISO 22282-2:2012)
EN ISO 22282-3:2012	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Geohydraulic testing - Part 3: Water pressure tests in rock (ISO 22282-3:2012)
EN ISO 22282-4:2021	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Geohydraulic testing - Part 4: Pumping tests (ISO 22282-4:2021)
EN ISO 22282-5:2012	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Geohydraulic testing - Part 5: Infiltrometer tests (ISO 22282-5:2012)

EN ISO 22282-6:2012	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Geohydraulic testing - Part 6: Water permeability tests in a borehole using closed systems (ISO 22282-6:2012)
EN ISO 22475-1:2021	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Sampling methods and groundwater measurements - Part 1: Technical principles for the sampling of soil, rock and groundwater (ISO 22475-1:2021)
EN ISO 22476-1:2023	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Field testing - Part 1: Electrical cone and piezocone penetration test (ISO 22476-1:2022)
EN ISO 22476-2:2005/A1:2011	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Field testing - Part 2: Dynamic probing - Amendment 1 (ISO 22476-2:2005/Amd 1:2011)
EN ISO 22476-2:2005	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Field testing - Part 2: Dynamic probing (ISO 22476-2:2005)
EN ISO 22476-3:2005/A1:2011	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Field testing - Part 3: Standard penetration test - Amendment 1 (ISO 22476-3:2005/Amd 1:2011)
EN ISO 22476-3:2005	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Field testing - Part 3: Standard penetration test (ISO 22476-3:2005)
EN ISO 22476-4:2021	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Field testing - Part 4: Prebored pressuremeter test by Ménard procedure (ISO 22476-4:2021)
EN ISO 22476-5:2023	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Field testing - Part 5: Prebored pressuremeter test (ISO 22476-5:2023)
EN ISO 22476-6:2018	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Field testing - Part 6: Self boring pressuremeter test (ISO 22476-6:2018)
EN ISO 22476-7:2012	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Field testing - Part 7: Borehole jack test (ISO 22476-7:2012)
EN ISO 22476-8:2018	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Field testing - Part 8: Full displacement pressuremeter test (ISO 22476-8:2018)
EN ISO 22476-9:2020	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Field testing - Part 9: Field vane test (FVT and FVT-F) (ISO 22476-9:2020)
EN ISO 22476-10:2017	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Field testing - Part 10: Weight sounding test (ISO 22476-10:2017)
EN ISO 22476-11:2017	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Field testing - Part 11: Flat dilatometer test (ISO 22476-11:2017)
EN ISO 22476-12:2009	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Field testing - Part 12: Mechanical cone penetration test (CPTM) (ISO 22476-12:2009)
EN ISO 22476-14:2020	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Field testing - Part 14: Borehole dynamic probing (ISO 22476-14:2020)
EN ISO 22476-15:2016	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Field testing - Part 15: Measuring while drilling (ISO 22476-15:2016)
EN ISO 22476-16:2024	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Field testing - Part 16: Borehole shear test (ISO 22476-16:2024)
EN ISO 22477-1:2018	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Testing of geotechnical structures - Part 1: Testing of piles: static compression load testing (ISO 22477-1:2018, Corrected version 2019-03)
EN ISO 22477-2:2023	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Testing of geotechnical structures - Part 2: Testing of piles: static tension load testing (ISO 22477-2:2023)
EN ISO 22477-4:2018	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Testing of geotechnical structures - Part 4: Testing of piles: dynamic load testing (ISO 22477-4:2018)
EN ISO 22477-5:2018	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Testing of geotechnical structures - Part 5: Testing of grouted anchors (ISO 22477-5:2018)
EN ISO 22477-10:2016	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Testing of geotechnical structures - Part 10: Testing of piles: rapid load testing (ISO 22477-10:2016)
CEN ISO/TS 24283-1:2022	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Qualification criteria and assessment - Part 1: Qualified technician and qualified operator (ISO/TS 24283-1:2022)
CEN ISO/TS 24283-2:2022	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Qualification criteria and assessment - Part 2: Responsible expert (ISO/TS 24283-2:2022)
CEN ISO/TS 24283-3:2022	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Qualification criteria and assessment - Part 3: Qualified enterprise (ISO/TS 24283-3:2022)

Table 12. CEN/TC 341 Projects under development.

Project reference	Title
FprEN ISO 16383-1	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Laboratory testing of rock - Part 1: Determination of water content (ISO/FDIS 16383-1:2025)
prEN ISO 16383-2	Geotechnical investigation and testing – Laboratory testing of rock – Part 2: Determination of bulk density

prEN ISO 16383-3	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Laboratory testing of rock - Part 3: Determination of the uniaxial compressive strength and deformability
prEN ISO 17892-13	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Laboratory testing of soil — Part 13: Swelling test for Soils, Hard Soils and Soft Rocks — Procedure with cycles on a single specimen
prEN ISO 18674-6	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Geotechnical monitoring by field instrumentation – Part 6: Measurement of settlement : Hydraulic settlement systems
prEN ISO 18674-7	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Geotechnical monitoring by field instrumentation - Part 7: Measurement of strains: Strain gauges (ISO/DIS 18674-7:2024)
prEN ISO 18674-9	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Geotechnical monitoring by field instrumentation – Part 9: Measurement of displacement by Geodetic means
EN ISO 22476-1:2023/prA1	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Field testing — Part 1: Electrical cone and piezocone penetration test — Amendment 1
prEN ISO 22477-6	Geotechnical investigation and testing - Testing of geotechnical structures - Part 6: Load testing of soil nails and rock bolts (ISO/DIS 22477-6:2025)

Table 13. Standards from CEN/TC 288.

Reference	Title
EN 1536:2010+A1:2015	Execution of special geotechnical work - Bored piles
EN 1537:2013	Execution of special geotechnical works - Ground anchors
EN 1538:2010+A1:2015	Execution of special geotechnical work - Diaphragm walls
EN 12063:2024	Execution of special geotechnical work - Sheet pile walls, combined pile walls, high modulus walls
EN 12699:2015	Execution of special geotechnical works - Displacement piles
EN 12715:2020	Execution of special geotechnical work - Grouting
EN 12716:2018	Execution of special geotechnical work - Jet grouting
EN 14199:2015	Execution of special geotechnical works - Micropiles
EN 14475:2006	Execution of special geotechnical works - Reinforced fill
EN 14475:2006/AC:2006	Execution of special geotechnical works - Reinforced fill
EN 14490:2010	Execution of special geotechnical works - Soil nailing
EN 14679:2005	Execution of special geotechnical works - Deep mixing
EN 14679:2005/AC:2006	Execution of special geotechnical works - Deep mixing
EN 14731:2005	Execution of special geotechnical works - Ground treatment by deep vibration
EN 15237:2007	Execution of special geotechnical works - Vertical drainage
EN 1536:2010+A1:2015	Execution of special geotechnical work - Bored piles
EN 1537:2013	Execution of special geotechnical works - Ground anchors
EN 1538:2010+A1:2015	Execution of special geotechnical work - Diaphragm walls
EN 12063:2024	Execution of special geotechnical work - Sheet pile walls, combined pile walls, high modulus walls
EN 12699:2015	Execution of special geotechnical works - Displacement piles
EN 12715:2020	Execution of special geotechnical work - Grouting
EN 12716:2018	Execution of special geotechnical work - Jet grouting
EN 14199:2015	Execution of special geotechnical works - Micropiles
EN 14475:2006	Execution of special geotechnical works - Reinforced fill
EN 14475:2006/AC:2006	Execution of special geotechnical works - Reinforced fill
EN 14490:2010	Execution of special geotechnical works - Soil nailing
EN 14679:2005	Execution of special geotechnical works - Deep mixing
EN 14679:2005/AC:2006	Execution of special geotechnical works - Deep mixing
EN 14731:2005	Execution of special geotechnical works - Ground treatment by deep vibration
EN 15237:2007	Execution of special geotechnical works - Vertical drainage

Table 14. CEN/TC 288 Projects under development.

Project reference	Title
prEN 14679	Execution of special geotechnical works - In-situ soil mixing
prEN 14679 rev	Execution of special geotechnical works - Deep mixing

Table 15. Standards from IEC/TC 68.

Reference	Title
IEC 60404-1:2016 RLV	Magnetic materials — Part 1: Classification
IEC 60404-1:2016	Magnetic materials — Part 1: Classification
IEC 60404-1-1:2004	Magnetic materials — Part 1-1: Classification — Surface insulations of electrical steel sheet, strip and laminations
IEC 60404-2:1996+AMD1:2008 CSV	Magnetic materials — Part 2: Methods of measurement of the magnetic properties of electrical steel strip and sheet by means of an Epstein frame
IEC 60404-2:1996	Magnetic materials — Part 2: Methods of measurement of the magnetic properties of electrical steel sheet and strip by means of an Epstein frame
IEC 60404-2:1996/AMD1:2008	Amendment 1 — Magnetic materials — Part 2: Methods of measurement of magnetic properties of electrical steel strip and sheet by means of an Epstein frame
IEC 60404-2:1996/AMD1:2008/COR1:2018	Corrigendum 1 — Amendment 1 — Magnetic materials — Part 2: Methods of measurement of magnetic properties of electrical steel strip and sheet by means of an Epstein frame
IEC 60404-3:2022	Magnetic materials — Part 3: Methods of measurement of the magnetic properties of electrical steel strip and sheet by means of a single sheet tester
IEC 60404-3:2022 RLV	Magnetic materials — Part 3: Methods of measurement of the magnetic properties of electrical steel strip and sheet by means of a single sheet tester
IEC 60404-4:1995+AMD1:2000+AMD2:2008 CSV	Magnetic materials — Part 4: Methods of measurement of d.c. magnetic properties of magnetically soft materials
IEC 60404-4:1995+AMD1:2000 CSV	Magnetic materials — Part 4: Methods of measurement of d.c. magnetic properties of magnetically soft materials
IEC 60404-4:1995	Magnetic materials — Part 4: Methods of measurement of d.c. magnetic properties of iron and steel
IEC 60404-4:1995/AMD1:2000	Amendment 1 — Magnetic materials — Part 4: Methods of measurement of d.c. magnetic properties of iron and steel
IEC 60404-4:1995/AMD2:2008	Amendment 2 — Magnetic materials — Part 4: Methods of measurement of d.c. magnetic properties of magnetically soft materials
IEC 60404-5:2015	Magnetic materials — Part 5: Permanent magnet (magnetically hard) materials — Methods of measurement of magnetic properties
IEC 60404-5:2015 RLV	Magnetic materials — Part 5: Permanent magnet (magnetically hard) materials — Methods of measurement of magnetic properties
IEC 60404-6:2018+AMD1:2021 CSV	Magnetic materials — Part 6: Methods of measurement of the magnetic properties of magnetically soft metallic and powder materials at frequencies in the range 20 Hz to 100 kHz by the use of ring specimens
IEC 60404-6:2018 RLV	Magnetic materials — Part 6: Methods of measurement of the magnetic properties of magnetically soft metallic and powder materials at frequencies in the range 20 Hz to 100 kHz by the use of ring specimens
IEC 60404-6:2018	Magnetic materials — Part 6: Methods of measurement of the magnetic properties of magnetically soft metallic and powder materials at frequencies in the range 20 Hz to 100 kHz by the use of ring specimens
IEC 60404-6:2018/COR1:2018	Corrigendum 1 — Magnetic materials — Part 6: Methods of measurement of the magnetic properties of magnetically soft metallic and powder materials at frequencies in the range 20 Hz to 100 kHz by the use of ring specimens
IEC 60404-6:2018/AMD1:2021	Amendment 1 — Magnetic materials — Part 6: Methods of measurement of the magnetic properties of magnetically soft metallic and powder materials at frequencies in the range 20 Hz to 100 kHz by the use of ring specimens
IEC 60404-7:2019	Magnetic materials — Part 7: Method of measurement of the coercivity (up to 160 kA/m) of magnetic materials in an open magnetic circuit
IEC 60404-8-1:2023	Magnetic materials — Part 8-1: Specifications for individual materials — Permanent magnet (magnetically hard) materials
IEC 60404-8-3:2023	Magnetic materials — Part 8-3: Specifications for individual materials — Cold-rolled non-oriented electrical steel strip and sheet delivered in the semi-processed state
IEC 60404-8-4:2022 RLV	Magnetic materials — Part 8-4: Specifications for individual materials — Cold-rolled non-oriented electrical steel strip and sheet delivered in the fully-processed state
IEC 60404-8-4:2022	Magnetic materials — Part 8-4: Specifications for individual materials — Cold-rolled non-oriented electrical steel strip and sheet delivered in the fully-processed state
IEC 60404-8-5:2020	Magnetic materials — Part 8-5: Specifications for individual materials — Electrical steel strip and sheet with specified mechanical properties and magnetic polarization
IEC 60404-8-6:2016	Magnetic materials — Part 8-6: Specifications for individual materials — Soft magnetic metallic materials

IEC 60404-8-7:2020	Magnetic materials — Part 8-7: Specifications for individual materials — Cold-rolled grain-oriented electrical steel strip and sheet delivered in the fully-processed state
IEC 60404-8-7:2020 RLV	Magnetic materials — Part 8-7: Specifications for individual materials — Cold-rolled grain-oriented electrical steel strip and sheet delivered in the fully-processed state
IEC 60404-8-8:2017	Magnetic materials — Part 8-8: Specifications for individual materials — Thin electrical steel strip and sheet for use at medium frequencies
IEC 60404-8-9:1994	Magnetic materials — Part 8: Specifications for individual materials — Section 9: Standard specification for sintered soft magnetic materials
IEC 60404-8-10:2009	Magnetic materials — Part 8-10: Specifications for individual materials — Magnetic materials (iron and steel) for use in relays
IEC 60404-8-11:2018	Magnetic materials — Part 8-11: Specifications for individual materials — Fe-based amorphous strip delivered in the semi-processed state
IEC 60404-9:2018	Magnetic materials — Part 9: Methods of determination of the geometrical characteristics of electrical steel strip and sheet
IEC 60404-10:2016 RLV	Magnetic materials — Part 10: Methods of measurement of magnetic properties of electrical steel strip and sheet at medium frequencies
IEC 60404-10:2016	Magnetic materials — Part 10: Methods of measurement of magnetic properties of electrical steel strip and sheet at medium frequencies
IEC 60404-10:2016/ COR1:2018	Corrigendum 1 — Magnetic materials — Part 10: Methods of measurement of magnetic properties of electrical steel strip and sheet at medium frequencies
IEC 60404-11:2021	Magnetic materials — Part 11: Methods of measurement of the surface insulation resistance of electrical steel strip and sheet
IEC 60404-12:2023	Magnetic materials — Part 12: Methods of test for the assessment of the thermal endurance of surface insulation coatings on electrical steel strip and sheet
IEC 60404-13:2018	Magnetic materials — Part 13: Methods of measurement of resistivity, density and stacking factor of electrical steel strip and sheet
IEC 60404-14:2002	Magnetic materials — Part 14: Methods of measurement of the magnetic dipole moment of a ferromagnetic material specimen by the withdrawal or rotation method
IEC 60404-15:2012+AMD1:2016 CSV	Magnetic materials — Part 15: Methods for the determination of the relative magnetic permeability of feebly magnetic materials
IEC 60404-15:2012	Magnetic materials — Part 15: Methods for the determination of the relative magnetic permeability of feebly magnetic materials
IEC 60404-15:2012/ AMD1:2016	Amendment 1 — Magnetic materials — Part 15: Methods for the determination of the relative magnetic permeability of feebly magnetic materials
IEC 60404-16:2018	Magnetic materials — Part 16: Methods of measurement of the magnetic properties of Fe-based amorphous strip by means of a single sheet tester
IEC 60404-16:2018/ COR1:2018	Corrigendum 1 — Magnetic materials — Part 16: Methods of measurement of the magnetic properties of Fe-based amorphous strip by means of a single sheet tester
IEC 60404-17:2021	Magnetic materials — Part 17: Methods of measurement of the magnetostriction characteristics of grain-oriented electrical steel strip and sheet by means of a single sheet tester and an optical sensor
IEC TR 61807:1999	Magnetic properties of magnetically hard materials at elevated temperatures — Methods of measurement
IEC TR 62331:2005	Pulsed field magnetometry
IEC TR 62383:2006	Determination of magnetic loss under magnetic polarization waveforms including higher harmonic components — Measurement, modelling and calculation methods
IEC TR 62517:2009	Magnetizing behaviour of permanent magnets
IEC TR 62518:2009	Rare earth sintered magnets — Stability of the magnetic properties at elevated temperatures
IEC TR 62581:2010	Electrical steel — Methods of measurement of the magnetostriction characteristics by means of single sheet and Epstein test specimens
IEC TR 62797:2013	International comparison of measurements of the magnetic moment using vibrating sample magnetometers (VSM) and superconducting quantum interference device (SQUID) magnetometers
IEC TR 62981:2017	Studies and comparisons of magnetic measurements on grain-oriented electrical steelsheet determined by the single sheet test method and Epstein test method
IEC TR 63114:2018	Electrical steel — Reverse bend test method of electrical steel strip and sheet
IEC TR 63304:2021	Methods of measurement of the magnetic properties of permanent magnet (magnetically hard) materials in an open magnetic circuit using a superconducting magnet

Table 16. IEC/TC 68 Projects under development.

Project Reference	Title
PWI TR 68-9	IEC Technical Report on studies of the measurements of the magnetic properties of electrical steels using a single sheet tester with magnetic field strength sensing H-coils
PWI 68-10	Future IEC 63311 ED1: Permanent magnet (magnetically hard) materials — Method of measurement based upon the pulsed field magnetometry (PFM) technique
PWI TR 68-11	IEC Technical Report — Methods of measurement of the magnetic properties of non-oriented electrical steel strip and sheet by means of a small single sheet tester.
IEC 60404-1/AMD1 ED3	Amendment 1 — Magnetic materials — Part 1: Classification
IEC 60404-1-1/AMD1 ED1	Amendment 1 — Magnetic materials — Part 1-1: Classification — Surface insulations of electrical steel strip, sheet and laminations
IEC 60404-18 ED1	Magnetic materials — Part 18: Permanent magnet (magnetically hard) materials — Methods of measurement of the magnetic properties in an open magnetic circuit using a superconducting magnet

Table 17. Standards from ISO/TC 79.

Reference	Title
ISO 115:2024	Unalloyed aluminium ingots for remelting — Classification and composition
ISO 209:2024	Aluminium and aluminium alloys — Chemical composition
ISO 791:1973	Magnesium alloys — Determination of aluminium — 8-hydroxyquinoline gravimetric method
ISO 792:1973	Magnesium and magnesium alloys — Determination of iron — Orthophenanthroline photometric method
ISO 793:1973	Aluminium and aluminium alloys — Determination of iron — Orthophenanthroline photometric method
ISO 794:1976	Magnesium and magnesium alloys — Determination of copper content — Oxalyldihydrazide photometric method
ISO 795:1976	Aluminium and aluminium alloys — Determination of copper content — Oxalyldihydrazide photometric method
ISO 796:1973	Aluminium alloys — Determination of copper — Electrolytic method
ISO 797:1973	Aluminium and aluminium alloys — Determination of silicon — Gravimetric method
ISO 808:1973	Aluminium and aluminium alloys — Determination of silicon — Spectrophotometric method with the reduced silicomolybdic complex
ISO 809:1973	Magnesium and magnesium alloys — Determination of manganese — Periodate photometric method (Manganese content between 0,01 and 0,8 %)
ISO 810:1973	Magnesium and magnesium alloys — Determination of manganese — Periodate photometric method (Manganese content less than 0,01 %)
ISO 886:1973	Aluminium and aluminium alloys — Determination of manganese — Photometric method (Manganese content between 0,005 and 1,5 %)
ISO 1118:1978	Aluminium and aluminium alloys — Determination of titanium — Spectrophotometric chromotropic acid method
ISO 1178:1976	Magnesium alloys — Determination of soluble zirconium — Alizarin sulphonate photometric method
ISO 1783:1973	Magnesium alloys — Determination of zinc — Volumetric method
ISO 1784:1976	Aluminium alloys — Determination of zinc — EDTA titrimetric method
ISO 1975:1973	Magnesium and magnesium alloys — Determination of silicon — Spectrophotometric method with the reduced silicomolybdic complex
ISO 2085:2018	Anodizing of aluminium and its alloys — Check for continuity of thin anodic oxidation coatings — Copper sulfate test
ISO 2106:2019	Anodizing of aluminium and its alloys — Determination of mass per unit area (surface density) of anodic oxidation coatings — Gravimetric method
ISO 2107:2023	Aluminium and aluminium alloys — Wrought products — Temper designations
ISO 2128:2010	Anodizing of aluminium and its alloys — Determination of thickness of anodic oxidation coatings — Non-destructive measurement by split-beam microscope
ISO 2135:2024	Anodizing of aluminium and its alloys — Accelerated test of light fastness of coloured anodic oxidation coatings using artificial light
ISO 2143:2017	Anodizing of aluminium and its alloys — Estimation of loss of absorptive power of anodic oxidation coatings after sealing — Dye-spot test with prior acid treatment
ISO 2297:1973	Chemical analysis of aluminium and its alloys — Complexometric determination of magnesium

ISO 2353:1972	Magnesium and its alloys — Determination of manganese in magnesium alloys containing zirconium, rare earths, thorium and silver — Periodate photometric method
ISO 2354:1976	Magnesium alloys — Determination of insoluble zirconium — Alizarin sulphonate photometric method
ISO 2355:1972	Chemical analysis of magnesium and its alloys — Determination of rare earths — Gravimetric method
ISO 2376:2019	Anodizing of aluminium and its alloys — Determination of breakdown voltage and withstand voltage
ISO 2931:2017	Anodizing of aluminium and its alloys — Assessment of quality of sealed anodic oxidation coatings by measurement of admittance
ISO 3116:2019	Magnesium and magnesium alloys — Wrought magnesium and magnesium alloys
ISO 3210:2017	Anodizing of aluminium and its alloys — Assessment of quality of sealed anodic oxidation coatings by measurement of the loss of mass after immersion in acid solution(s)
ISO 3211:2018	Anodizing of aluminium and its alloys — Assessment of resistance of anodic oxidation coatings to cracking by deformation
ISO 3255:1974	Magnesium and magnesium alloys — Determination of aluminium — Chromazurol S photometric method
ISO 3256:1977	Aluminium and aluminium alloys — Determination of magnesium — Atomic absorption spectrophotometric method
ISO 3522:2007	Aluminium and aluminium alloys — Castings — Chemical composition and mechanical properties
ISO 3978:1976	Aluminium and aluminium alloys — Determination of chromium — Spectrophotometric method using diphenylcarbazide, after extraction
ISO 3980:1977	Aluminium and aluminium alloys — Determination of copper — Atomic absorption spectrophotometric method
ISO 3981:1977	Aluminium and aluminium alloys — Determination of nickel — Atomic absorption spectrophotometric method
ISO 4155:2022	Magnesium and magnesium alloys — Determination of nickel — Inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometric method
ISO 4192:1981	Aluminium and aluminium alloys — Determination of lead content — Flame atomic absorption spectrometric method
ISO 4193:1981	Aluminium and aluminium alloys — Determination of chromium content — Flame atomic absorption spectrometric method
ISO 4194:1981	Magnesium alloys — Determination of zinc content — Flame atomic absorption spectrometric method
ISO 5194:1981	Aluminium and aluminium alloys — Determination of zinc content — Flame atomic absorption spectrometric method
ISO 5196-1:1980	Magnesium alloys — Determination of thorium — Part 1: Gravimetric method
ISO 5196-2:1980	Magnesium alloys — Determination of thorium — Part 2: Titrimetric method
ISO 6139:1993	Aluminium ores — Experimental determination of the heterogeneity of distribution of a lot
ISO 6361-1:2011	Wrought aluminium and aluminium alloys — Sheets, strips and plates — Part 1: Technical conditions for inspection and delivery
ISO 6361-2:2014	Wrought aluminium and aluminium alloys — Sheets, strips and plates — Part 2: Mechanical properties
ISO 6361-3:2014	Wrought aluminium and aluminium alloys — Sheets, strips and plates — Part 3: Strips: Tolerances on shape and dimensions
ISO 6361-4:2014	Wrought aluminium and aluminium alloys — Sheets, strips and plates — Part 4: Sheets and plates: Tolerances on shape and dimensions
ISO 6361-5:2011	Wrought aluminium and aluminium alloys — Sheets, strips and plates — Part 5: Chemical composition
ISO 6362-1:2022	Wrought aluminium and aluminium alloys — Extruded rods/bars, tubes and profiles — Part 1: Technical conditions for inspection and delivery
ISO 6362-2:2022	Wrought aluminium and aluminium alloys — Extruded rods/bars, tubes and profiles — Part 2: Mechanical properties
ISO 6362-3:2022	Wrought aluminium and aluminium alloys — Extruded rods/bars, tubes and profiles — Part 3: Tolerances on form and dimensions for extruded rectangular bars
ISO 6362-4:2022	Wrought aluminium and aluminium alloys — Extruded rods/bars, tubes and profiles — Part 4: Tolerances on form and dimensions for profiles
ISO 6362-5:2022	Wrought aluminium and aluminium alloys — Extruded rods/bars, tubes and profiles — Part 5: Tolerances on form and dimensions for round, square and hexagonal bars

ISO 6362-6:2025	Wrought aluminium and aluminium alloys — Extruded rods/bars, tubes and profiles — Part 6: Round, square, rectangular and hexagonal tubes — Tolerances on shape and dimensions
ISO 6362-7:2022	Wrought aluminium and aluminium alloys — Extruded rods/bars, tubes and profiles — Part 7: Chemical composition
ISO 6363-1:2022	Wrought aluminium and aluminium alloys — Cold-drawn rods/bars, tubes and wires — Part 1: Technical conditions for inspection and delivery
ISO 6363-2:2022	Wrought aluminium and aluminium alloys — Cold-drawn rods/bars, tubes and wires — Part 2: Mechanical properties
ISO 6363-3:2022	Wrought aluminium and aluminium alloys — Cold-drawn rods/bars, tubes and wires — Part 3: Tolerances on form and dimensions for drawn rods/bars and wires
ISO 6363-4:2022	Wrought aluminium and aluminium alloys — Cold-drawn rods/bars, tubes and wires — Part 4: Tolerances on form and dimensions for drawn rectangular bars and wires
ISO 6363-5:2022	Wrought aluminium and aluminium alloys — Cold-drawn rods/bars, tubes and wires — Part 5: Tolerances on form and dimensions for drawn square and hexagonal bars and wires
ISO 6363-6:2022	Wrought aluminium and aluminium alloys — Cold-drawn rods/bars, tubes and wires — Part 6: Tolerances on form and dimensions for drawn round tubes
ISO 6581:2018	Anodizing of aluminium and its alloys — Determination of the comparative fastness to ultraviolet light and heat of coloured anodic oxidation coatings
ISO 6719:2010	Anodizing of aluminium and its alloys — Measurement of reflectance characteristics of aluminium surfaces using integrating-sphere instruments
ISO 6827:1981	Aluminium and aluminium alloys — Determination of titanium content — Diantiprylmethane photometric method
ISO 7209:2023	Titanium and titanium alloys — Plate, sheet and strip — Technical delivery conditions
ISO 7209:2023/Amd 1:2024	Titanium and titanium alloys — Plate, sheet and strip — Technical delivery conditions
ISO 7217:2023	Titanium and titanium alloys — Bar, rod and billet — Technical delivery conditions
ISO 7217:2023/Amd 1:2024	Titanium and titanium alloys — Bar, rod and billet — Technical delivery conditions
ISO/TR 7242:1981	Chemical analysis of light metals and their alloys — Statistical interpretation of inter-laboratory trials
ISO 7271:2011	Aluminium and aluminium alloys — Foil and thin strip — Dimensional tolerances
ISO 7583:2013	Anodizing of aluminium and its alloys — Terms and definitions
ISO 7599:2018	Anodizing of aluminium and its alloys — Method for specifying decorative and protective anodic oxidation coatings on aluminium
ISO 7668:2021	Anodizing of aluminium and its alloys — Measurement of specular reflectance and specular gloss of anodic oxidation coatings at angles of 20°, 45°, 60° or 85°
ISO 7759:2010	Anodizing of aluminium and its alloys — Measurement of reflectance characteristics of aluminium surfaces using a goniophotometer or an abridged goniophotometer
ISO 8251:2018	Anodizing of aluminium and its alloys — Measurement of abrasion resistance of anodic oxidation coatings
ISO 8287:2021	Magnesium and magnesium alloys — Unalloyed magnesium — Chemical composition
ISO 8993:2018	Anodizing of aluminium and its alloys — Rating system for the evaluation of pitting corrosion — Chart method
ISO 8994:2018	Anodizing of aluminium and its alloys — Rating system for the evaluation of pitting corrosion — Grid method
ISO 10049:2019	Aluminium alloy castings — Visual method for assessing porosity
ISO 10074:2021	Anodizing of aluminium and its alloys — Specification for hard anodic oxidation coatings on aluminium and its alloys
ISO 10215:2018	Anodizing of aluminium and its alloys — Visual determination of image clarity of anodic oxidation coatings — Chart scale method
ISO 10216:2024	Anodizing of aluminium and its alloys — Instrumental determination of image clarity of anodic oxidation coatings — Instrumental method
ISO 13092:2012	Titanium and titanium alloys — Titanium sponge
ISO 13093:2023	Titanium and titanium alloys — Determination of carbon — Infrared absorption method after combustion in an induction furnace
ISO 16220:2017	Magnesium and magnesium alloys — Magnesium alloy ingots and castings
ISO/TR 16689:2012	Anodizing of aluminium and its alloys — Experimental research on possible alternative sealing quality test methods to replace the phosphoric acid/chromic acid immersion test — Evaluation of correlations
ISO 17615:2007	Aluminium and aluminium alloys — Alloyed ingots for remelting — Specifications

ISO 17615:2007/ Cor 1:2008	Aluminium and aluminium alloys — Alloyed ingots for remelting — Specifications — Technical Corrigendum 1
ISO 18762:2016	Tubes of titanium and titanium alloys — Welded tubes for condensers and heat exchangers — Technical delivery conditions
ISO 18768-1:2022	Organic coatings on aluminium and its alloys — Methods for specifying decorative and protective organic coatings on aluminium — Part 1: Powder coatings
ISO 18768-2:2022	Organic coatings on aluminium and its alloys — Methods for specifying decorative and protective organic coatings on aluminium — Part 2: Liquid coatings
ISO 18771:2019	Anodizing of aluminium and its alloys — Method to test the surface abrasion resistance using glass-coated abrasive paper
ISO 20260:2019	Magnesium and magnesium alloys — Determination of mercury
ISO 21334:2022	Titanium and titanium alloys — Strip for welded tubes — Technical delivery conditions
ISO 21339:2023	6Al-4V titanium alloys — Determination of aluminium and vanadium contents — Inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectrometric method
ISO 22960:2008	Titanium and titanium alloys — Determination of iron — Molecular absorption spectrometry using 1, 10-phenanthroline
ISO 22961:2008	Titanium and titanium alloys — Determination of iron — Atomic absorption spectrometry
ISO 22962:2008	Titanium and titanium alloys — Determination of iron — Inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectrometry
ISO 22963:2008	Titanium and titanium alloys — Determination of oxygen — Infrared method after fusion under inert gas
ISO 23052:2020	Anodizing of aluminium and its alloys — Test method for chemical resistance of anodic oxidation coatings on aluminium and its alloys using electromotive force apparatus
ISO 23515:2022	Titanium and titanium alloys — Designation system
ISO 23694:2021	Wrought magnesium and magnesium alloys — Extruded rods/bars and tubes
ISO 23700:2021	Wrought magnesium and magnesium alloys — Rolled plates and sheets
ISO 25902-1:2009	Titanium pipes and tubes — Non-destructive testing — Part 1: Eddy-current examination
ISO 25902-2:2010	Titanium pipes and tubes — Non-destructive testing — Part 2: Ultrasonic testing for the detection of longitudinal imperfections
ISO 26202:2019	Magnesium and magnesium alloys — Magnesium alloys for cast anodes
ISO 28340:2013	Combined coatings on aluminium — General specifications for combined coatings of electrophoretic organic coatings and anodic oxidation coatings on aluminium
ISO 28401:2010	Light metals and their alloys — Titanium and titanium alloys — Classification and terminology

Table 18. ISO/TC 79 Projects under development.

Project Reference	Title
ISO/DIS 3210	Anodizing of aluminium and its alloys — Assessment of quality of sealed anodic oxidation coatings by measurement of the loss of mass after immersion in acid solution(s)
ISO/AWI 7271-1	Aluminium and aluminium alloys — Foil and thin strip — Part 1: Technical conditions for inspection and delivery
ISO/AWI 7271-2	Aluminium and aluminium alloys — Foil and thin strip — Part 2: Mechanical properties
ISO/DIS 3116	Magnesium and magnesium alloys — Wrought magnesium and magnesium alloys
ISO/WD 22177	Magnesium and magnesium alloys — Determination of Rare earth elements — Inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectrometry
ISO/WD 22202	Magnesium and magnesium alloys — Determination of alloying and impurity elements — Inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometric method
ISO/WD 22230	Specification for phosphate conversion coating on magnesium and its alloys
ISO/DIS 22233	Magnesium and magnesium alloys — Magnesium alloy die castings
ISO/WD 25048	Titanium and titanium alloys-Welded pipes-Technical delivery conditions
ISO/AWI 6139	Aluminium ores — Experimental determination of the heterogeneity of distribution of a lot
ISO/AWI 6140	Aluminium ores — Preparation of samples
ISO/AWI 8685	Aluminium ores — Sampling procedures
ISO/CD 9033	Aluminium ores — Determination of the moisture content of bulk material

Table 19. Standards from ISO/TC 102.

Reference	Title
ISO 2596:2006	Iron ores — Determination of hygroscopic moisture in analytical samples — Gravimetric, Karl Fischer and mass-loss methods
ISO 2597-1:2006	Iron ores — Determination of total iron content — Part 1: Titrimetric method after tin(II) chloride reduction
ISO 2597-2:2019	Iron ores — Determination of total iron content — Part 2: Titrimetric methods after titanium(III) chloride reduction
ISO/TS 2597-4:2019	Iron ores — Determination of total iron content — Part 4: Potentiometric titration method
ISO 2598-1:1992	Iron ores — Determination of silicon content — Part 1: Gravimetric methods
ISO 2598-2:1992	Iron ores — Determination of silicon content — Part 2: Reduced molybdosilicate spectrophotometric method
ISO 2599:2003	Iron ores — Determination of phosphorus content — Titrimetric method
ISO 3082:2017	Iron ores — Sampling and sample preparation procedures
ISO 3084:1998	Iron ores — Experimental methods for evaluation of quality variation
ISO 3085:2019	Iron ores — Experimental methods for checking the precision of sampling, sample preparation and measurement
ISO 3086:2006	Iron ores — Experimental methods for checking the bias of sampling
ISO 3087:2020	Iron ores — Determination of the moisture content of a lot
ISO 3271:2015	Iron ores for blast furnace and direct reduction feedstocks — Determination of the tumble and abrasion indices
ISO 3852:2007	Iron ores for blast furnace and direct reduction feedstocks — Determination of bulk density
ISO 4687-1:1992	Iron ores — Determination of phosphorus content — Part 1: Molybdenum blue spectrophotometric method
ISO/TR 4688-1:2017	Iron ores — Determination of aluminium — Part 1: Flame atomic absorption spectrometric method
ISO/TS 4689-1:2023	Iron ores — Determination of sulfur content — Part 1: Barium sulfate gravimetric method
ISO 4689-2:2017	Iron ores — Determination of sulfur content — Part 2: Combustion/titration method
ISO 4689-3:2017	Iron ores — Determination of sulfur content — Part 3: Combustion/infrared method
ISO 4691:2009	Iron ores — Determination of titanium — Diantipryl methane spectrophotometric method
ISO 4694:1987	Iron ores — Determination of fluorine content — Ion-selective electrode method
ISO 4695:2021	Iron ores for blast furnace feedstocks — Determination of the reducibility by the rate of reduction index
ISO 4696-1:2015	Iron ores for blast furnace feedstocks — Determination of low-temperature reduction-disintegration indices by static method — Part 1: Reduction with CO, CO ₂ , H ₂ and N ₂
ISO 4696-2:2015	Iron ores for blast furnace feedstocks — Determination of low-temperature reduction-disintegration indices by static method — Part 2: Reduction with CO and N ₂
ISO 4698:2022	Iron ore pellets for blast furnace feedstocks — Determination of the free-swelling index
ISO 4700:2015	Iron ore pellets for blast furnace and direct reduction feedstocks — Determination of the crushing strength
ISO 4701:2019	Iron ores and direct reduced iron — Determination of size distribution by sieving
ISO 5416:2006	Direct reduced iron — Determination of metallic iron — Bromine-methanol titrimetric method
ISO 5418-1:2006	Iron ores — Determination of copper — Part 1: 2,2'-Biquinolyl spectrophotometric method
ISO 5418-2:2006	Iron ores — Determination of copper — Part 2: Flame atomic absorption spectrometric method
ISO 6830:1986	Iron ores — Determination of aluminium content — EDTA titrimetric method
ISO 7215:2015	Iron ores for blast furnace feedstocks — Determination of the reducibility by the final degree of reduction index
ISO 7335:1987	Iron ores — Determination of combined water content — Karl Fischer titrimetric method
ISO 7764:2006	Iron ores — Preparation of predried test samples for chemical analysis
ISO 7834:1987	Iron ores — Determination of arsenic content — Molybdenum blue spectrophotometric method
ISO 7992:2022	Iron ores for blast furnace feedstocks — Determination of reduction under load
ISO 8263:1992	Iron ore fines — Method for presentation of the results of sintering tests
ISO 8371:2024	Iron ores for blast furnace feedstocks — Determination of the decrepitation index
ISO 9035:1989	Iron ores — Determination of acid-soluble iron(II) content — Titrimetric method
ISO 9516-1:2003	Iron ores — Determination of various elements by X-ray fluorescence spectrometry — Part 1: Comprehensive procedure
ISO/TS 9516-2:2024	Iron ores — Determination of various elements by X-ray fluorescence spectrometry — Part 2: Single element calibration procedure

ISO/TS 9516-4:2021	Iron ores — Determination of various elements by X-ray fluorescence spectrometry — Part 4: Performance-based method using fusion preparation method
ISO 9517:2007	Iron ores — Determination of water-soluble chloride — Ion-selective electrode method
ISO 9682-1:2009	Iron ores — Determination of manganese content — Part 1: Flame atomic absorption spectrometric method
ISO 9682-2:2006	Iron ores — Determination of manganese content — Part 2: Periodate spectrophotometric method
ISO 9683-1:2006	Iron ores — Determination of vanadium — Part 1: BPHA spectrophotometric method
ISO 9683-2:2009	Iron ores — Determination of vanadium — Part 2: Flame atomic absorption spectrometric methods
ISO 9685:1991	Iron ores — Determination of nickel and/or chromium contents — Flame atomic absorption spectrometric method
ISO/TR 9686:2017	Direct reduced iron — Determination of carbon and/or sulfur — High-frequency combustion method with infrared measurement
ISO 10203:2017	Iron ores — Determination of calcium — Flame atomic absorption spectrometric method
ISO 10204:2017	Iron ores — Determination of magnesium — Flame atomic absorption spectrometric method
ISO 10835:2007	Direct reduced iron and hot briquetted iron — Sampling and sample preparation
ISO 11256:2015	Iron ore pellets for shaft direct-reduction feedstocks — Determination of the clustering index
ISO 11257:2022	Iron ores for shaft direct-reduction feedstocks — Determination of the low-temperature reduction-disintegration index and degree of metallization
ISO 11258:2015	Iron ores for shaft direct-reduction feedstocks — Determination of the reducibility index, final degree of reduction and degree of metallization
ISO 11323:2010	Iron ore and direct reduced iron — Vocabulary
ISO/TR 11422:1996	Iron ores — Recommended procedures for iron ore dissolution using either acid digestion or alkali fusion
ISO 11459:1997	Iron ores — Certified reference materials — Preparation and certification for use in chemical analysis
ISO 11533:2009	Iron ores — Determination of cobalt — Flame atomic absorption spectrometric method
ISO 11534:2006	Iron ores — Determination of tin — Flame atomic absorption spectrometric method
ISO 11535:2006	Iron ores — Determination of various elements — Inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectrometric method
ISO 11536:2015	Iron ores — Determination of loss on ignition — Gravimetric method
ISO 13310:1997	Iron ores — Determination of zinc content — Flame atomic absorption spectrometric method
ISO 13311:1997	Iron ores — Determination of lead content — Flame atomic absorption spectrometric method
ISO 13312:2017	Iron ores — Determination of potassium — Flame atomic absorption spectrometric method
ISO 13313:2017	Iron ores — Determination of sodium — Flame atomic absorption spectrometric method
ISO 13930:2015	Iron ores for blast furnace feedstocks — Determination of low-temperature reduction-disintegration indices by dynamic method
ISO 15633:2017	Iron ores — Determination of nickel — Flame atomic absorption spectrometric method
ISO 15634:2015	Iron ores — Determination of chromium content — Flame atomic absorption spectrometric method
ISO 15967:2007	Direct reduced iron — Determination of the tumble and abrasion indices of hot briquetted iron (HBI)
ISO 15968:2016	Direct reduced iron — Determination of apparent density and water absorption of hot briquetted iron (HBI)
ISO 16042:2007	Iron ores — Guidelines for the use of certified reference materials (CRMs)
ISO/TR 16043:2015	Iron ores — Determination of chlorine content — X-ray fluorescence spectrometric method
ISO 16742:2014	Iron ores — Sampling of slurries
ISO 16878:2016	Iron ores — Determination of metallic iron content — Iron(III) chloride titrimetric method
ISO 17992:2013	Iron ores — Determination of arsenic content — Hydride generation atomic absorption spectrometric method
ISO/TR 18230:2015	Iron ores — Determination of loss on ignition — Non-oxidised ores
ISO/TR 18231:2016	Iron ores — Wavelength dispersive X-ray fluorescence spectrometers — Determination of precision
ISO/TR 18336:2016	Guidelines for good XRF laboratory practice for the iron ore industry
ISO 21283:2018	Iron ores — Determination of specific surface area — Test method using air-permeability apparatus (Blaine)
ISO 21826-1:2022	Iron ores — Determination of total iron content using the EDTA photometric titration method — Part 1: Microwave digestion method
ISO 22682:2017	Iron ores — Determination of trace elements — Plasma spectrometric method

Table 20. ISO/TC 102 Projects under development.

Project Reference	Title
ISO/AWI 3082	Iron ores — Sampling and sample preparation procedures
ISO/CD 3084	Iron ores — Experimental methods for evaluation of quality variation
ISO/WD 4694	Iron ores — Determination of fluorine content — Ion-selective electrode method
ISO/AWI 15633	Iron ores — Determination of nickel — Flame atomic absorption spectrometric method
ISO/AWI 15634	Iron ores — Determination of chromium content — Flame atomic absorption spectrometric method
ISO/WD TR 20133	Iron ores — Determination of sodium content by X-ray fluorescence spectrometry
ISO/CD 21826-2	Iron ores — Determination of total iron content using the EDTA photometric titration method — Part 2: Fusion decomposition method
ISO/CD 25319	Determination of Fe Metal in sponge iron and briquettes

Table 21. Standards from ISO/TC 132.

Reference	Title
ISO 310:1992	Manganese ores and concentrates — Determination of hygroscopic moisture content in analytical samples — Gravimetric method
ISO 312:1986	Manganese ores — Determination of active oxygen content, expressed as manganese dioxide — Titrimetric method
ISO 315:1984	Manganese ores and concentrates — Determination of nickel content — Dimethylglyoxime spectrometric method and flame atomic absorption spectrometric method
ISO 317:1984	Manganese ores and concentrates — Determination of arsenic content — Spectrometric method
ISO 320:1981	Manganese ores — Determination of sulphur content — Barium sulphate gravimetric methods and sulphur dioxide titrimetric method after combustion
ISO 548:1981	Manganese ores — Determination of barium oxide content — Barium sulphate gravimetric method
ISO 549:1981	Manganese ores — Determination of combined water content — Gravimetric method
ISO 619:1981	Manganese ores — Determination of chromium content — Diphenylcarbazide photometric method and silver persulphate titrimetric method
ISO 3713:1987	Ferroalloys — Sampling and preparation of samples — General rules
ISO 4139:1979	Ferrosilicon — Determination of aluminium content — Flame atomic absorption spectrometric method
ISO 4140:1979	Ferrochromium and ferrosilicochromium — Determination of chromium content — Potentiometric method
ISO 4158:1978	Ferrosilicon, ferrosilicomanganese and ferrosilicochromium — Determination of silicon content — Gravimetric method
ISO 4159:1978	Ferromanganese and ferrosilicomanganese — Determination of manganese content — Potentiometric method
ISO 4293:1982	Manganese ores and concentrates — Determination of phosphorus content — Extraction-molybdovanadate photometric method
ISO 4295:1988	Manganese ores and concentrates — Determination of aluminium content — Photometric and gravimetric methods
ISO 4296-1:1984	Manganese ores — Sampling — Part 1: Increment sampling
ISO 4296-2:1983	Manganese ores — Sampling — Part 2: Preparation of samples
ISO 4297:1978	Manganese ores and concentrates — Methods of chemical analysis — General instructions
ISO 4298:2022	Manganese ores and concentrates — Determination of manganese content — Potentiometric method
ISO 4299:1989	Manganese ores — Determination of moisture content
ISO 4551:1987	Ferroalloys — Sampling and sieve analysis
ISO 4552-1:1987	Ferroalloys — Sampling and sample preparation for chemical analysis — Part 1: Ferrochromium, ferrosilicochromium, ferrosilicon, ferrosilicomanganese, ferromanganese
ISO 4552-2:1987	Ferroalloys — Sampling and sample preparation for chemical analysis — Part 2: Ferrotitanium, ferromolybdenum, ferrotungsten, ferroniobium, ferrovanadium

ISO 4571:1981	Manganese ores and concentrates — Determination of potassium and sodium content — Flame atomic emission spectrometric method
ISO 5445:1980	Ferrosilicon — Specification and conditions of delivery
ISO 5446:2017	Ferromanganese — Specification and conditions of delivery
ISO 5447:1980	Ferrosilicomanganese — Specification and conditions of delivery
ISO 5448:1981	Ferrochromium — Specification and conditions of delivery
ISO 5449:1980	Ferrosilicochromium — Specification and conditions of delivery
ISO 5450:1980	Ferrotungsten — Specification and conditions of delivery
ISO 5451:2022	Ferrovandium — Specification and conditions of delivery
ISO 5452:1980	Ferromolybdenum — Specification and conditions of delivery
ISO 5453:1980	Ferroniobium — Specification and conditions of delivery
ISO 5454:1980	Ferrotitanium — Specification and conditions of delivery
ISO 5889:1983	Manganese ores and concentrates — Determination of aluminium, copper, lead and zinc contents — Flame atomic absorption spectrometric method
ISO 5890:1981	Manganese ores and concentrates — Determination of silicon content — Gravimetric method
ISO 5975:1983	Chromium ores — Determination of calcium and magnesium contents — EDTA titrimetric method
ISO 5997:1984	Chromium ores and concentrates — Determination of silicon content — Molecular absorption spectrometric method and gravimetric method
ISO 6127:1981	Chromium ores — Determination of phosphorus content — Reduced molybdophosphate photometric method
ISO 6129:1981	Chromium ores — Determination of hygroscopic moisture content in analytical samples — Gravimetric method
ISO 6130:1985	Chromium ores — Determination of total iron content — Titrimetric method after reduction
ISO 6153:1989	Chromium ores — Increment sampling
ISO 6154:1989	Chromium ores — Preparation of samples
ISO 6230:1989	Manganese ores — Determination of size distribution by sieving
ISO 6233:1983	Manganese ores and concentrates — Determination of calcium and magnesium contents — EDTA titrimetric method
ISO 6331:2024	Chromium ores and concentrates — Determination of chromium content — Titrimetric method
ISO 6467:2018	Ferrovandium — Determination of vanadium content — Potentiometric method
ISO 6629:1981	Chromium ores and concentrates — Methods of chemical analysis — General instructions
ISO 7087:1984	Ferroalloys — Experimental methods for the evaluation of the quality variation and methods for checking the precision of sampling
ISO 7347:1987	Ferroalloys — Experimental methods for checking the bias of sampling and sample preparation
ISO 7373:1987	Ferroalloys — Experimental methods for checking the precision of sample division
ISO 7692:1983	Ferrotitanium — Determination of titanium content — Titrimetric method
ISO 7693:1984	Ferrotungsten — Determination of tungsten content — Cinchonine gravimetric method
ISO 7723:1984	Manganese ores and concentrates — Determination of titanium content — 4,4'-Diantiprylmethane spectrometric method
ISO 7953:1985	Manganese ores and concentrates — Determination of calcium and magnesium contents — Flame atomic absorption spectrometric method
ISO 7969:1985	Manganese ores and concentrates — Determination of sodium and potassium contents — Flame atomic absorption spectrometric method
ISO 7990:1985	Manganese ores and concentrates — Determination of total iron content — Titrimetric method after reduction and sulfosalicylic acid spectrophotometric method
ISO 8530:1986	Manganese and chromium ores — Experimental methods for checking the precision of sample division
ISO 8531:1986	Manganese and chromium ores — Experimental methods for checking the precision of moisture determination
ISO 8541:1986	Manganese and chromium ores — Experimental methods for checking the bias of sampling and sample preparation
ISO 8542:1986	Manganese and chromium ores — Experimental methods for evaluation of quality variation and methods for checking the precision of sampling
ISO 8889:1988	Chromium ores and concentrates — Determination of aluminium content — Complexometric method
ISO 8954-1:1990	Ferroalloys — Vocabulary — Part 1: Materials
ISO 8954-2:1990	Ferroalloys — Vocabulary — Part 2: Sampling and sample preparation
ISO 8954-3:1990	Ferroalloys — Vocabulary — Part 3: Sieve analysis
ISO 9292:1988	Manganese ores and concentrates — Determination of total iron content — 1,10-Phenanthroline spectrometric method

ISO 9681:1990	Manganese ores and concentrates — Determination of iron content — Flame atomic absorption spectrometric method
ISO 10386:1994	Ferroboron — Specification and conditions of delivery
ISO 10387:1994	Metal chrome — Specification and conditions of delivery

Table 22. ISO/TC 132 Projects under development.

Project Reference	Title
ISO/WD 9681	Manganese ores and concentrates — Determination of iron content — Flame atomic absorption spectrometric method

Table 23. Standards from ISO/TC 298.

Reference	Title
ISO 22444-1:2020	Rare earth — Vocabulary — Part 1: Minerals, oxides and other compounds
ISO 22444-2:2020	Rare earth — Vocabulary — Part 2: Metals and their alloys
ISO 22450:2020	Recycling of rare earth elements — Requirements for providing information on industrial waste and end-of-life products
ISO/TS 22451:2021	Recycling of rare earth elements — Methods for the measurement of rare earth elements in industrial waste and end-of-life products
ISO 22453:2021	Exchange of information on rare earth elements in industrial wastes and end-of-life cycled products
ISO 22927:2021	Rare earth — Packaging and labelling
ISO 22928-1:2024	Rare earth — Analysis by wavelength dispersive x-ray fluorescence spectrometry (WD-XRFS) — Part 1: Determination of composition of rare earth magnet scrap using standardless XRF commercial packages
ISO 23596:2023	Rare earth — Determination of rare earth content in individual rare earth metals and their compounds — Gravimetric method
ISO 23597:2023	Rare earth — Determination of rare earth content in individual rare earth metals and their oxides — Titration method
ISO 23664:2021	Traceability of rare earths in the supply chain from mine to separated products
ISO 24181-1:2024	Rare earth — Determination of non-rare earth impurities in individual rare earth metals and their oxides — ICP-AES — Part 1: Analysis of Al, Ca, Mg, Fe and Si
ISO 24544:2024	Rare earth — Recyclable Neodymium iron boron (NdFeB) resources — Classification, general requirements and acceptance conditions

Table 24. ISO/TC 298 Projects under development.

Project Reference	Title
ISO/FDIS 5976	Rare earth — Determination of loss on ignition in rare earth products — Gravimetric method
ISO/FDIS 17887	Traceability of rare earths in the supply chain from separated products to permanent magnets
ISO/WD 19456	Determination of rare earth impurity contents in individual rare earth metals and their oxides — Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry Part 1: Determination of rare earth impurity contents in individual La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Sm metals and their oxides
ISO/AWI 24457	Specifications for recycling of neodymium iron boron sintered permanent magnets
ISO/AWI 24468	Praseodymium-neodymium metal
ISO/FDIS 24548	Rare earth — Determination of moisture content in rare earth products — Gravimetric method
ISO/AWI 24961	Rare earths and lithium sustainability across the value chain : concentration, extraction, separation, conversion, recycling and reuse
ISO/AWI 25191	Guidelines for evaluating environmental impacts on the supply chain of rare earth elements

Table 25. Standards from ISO/TC 119.

Reference	Title
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ISO 2738:1999	Sintered metal materials, excluding hardmetals — Permeable sintered metal materials — Determination of density, oil content and open porosity
ISO 2739:2012	Sintered metal bushings — Determination of radial crushing strength
ISO 2740:2023	Sintered metal materials, excluding hardmetals — Tensile test pieces
ISO 3252:2023	Powder metallurgy — Vocabulary
ISO 3312:1987	Sintered metal materials and hardmetals — Determination of Young modulus
ISO 3325:1996	Sintered metal materials, excluding hardmetals — Determination of transverse rupture strength
ISO 3325:1996/ Amd 1:2001	Sintered metal materials, excluding hardmetals — Determination of transverse rupture strength — Amendment 1: Precision statement
ISO 3327:2009	Hardmetals — Determination of transverse rupture strength
ISO 3369:2006	Impermeable sintered metal materials and hardmetals — Determination of density
ISO 3738-1:1982	Hardmetals — Rockwell hardness test (scale A) — Part 1: Test method
ISO 3738-2:1988	Hardmetals — Rockwell hardness test (scale A) — Part 2: Preparation and calibration of standard test blocks
ISO 3907:2009	Hardmetals — Determination of total carbon — Gravimetric method
ISO 3908:2009	Hardmetals — Determination of insoluble (free) carbon — Gravimetric method
ISO 3909:1976	Hardmetals — Determination of cobalt — Potentiometric method
ISO 3923-1:2018	Metallic powders — Determination of apparent density — Part 1: Funnel method
ISO 3923-2:1981	Metallic powders — Determination of apparent density — Part 2: Scott volumeter method
ISO 3927:2017	Metallic powders, excluding powders for hardmetals — Determination of compressibility in uniaxial compression
ISO 3928:2016	Sintered metal materials, excluding hardmetals — Fatigue test pieces
ISO 3953:2011	Metallic powders — Determination of tap density
ISO 3954:2007	Powders for powder metallurgical purposes — Sampling
ISO 3995:2023	Metallic powders — Determination of green strength by transverse rupture of rectangular compacts
ISO 4003:1977	Permeable sintered metal materials — Determination of bubble test pore size
ISO 4022:2018	Permeable sintered metal materials — Determination of fluid permeability
ISO 4489:2019	Hardmetals — Sampling and testing
ISO 4490:2018	Metallic powders — Determination of flow rate by means of a calibrated funnel (Hall flowmeter)
ISO 4491-1:2023	Metallic powders — Determination of oxygen content by reduction methods — Part 1: General guidelines
ISO 4491-2:2023	Metallic powders — Determination of oxygen content by reduction methods — Part 2: Loss of mass on hydrogen reduction (hydrogen loss)
ISO 4491-3:1997	Metallic powders — Determination of oxygen content by reduction methods — Part 3: Hydrogen-reducible oxygen
ISO 4491-4:2019	Metallic powders — Determination of oxygen content by reduction methods — Part 4: Total oxygen by reduction-extraction
ISO 4492:2017	Metallic powders, excluding powders for hardmetals — Determination of dimensional changes associated with compacting and sintering
ISO 4496:2017	Metallic powders — Determination of acid-insoluble content in iron, copper, tin and bronze powders
ISO 4497:2020	Metallic powders — Determination of particle size by dry sieving
ISO 4498:2010	Sintered metal materials, excluding hardmetals — Determination of apparent hardness and microhardness
ISO 4499-1:2020	Hardmetals — Metallographic determination of microstructure — Part 1: Photomicrographs and description
ISO 4499-2:2020	Hardmetals — Metallographic determination of microstructure — Part 2: Measurement of WC grain size
ISO 4499-3:2016	Hardmetals — Metallographic determination of microstructure — Part 3: Measurement of microstructural features in Ti (C, N) and WC/cubic carbide based hardmetals
ISO 4499-4:2016	Hardmetals — Metallographic determination of microstructure — Part 4: Characterisation of porosity, carbon defects and eta-phase content
ISO 4501:1978	Hardmetals — Determination of titanium — Photometric peroxide method
ISO 4503:1978	Hardmetals — Determination of contents of metallic elements by X-ray fluorescence — Fusion method
ISO 4506:2018	Hardmetals — Compression test
ISO 4507:2000	Sintered ferrous materials, carburized or carbonitrided — Determination and verification of case-hardening depth by a micro-hardness test

ISO 4883:1978	Hardmetals — Determination of contents of metallic elements by X-ray fluorescence — Solution method
ISO 4884:2019	Hardmetals — Sampling and testing of powders using sintered test pieces
ISO 5754:2023	Sintered metal materials, excluding hardmetals — Unnotched impact test piece
ISO 5755:2022	Sintered metal material — Specifications
ISO 5842:2022	Powder metallurgy — Hot isostatic pressing — Argon detection using gas chromatography and mass spectrometry techniques
ISO 7625:2012	Sintered metal materials, excluding hardmetals — Preparation of samples for chemical analysis for determination of carbon content
ISO 7627-1:1983	Hardmetals — Chemical analysis by flame atomic absorption spectrometry — Part 1: General requirements
ISO 7627-2:1983	Hardmetals — Chemical analysis by flame atomic absorption spectrometry — Part 2: Determination of calcium, potassium, magnesium and sodium in contents from 0,001 to 0,02 % (m/m)
ISO 7627-3:1983	Hardmetals — Chemical analysis by flame atomic absorption spectrometry — Part 3: Determination of cobalt, iron, manganese and nickel in contents from 0,01 to 0,5 % (m/m)
ISO 7627-4:1983	Hardmetals — Chemical analysis by flame atomic absorption spectrometry — Part 4: Determination of molybdenum, titanium and vanadium in contents from 0,01 to 0,5 % (m/m)
ISO 7627-5:1983	Hardmetals — Chemical analysis by flame atomic absorption spectrometry — Part 5: Determination of cobalt, iron, manganese, molybdenum, nickel, titanium and vanadium in contents from 0,5 to 2 % (m/m)
ISO 7627-6:1985	Hardmetals — Chemical analysis by flame atomic absorption spectrometry — Part 6: Determination of chromium in contents from 0,01 to 2 % (m/m)
ISO 10070:2019	Metallic powders — Determination of envelope-specific surface area from measurements of the permeability to air of a powder bed under steady-state flow conditions
ISO 11873:2005	Hardmetals — Determination of sulfur and carbon contents in cobalt metal powders — Infrared detection method
ISO 11873:2005/ Cor 1:2008	Hardmetals — Determination of sulfur and carbon contents in cobalt metal powders — Infrared detection method — Technical Corrigendum 1
ISO 11876:2010	Hardmetals — Determination of calcium, copper, iron, potassium, magnesium, manganese, sodium, nickel and zinc in cobalt metal powders — Flame atomic absorption spectrometric method
ISO 11877:2008	Hardmetals — Determination of silicon in cobalt metal powders — Photometric method
ISO 13517:2020	Metallic powders — Determination of flow rate by means of a calibrated funnel (Gustavsson flowmeter)
ISO 13944:2012	Lubricated metal-powder mixes — Determination of lubricant content — Soxhlet extraction method
ISO 13947:2024	Metallic powders — Test method for the determination of non-metallic inclusions in metal powders using a powder-forged specimen
ISO 14168:2011	Metallic powders, excluding hardmetals — Method for testing copper-base infiltrating powders
ISO 14317:2015	Sintered metal materials excluding hardmetals — Determination of compressive yield strength
ISO 17352:2008	Hardmetals — Determination of silicon in cobalt metal powders using graphite-furnace atomic absorption
ISO 18549-1:2009	Metallic powders — Determination of apparent density and flow rate at elevated temperatures — Part 1: Determination of apparent density at elevated temperatures
ISO 18549-2:2009	Metallic powders — Determination of apparent density and flow rate at elevated temperatures — Part 2: Determination of flow rate at elevated temperatures
ISO 22068:2012	Sintered-metal injection-moulded materials — Specifications
ISO 23519:2010	Sintered metal materials, excluding hardmetals — Measurement of surface roughness
ISO 26482:2010	Hardmetals — Determination of lead and cadmium content
ISO 28079:2009	Hardmetals — Palmqvist toughness test
ISO 28080:2021	Hardmetals — Abrasion tests for hardmetals
ISO 28279:2010	Sintered metal materials — Determination of the level of cleanliness of powder-metallurgy parts

Table 26. ISO/TC 119 Projects under development.

Project Reference	Title
ISO/DIS 2738	Sintered metal materials, excluding hardmetals — Permeable sintered metal materials — Determination of density, oil content and open porosity

ISO/DIS 3325	Sintered metal materials, excluding hardmetals — Determination of transverse rupture strength
ISO/FDIS 3953	Metallic powders — Determination of tap density
ISO/FDIS 4491-3	Metallic powders — Determination of oxygen content by reduction methods — Part 3: Hydrogen-reducible oxygen
ISO/WD 22617	Metallic Powders — Soft magnetic composite materials — Specifications
ISO/AWI TR 23858	Preparation of metallographic specimens used for porosity determination
ISO/CD TR 23867.2	Ultrasonic testing of hardmetals
ISO/DIS 28079	Hardmetals — Palmqvist toughness test

Table 27. Standards from CEN/TC 458.

Reference	Title
EN 17877:2023	Dynamic mixers and agitators — Definitions and hydraulic characterizations

Table 28. Standards from IEC/TC 65.

Reference	Title
IEC 60381-1:1982	Analogue signals for process control systems. Part 1: Direct current signals
IEC 60381-2:1978	Analogue signals for process control systems. Part 2: Direct voltage signals
IEC 60382:1991	Analogue pneumatic signal for process control systems
IEC 60946:1988	Binary direct voltage signals for process measurement and control systems
IEC 61010-2-201:2024	Safety requirements for electrical equipment for measurement, control, and laboratory use — Part 2-201: Particular requirements for control equipment
IEC 61010-2-202:2020	Safety requirements for electrical equipment for measurement, control and laboratory use — Part 2-202: Particular requirements for electrically operated valve actuators
IEC TS 61081:1991	Pneumatic instruments driven by associated process gas — Safe installation and operating procedures — Guidelines
IEC 61506:1997	Industrial-process measurement and control — Documentation of application software
IEC 62419:2008	Control technology — Rules for the designation of measuring instruments
IEC 62424:2016	Representation of process control engineering — Requests in P&ID diagrams and data exchange between P&ID tools and PCE-CAE tools
IEC TS 62443-1-1:2009	Industrial communication networks — Network and system security — Part 1-1: Terminology, concepts and models
IEC TS 62443-1-5:2023	Security for industrial automation and control systems — Part 1-5: Scheme for IEC 62443 security profiles
IEC 62443-2-1:2024	Industrial communication networks — Network and system security — Part 2-1: Establishing an industrial automation and control system security program
IEC PAS 62443-2-2:2025	Security for industrial automation and control systems – Part 2-2: IACS security protection scheme
IEC TR 62443-2-3:2015	Security for industrial automation and control systems — Part 2-3: Patch management in the IACS environment
IEC 62443-2-4:2023	Security for industrial automation and control systems — Part 2-4: Security program requirements for IACS service providers
IEC TR 62443-3-1:2009	Industrial communication networks — Network and system security — Part 3-1: Security technologies for industrial automation and control systems
IEC 62443-3-2:2020	Security for industrial automation and control systems — Part 3-2: Security risk assessment for system design
IEC 62443-3-3:2013/ COR1:2014	Corrigendum 1 — Industrial communication networks — Network and system security — Part 3-3: System security requirements and security levels
IEC 62443-3-3:2013	Industrial communication networks — Network and system security — Part 3-3: System security requirements and security levels
IEC 62443-4-1:2018	Security for industrial automation and control systems — Part 4-1: Secure product development lifecycle requirements
IEC 62443-4-2:2019/ COR1:2022	Corrigendum 1 — Security for industrial automation and control systems — Part 4-2: Technical security requirements for IACS components
IEC 62443-4-2:2019	Security for industrial automation and control systems — Part 4-2: Technical security requirements for IACS components

IEC TS 62443-6-1:2024	Security for industrial automation and control systems — Part 6-1: Security evaluation methodology for IEC 62443-2-4
IEC TS 62443-6-2:2025	Security for industrial automation and control systems - Part 6-2: Security evaluation methodology for IEC 62443-4-2
IEC 62708:2015	Documents kinds for electrical and instrumentation projects in the process industry
IEC 62832-1:2020	Industrial-process measurement, control and automation — Digital factory framework — Part 1: General principles
IEC 62832-2:2020	Industrial-process measurement, control and automation — Digital factory framework — Part 2: Model elements
IEC 62832-3:2020	Industrial-process measurement, control and automation — Digital factory framework — Part 3: Application of Digital Factory for life cycle management of production systems
IEC TR 63283-5:2024	Industrial-process measurement, control and automation – Smart manufacturing – Part 5: Market and innovation trends analysis
IEC TR 63319:2025	A meta-modelling analysis approach to smart manufacturing reference models
IEC 63339:2024	Unified reference model for smart manufacturing
IEC 63376:2023	Industrial facility energy management system (FEMS) - Functions and information flows
IEC PAS 63441:2022	Functional architecture of industrial internet system for industrial automation applications
ISO 20140-5:2024	Automation systems and integration - Evaluating energy efficiency and other factors of manufacturing systems that influence the environment - Part 5: Environmental performance evaluation data
IEC TR 62837:2013	Energy efficiency through automation systems
IEC TS 62872-1:2019	Industrial-process measurement, control and automation — Part 1: System interface between industrial facilities and the smart grid
IEC 62872-2:2022	Industrial-process measurement, control and automation — Part 2: Internet of Things (IoT) — Application framework for industrial facility demand response energy management
IEC 62881:2018	Cause and effect matrix
IEC 62890:2020	Industrial-process measurement, control and automation — Life-cycle-management for systems and components
IEC TR 63069:2019	Industrial-process measurement, control and automation — Framework for functional safety and security
IEC TS 63164-1:2020	Reliability of industrial automation devices and systems — Part 1: Assurance of automation devices reliability data and specification of their source
IEC TR 63164-2:2020	Reliability of industrial automation devices and systems — Part 2: System reliability
IEC 63278-1:2023	Asset Administration Shell for industrial applications — Part 1: Asset Administration Shell structure
IEC TR 63283-1:2022	Industrial-process measurement, control and automation — Smart manufacturing — Part 1: Terms and definitions
IEC TR 63283-2:2022	Industrial-process measurement, control and automation — Smart manufacturing — Part 2: Use cases
IEC TR 63283-3:2022	Industrial-process measurement, control and automation — Smart manufacturing — Part 3: Challenges for cybersecurity
IEC PAS 63325:2020	Lifecycle requirements for functional safety and security for IACS
IEC 63376:2023	Industrial facility energy management system (FEMS) — Functions and information flows
IEC PAS 63441:2022	Functional architecture of industrial internet system for industrial automation applications

Table 29. IEC/TC 65 Projects under development.

Project Reference	Title
PNW 65-1120 ED1	Industrial Automation Product Data
PNW 65-1126 ED1	Application function blocks and logic diagrams for Upstream Oil & Gas processes – System Control Diagrams – Part 3: Application Function Blocks
PNW 65-1127 ED1	Application function blocks and logic diagrams for Upstream Oil & Gas processes – System Control Diagrams – Part 2: Diagram symbols and drawing principles
IEC 60050-351 ED5	International Electrotechnical Vocabulary (IEV) - Part 351: Control technology
IEC 62443-1-1 ED1	Security for automation and control systems – Part 1-1: Overview and Guidance for the IEC 62443 Series
IEC PAS 62443-1-6 ED1	Security for Industrial Automation and Control Systems - Part 1-6: Application of the IEC 62443 standards to the Industrial Internet of Things
IEC 62443-6-1 ED1	Security for Automation and Control Systems - Part 6-1: Security evaluation methodology for IEC 62443-2-4

IEC TS 63069 ED1	Framework for safety and security
IEC 63131-1 ED1	Application function blocks and logic diagrams for Upstream Oil & Gas processes – System Control Diagrams – Part 1: General principles
IEC 63278-2 ED1	Asset Administration Shell for Industrial Applications – Part 2: Information meta model
IEC 63278-3 ED1	Asset Administration Shell for Industrial Applications – Part 3: Security provisions for Asset Administration Shells
IEC 63278-4 ED1	Asset administration shell for industrial applications - Part 4: Applications of Asset Administration Shell
IEC 63278-5 ED1	Asset Administration Shell for industrial applications – Part 5: Interfaces
IEC TR 63283-2 ED2	Industrial-process measurement, control and automation - Smart manufacturing - Part 2: Use cases
IEC TS 63283-2 ED1	Industrial-process measurement, control and automation - Smart manufacturing - Part 2: Use cases
IEC TR 63283-4 ED1	Industrial-process measurement, control and automation – Smart Manufacturing – Part 4: Recommendations for the usage of new technologies
IEC TR 63319:2025 ED1	A meta-modelling analysis approach to smart manufacturing reference models
IEC TR 63597 ED1	Application of IEC 63339 to Smart Manufacturing Reference Models
IEC TR 63657-1 ED1	Internet of Things (IoT) - Part 1: IoT Applications for Long-distance Oil and Gas Pipeline
IEC TR 63657-2 ED1	Internet of Things (IoT) – Part 2: IoT applications for natural gas distribution system

Table 30. Standards from IEC/TC 27.

Reference	Title
IEC 60239:2005	Graphite electrodes for electric arc furnaces - Dimensions and designation
IEC 60398:2015	Installations for electroheating and electromagnetic processing - General performance test methods
IEC 60519-1:2020	Safety in installations for electroheating and electromagnetic processing - Part 1: General requirements
IEC 60519-3:2005	Safety in electroheat installations - Part 3: Particular requirements for induction and conduction heating and induction melting installations
IEC 60519-4:2021	Safety in installations for electroheating and electromagnetic processing - Part 4: Particular requirements for arc furnace installations
IEC 60519-6:2022	Safety in installations for electroheating and electromagnetic processing - Part 6: Particular requirements for high frequency dielectric and microwave heating and processing equipment
IEC 60519-7:2008	Safety in electroheat installations - Part 7: Particular requirements for installations with electron guns
IEC 60519-8:2020	Safety in installations for electroheating and electromagnetic processing - Part 8: Particular requirements for electroslag remelting furnaces
IEC 60519-11:2007	Safety in electroheat installations - Part 11: Particular requirements for installations using the effect of electromagnetic forces on liquid metals
IEC 60519-12:2016	Safety in installations for electroheating and electromagnetic processing - Part 12: Particular requirements for infrared electroheating
IEC 60676:2024	Industrial electroheating equipment - Test methods for direct arc furnaces
IEC TS 60680:2008	Test methods of plasma equipment for electroheat and electrochemical applications
IEC 60683:2011	Industrial electroheating equipment - Test methods for submerged-arc furnaces
IEC 60703:2008	Test methods for electroheating installations with electron guns
IEC 60779:2020	Installations for electroheating and electromagnetic processing - Test methods for electroslag remelting furnaces
IEC 61307:2011	Industrial microwave heating installations - Test methods for the determination of power output
IEC 61308:2005	High-frequency dielectric heating installations - Test methods for the determination of power output
IEC TR 62157:2001	Cylindrical machined carbon electrodes - Nominal dimensions
IEC/IEEE 62395-1:2024	Electrical resistance trace heating systems for industrial and commercial applications - Part 1: General and testing requirements
IEC/IEEE 62395-2:2024	Electrical resistance trace heating systems for industrial and commercial applications - Part 2: Application guide for system design, installation and maintenance
IEC 62693:2013	Industrial electroheating installations - Test methods for infrared electroheating installations
IEC 62798:2014	Industrial electroheating equipment - Test methods for infrared emitters
IEC 62798:2014/COR1:2014	Corrigendum 1 - Industrial electroheating equipment - Test methods for infrared emitters

IEC TS 62996:2017	Industrial electroheating and electromagnetic processing equipment - Requirements on touch currents, voltages and electric fields from 1 kHz to 6 MHz
IEC TS 62997:2017	Industrial electroheating and electromagnetic processing equipment - Evaluation of hazards caused by magnetic nearfields from 1 Hz to 6 MHz
IEC 63078:2019	Installations for electroheating and electromagnetic processing - Test methods for induction through-heating installations

Table 31. IEC/TC 27 Projects under development.

Project Reference	Title
IEC 60050-841 ED3	International Electrotechnical Vocabulary (IEV) - Part 841: Industrial electroheating and electromagnetic processing
IEC 60519-4/AMD1 ED5	Amendment 1 - Safety in installations for electroheating and electromagnetic processing - Part 4: Particular requirements for arc furnace installations
IEC 60683 ED3	Industrial electroheating equipment - Test methods for submerged-arc furnaces
IEC 61307 ED4	Industrial microwave heating installations - Test methods for the determination of power output
IEC 61308 ED3	High-frequency dielectric heating installations - Test methods for the determination of power output

Table 32. Standards from ISO/TC 24.

Reference	Title
SO/AWI TS 4806	Guideline for evaluation of particle number concentration of suspended particles in liquid
ISO/TS 4807:2022	Reference materials for particle size measurement — Specification of requirements
ISO/TS 5973:2024	Laser diffraction measurements — Good practice
ISO 9276-1:1998	Representation of results of particle size analysis — Part 1: Graphical representation
ISO 9276-1:1998/ Cor 1:2004	Representation of results of particle size analysis — Part 1: Graphical representation — Technical Corrigendum 1
ISO 9276-2:2014	Representation of results of particle size analysis — Part 2: Calculation of average particle sizes/diameters and moments from particle size distributions
ISO 9276-3:2008	Representation of results of particle size analysis — Part 3: Adjustment of an experimental curve to a reference model
ISO 9276-4:2001	Representation of results of particle size analysis — Part 4: Characterization of a classification process
ISO 9276-4:2001/ Amd 1:2017	Representation of results of particle size analysis — Part 4: Characterization of a classification process — Amendment 1: Additional explanations and minor corrections
ISO 9276-5:2005	Representation of results of particle size analysis — Part 5: Methods of calculation relating to particle size analyses using logarithmic normal probability distribution
ISO 9276-6:2008	Representation of results of particle size analysis — Part 6: Descriptive and quantitative representation of particle shape and morphology
ISO 9277:2022	Determination of the specific surface area of solids by gas adsorption — BET method
ISO 12154:2014	Determination of density by volumetric displacement — Skeleton density by gas pycnometry
ISO/TR 13097:2013	Guidelines for the characterization of dispersion stability
ISO 13099-1:2012	Colloidal systems — Methods for zeta-potential determination — Part 1: Electroacoustic and electrokinetic phenomena
ISO 13099-2:2012	Colloidal systems — Methods for zeta-potential determination — Part 2: Optical methods
ISO 13099-3:2014	Colloidal systems — Methods for zeta potential determination — Part 3: Acoustic methods
ISO 13100:2024	Methods for zeta potential determination — Streaming potential and streaming current methods for porous materials
ISO 13317-1:2024	Determination of particle size distribution by gravitational liquid sedimentation methods — Part 1: General principles, requirements and guidance
ISO 13317-2:2001	Determination of particle size distribution by gravitational liquid sedimentation methods — Part 2: Fixed pipette method
ISO 13317-3:2001	Determination of particle size distribution by gravitational liquid sedimentation methods — Part 3: X-ray gravitational technique
ISO 13317-4:2014	Determination of particle size distribution by gravitational liquid sedimentation methods — Part 4: Balance method

ISO 13317-5:2025	Determination of particle size distribution by gravitational liquid sedimentation methods — Part 5: Photosedimentation techniques
ISO 13318-1:2024	Determination of particle size distribution by centrifugal liquid sedimentation methods — Part 1: General principles, requirements and guidance
ISO 13318-2:2007	Determination of particle size distribution by centrifugal liquid sedimentation methods — Part 2: Photocentrifuge method
ISO 13318-3:2004	Determination of particle size distribution by centrifugal liquid sedimentation methods — Part 3: Centrifugal X-ray method
ISO 13319-1:2021	Determination of particle size distribution — Electrical sensing zone method — Part 1: Aperture/orifice tube method
ISO 13319-2:2023	Determination of particle size distribution — Electrical sensing zone method — Part 2: Tunable resistive pulse sensing method
ISO 13320:2020	Particle size analysis — Laser diffraction methods
ISO 13322-1:2014	Particle size analysis — Image analysis methods — Part 1: Static image analysis methods
ISO 13322-2:2021	Particle size analysis — Image analysis methods — Part 2: Dynamic image analysis methods
ISO/TS 14411-1:2017	Preparation of particulate reference materials — Part 1: Polydisperse material based on picket fence of monodisperse spherical particles
ISO 14411-2:2020	Preparation of particulate reference materials — Part 2: Polydisperse spherical particles
ISO 14488:2007	Particulate materials — Sampling and sample splitting for the determination of particulate properties
ISO 14488:2007/ Amd 1:2019	Particulate materials — Sampling and sample splitting for the determination of particulate properties — Amendment 1
ISO 14887:2000	Sample preparation — Dispersing procedures for powders in liquids
ISO 15900:2020	Determination of particle size distribution — Differential electrical mobility analysis for aerosol particles
ISO 15901-1:2016	Evaluation of pore size distribution and porosity of solid materials by mercury porosimetry and gas adsorption — Part 1: Mercury porosimetry
ISO 15901-2:2022	Pore size distribution and porosity of solid materials by mercury porosimetry and gas adsorption — Part 2: Analysis of nanopores by gas adsorption
ISO 17867:2020	Particle size analysis — Small angle X-ray scattering (SAXS)
ISO 18747-1:2018	Determination of particle density by sedimentation methods — Part 1: Isopycnic interpolation approach
ISO 18747-2:2019	Determination of particle density by sedimentation methods — Part 2: Multi-velocity approach
ISO 19430:2024	Particle size analysis — Particle tracking analysis (PTA) method
ISO 19996:2024	Charge conditioning of aerosol particles for particle characterization and the generation of calibration and test aerosols
ISO/TR 19997:2018	Guidelines for good practices in zeta-potential measurement
ISO 20804:2022	Determination of the specific surface area of porous and particulate systems by small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS)
ISO 20998-1:2006	Measurement and characterization of particles by acoustic methods — Part 1: Concepts and procedures in ultrasonic attenuation spectroscopy
ISO 20998-2:2022	Measurement and characterization of particles by acoustic methods — Part 2: Linear theory
ISO 20998-3:2017	Measurement and characterization of particles by acoustic methods — Part 3: Guidelines for non-linear theory
ISO 21501-1:2009	Determination of particle size distribution — Single particle light interaction methods — Part 1: Light scattering aerosol spectrometer
ISO 21501-2:2019	Determination of particle size distribution — Single particle light interaction methods — Part 2: Light scattering liquid-borne particle counter
ISO 21501-3:2019	Determination of particle size distribution — Single particle light interaction methods — Part 3: Light extinction liquid-borne particle counter
ISO 21501-4:2018	Determination of particle size distribution — Single particle light interaction methods — Part 4: Light scattering airborne particle counter for clean spaces
ISO 21501-4:2018/ Amd 1:2023	Determination of particle size distribution — Single particle light interaction methods — Part 4: Light scattering airborne particle counter for clean spaces — Amendment 1
ISO/TS 22107:2021	Dispersibility of solid particles into a liquid
ISO 22412:2017	Particle size analysis — Dynamic light scattering (DLS)
ISO/TR 22814:2020	Good practice for dynamic light scattering (DLS) measurements
ISO 23484:2023	Determination of particle concentration by small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS)
ISO 26824:2022	Particle characterization of particulate systems — Vocabulary
ISO 27891:2015	Aerosol particle number concentration — Calibration of condensation particle counters

ISO 565:1990	Test sieves — Metal wire cloth, perforated metal plate and electroformed sheet — Nominal sizes of openings
ISO 2194:1991	Industrial screens — Woven wire cloth, perforated plate and electroformed sheet — Designation and nominal sizes of openings
ISO 2395:1990	Test sieves and test sieving — Vocabulary
ISO 2591-1:1988	Test sieving — Part 1: Methods using test sieves of woven wire cloth and perforated metal plate
ISO 3310-1:2016	Test sieves — Technical requirements and testing — Part 1: Test sieves of metal wire cloth
ISO 3310-2:2013	Test sieves — Technical requirements and testing — Part 2: Test sieves of perforated metal plate
ISO 3310-3:1990	Test sieves — Technical requirements and testing — Part 3: Test sieves of electroformed sheets
ISO 4782:1987	Metal wire for industrial wire screens and woven wire cloth
ISO 4783-1:1989	Industrial wire screens and woven wire cloth — Guide to the choice of aperture size and wire diameter combinations — Part 1: Generalities
ISO 4783-2:1989	Industrial wire screens and woven wire cloth — Guide to the choice of aperture size and wire diameter combinations — Part 2: Preferred combinations for woven wire cloth
ISO 4783-3:1981	Industrial wire screens and woven wire cloth — Guide to the choice of aperture size and wire diameter combinations — Part 3: Preferred combinations for pre-crimped or pressure-welded wire screens
ISO 7805-1:1984	Industrial plate screens — Part 1: Thickness of 3 mm and above
ISO 7805-2:1987	Industrial plate screens — Part 2: Thickness below 3 mm
ISO 7806:1983	Industrial plate screens — Codification for designating perforations
ISO 9044:2016	Industrial woven wire cloth — Technical requirements and tests
ISO 9045:1990	Industrial screens and screening — Vocabulary
ISO 10630:1994	Industrial plate screens — Specifications and test methods
ISO 14315:1997	Industrial wire screens — Technical requirements and testing

Table 33. ISO/TC 24 Projects under development.

Project Reference	Title
ISO/AWI TS 4806	Guideline for evaluation of particle number concentration of suspended particles in liquid
ISO/PRF 9276-1	Representation of results of particle size analysis — Part 1: Graphical representation
ISO/PRF 13099-2	Colloidal systems — Methods for zeta-potential determination — Part 2: Optical methods
ISO/AWI 14488	Particulate materials — Sampling and sample splitting for the determination of particulate properties
ISO/AWI TS 17603	Electrical sensing zone measurements – Recommended good practice
ISO/FDIS 19430	Determination of particle size distribution and number concentration by particle tracking analysis (PTA)
ISO/AWI TR 19672	Particle characterization — Algorithms for reference image generation for image analysis
ISO/CD TS 19673	Particle characterization — Colour image analysis methods
ISO/CD 19676	Single particle light interaction methods — Bio-fluorescence airborne particle counter for clean spaces
ISO/AWI TS 19684	Measurement of heterogeneity in liquid dispersions
ISO/WD TS 19997	Guidelines for good practices in zeta-potential measurement
ISO/DIS 21501-1	Determination of particle size distribution — Single particle light interaction methods — Part 1: Light scattering aerosol spectrometer
ISO/PWI 22064	Determination of core radius and shell thickness of spherical core-shell particles by small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS)
ISO/FDIS 22412	Particle size analysis — Dynamic light scattering (DLS)

Table 34. Standards from IEC/TC 85.

Reference	Title
IEC 60051-1:2016	Direct acting indicating analogue electrical measuring instruments and their accessories - Part 1: Definitions and general requirements common to all parts
IEC 60051-2:2018	Direct acting indicating analogue electrical measuring instruments and their accessories - Part 2: Special requirements for ammeters and voltmeters
IEC 60051-3:2018	Direct acting indicating analogue electrical measuring instruments and their accessories - Part 3: Special requirements for wattmeters and varmeters

IEC 60051-4:2018	Direct acting indicating analogue electrical measuring instruments and their accessories title - Part 4: Special requirements for frequency meters
IEC 60051-5:2017	Direct acting indicating analogue electrical measuring instruments and their accessories - Part 5: Special requirements for phase meters, power factor meters and synchrosopes
IEC 60051-6:2017	Direct acting indicating analogue electrical measuring instruments and their accessories - Part 6: Special requirements for ohmmeters (impedance meters) and conductance meters
IEC 60051-7:2017	Direct acting indicating analogue electrical measuring instruments and their accessories - Part 7: Special requirements for multi-function instruments
IEC 60051-8:2017	Direct acting indicating analogue electrical measuring instruments and their accessories - Part 8: Special requirements for accessories
IEC 60051-9:2019	Direct acting indicating analogue electrical measuring instruments and their accessories - Part 9: Recommended test methods
IEC 60258:1968	Direct acting recording electrical measuring instruments and their accessories
IEC 60258:1968/AMD1:1976	Amendment 1 - Direct acting recording electrical measuring instruments and their accessories
IEC 60359:2001	Electrical and electronic measurement equipment - Expression of performance
IEC 60428:1973	Standard cells
IEC 60469:2013	Transitions, pulses and related waveforms - Terms, definitions and algorithms
IEC 60477-1:2022	Laboratory resistors - Part 1: Laboratory DC resistors
IEC 60477-2:2022	Laboratory resistors - Part 2: Laboratory AC resistors
IEC 60523:1975	Direct-current potentiometers
IEC 60523:1975/AMD1:1979	Amendment 1 - Direct-current potentiometers
IEC 60523:1975/AMD1:1979/CO R1:1980	Corrigendum 1 to Amendment 1 - Direct-current potentiometers
IEC 60523:1975/AMD2:1997	Amendment 2 - Direct-current potentiometers
IEC 60524:1975	Direct-current resistive volt ratio boxes
IEC 60524:1975/AMD1:1981	Amendment 1 - Direct-current resistive volt ratio boxes
IEC 60524:1975/AMD2:1997	Amendment 2 - Direct-current resistive volt ratio boxes
IEC 60564:1977	D.C. bridges for measuring resistance
IEC 60564:1977/AMD1:1981	Amendment 1 - D.C. bridges for measuring resistance
IEC 60564:1977/AMD2:1997	Amendment 2 - D.C. bridges for measuring resistance
IEC 60615:1978	Terminology for microwave apparatus
IEC 60618:1978	Inductive voltage dividers
IEC 60618:1978/AMD1:1981	Amendment 1 - Inductive voltage dividers
IEC 60618:1978/AMD2:1997	Amendment 2 - Inductive voltage dividers
IEC 60624:1978	Expression of the performance of pulse generators
IEC 60688:2024	Electrical measuring transducers for converting AC and DC electrical quantities to analogue or digital signals
IEC 61028:1990	Electrical measuring instruments - X-Y recorders
IEC 61028:1990/AMD1:1995	Amendment 1 - Electrical measuring instruments - X-Y recorders
IEC 61028:1990/AMD2:1997	Amendment 2 - Electrical measuring instruments - X-Y recorders
IEC 61143-1:1992	Electrical measuring instruments - X-t recorders - Part 1: Definitions and requirements
IEC 61143-1:1992/AMD1:1997	Amendment 1 - Electrical measuring instruments - X-t recorders - Part 1: Definitions and requirements
IEC 61143-2:1992	Electrical measuring instruments - X-t recorders - Part 2: Recommended additional test methods
IEC 61187:1993	Electrical and electronic measuring equipment - Documentation
IEC 61554:2025	Panel mounted equipment - Electrical measuring instruments - Dimensions for panel mounting
IEC 61557-1:2019	Electrical safety in low voltage distribution systems up to 1 000 V AC and 1 500 V DC - Equipment for testing, measuring or monitoring of protective measures - Part 1: General requirements
IEC 61557-1:2019/AMD1:2024	Amendment 1 - Electrical safety in low voltage distribution systems up to 1 000 V AC and 1 500 V DC - Equipment for testing, measuring or monitoring of protective measures - Part 1: General requirements
IEC 61557-2:2019	Electrical safety in low voltage distribution systems up to 1 000 V AC and 1 500 V DC - Equipment for testing, measuring or monitoring of protective measures - Part 2: Insulation resistance
IEC 61557-3:2019	Electrical safety in low voltage distribution systems up to 1 000 V AC and 1 500 V DC - Equipment for testing, measuring or monitoring of protective measures - Part 3: Loop impedance
IEC 61557-4:2019	Electrical safety in low voltage distribution systems up to 1 000 V AC and 1 500 V DC - Equipment for testing, measuring or monitoring of protective measures - Part 4: Resistance of earth connection and equipotential bonding
IEC 61557-5:2019	Electrical safety in low voltage distribution systems up to 1 000 V AC and 1 500 V DC - Equipment for testing, measuring or monitoring of protective measures - Part 5: Resistance to earth

IEC 61557-6:2019	Electrical safety in low voltage distribution systems up to 1 000 V AC and 1 500 V DC - Equipment for testing, measuring or monitoring of protective measures - Part 6: Effectiveness of residual current devices (RCD) in TT, TN and IT systems
IEC 61557-7:2019	Electrical safety in low voltage distribution systems up to 1 000 V AC and 1 500 V DC - Equipment for testing, measuring or monitoring of protective measures - Part 7: Phase sequence
IEC 61557-7:2019/AMD1:2023	Amendment 1 - Electrical safety in low voltage distribution systems up to 1 000 V AC and 1 500 V DC - Equipment for testing, measuring or monitoring of protective measures - Part 7: Phase sequence
IEC 61557-8:2014	Electrical safety in low voltage distribution systems up to 1 000 V a.c. and 1 500 V d.c. - Equipment for testing, measuring or monitoring of protective measures - Part 8: Insulation monitoring devices for IT systems
IEC 61557-8:2014/COR1:2016	Corrigendum 1 - Electrical safety in low voltage distribution systems up to 1 000 V a.c. and 1 500 V d.c. - Equipment for testing, measuring or monitoring of protective measures - Part 8: Insulation monitoring devices for IT systems
IEC 61557-9:2023	Electrical safety in low voltage distribution systems up to 1 000 V AC and 1 500 V DC - Equipment for testing, measuring or monitoring of protective measures - Part 9: Equipment for insulation fault location in IT systems
IEC 61557-10:2024	Electrical safety in low voltage distribution systems up to 1 000 V AC and 1 500 V DC - Equipment for testing, measuring or monitoring of protective measures - Part 10: Combined measuring equipment for testing, measuring and monitoring of protective measures
IEC 61557-11:2020	Electrical safety in low voltage distribution systems up to 1 000 V AC and 1 500 V DC - Equipment for testing, measuring or monitoring of protective measures - Part 11: Effectiveness of residual current monitors (RCM) in TT, TN and IT systems
IEC 61557-12:2018	Electrical safety in low voltage distribution systems up to 1 000 V AC and 1 500 V DC - Equipment for testing, measuring or monitoring of protective measures - Part 12: Power metering and monitoring devices (PMD)
IEC 61557-12:2018/COR1:2022	Corrigendum 1 - Electrical safety in low voltage distribution systems up to 1 000 V AC and 1 500 V DC - Equipment for testing, measuring or monitoring of protective measures - Part 12: Power metering and monitoring devices (PMD)
IEC 61557-12:2018/AMD1:2021	Amendment 1 - Electrical safety in low voltage distribution systems up to 1 000 V AC and 1 500 V DC - Equipment for testing, measuring or monitoring of protective measures - Part 12: Power metering and monitoring devices (PMD)
IEC 61557-12:2018/AMD1:2021/COR1:2022	Corrigendum 1 - Electrical safety in low voltage distribution systems up to 1 000 V AC and 1 500 V DC - Equipment for testing, measuring or monitoring of protective measures - Part 12: Power metering and monitoring devices (PMD)
IEC 61557-13:2023	Electrical safety in low voltage distribution systems up to 1 000 V AC and 1 500 V DC - Equipment for testing, measuring or monitoring of protective measures - Part 13: Hand-held and hand-manipulated current clamps and sensors for measurement of leakage currents in electrical distribution systems
IEC 61557-14:2023	Electrical safety in low voltage distribution systems up to 1 000 V AC and 1 500 V DC - Equipment for testing, measuring or monitoring of protective measures - Part 14: Equipment for testing the safety of electrical equipment of machinery
IEC 61557-15:2014	Electrical safety in low voltage distribution systems up to 1 000 V a.c. and 1 500 V d.c. - Equipment for testing, measuring or monitoring of protective measures - Part 15: Functional safety requirements for insulation monitoring devices in IT systems and equipment for insulation fault location in IT systems
IEC 61557-16:2023	Electrical safety in low voltage distribution systems up to 1 000 V AC and 1 500 V DC - Equipment for testing, measuring or monitoring of protective measures - Part 16: Equipment for testing the effectiveness of the protective measures of electrical equipment and/or medical electrical equipment
IEC 61557-17:2021	Electrical safety in low voltage distribution systems up to 1 000 V AC and 1 500 V DC - Equipment for testing, measuring or monitoring of protective measures - Part 17: Non-contact AC voltage indicators
IEC 62008:2005	Performance characteristics and calibration methods for digital data acquisition systems and relevant software
IEC 62586-1:2017	Power quality measurement in power supply systems - Part 1: Power quality instruments (PQI)
IEC 62586-2:2017	Power quality measurement in power supply systems - Part 2: Functional tests and uncertainty requirements
IEC 62586-2:2017/COR1:2018	Corrigendum 1 - Power quality measurement in power supply systems - Part 2: Functional tests and uncertainty requirements
IEC 62586-2:2017/AMD1:2021	Amendment 1 - Power quality measurement in power supply systems - Part 2: Functional tests and uncertainty requirements

IEC 62754:2017	Computation of waveform parameter uncertainties
IEC 62792:2015	Measurement method for the output of electroshock weapons
IEC 62974-1:2024	Monitoring and measuring systems used for data collection, aggregation and analysis - Part 1: Device requirements
IEC TS 63191:2023	Demand-side power quality management
IEC TR 63213:2019	Power measurement applications within electrical distribution networks and electrical installations
IEC TS 63297:2021	Sensing devices for non-intrusive load monitoring (NILM) systems
IEC TS 63383:2022	Cybersecurity aspects of devices used for power metering and monitoring, power quality monitoring, data collection and analysis
IEC TR 63519:2024	Aspects and understanding of measurement uncertainty - Background information on measurement uncertainty based on the example of IEC TC 85 (Measuring equipment for electrical and electromagnetic quantities)

Table 35. IEC/TC 85 Projects under development.

Project Reference	Title
PNW TS 85-954 ED1	Statistical method for verification of measurement performance
IEC 61557-12 ED3	Electrical safety in low voltage distribution systems up to 1 000 V AC and 1 500 V DC - Equipment for testing, measuring or monitoring of protective measures - Part 12: Power metering and monitoring devices (PMD)
IEC 61557-12-2 ED1	Electrical safety in low voltage distribution systems up to 1 000 V AC and 1 500 V DC – Equipment for testing, measuring or monitoring of protective measures – Part 12-2: Functional test procedure for PMD and EPMF
IEC 61557-18 ED1	Electrical safety in low voltage distribution systems up to 1 000 V AC and 1 500 V DC – equipment for testing, measuring or monitoring of protective measures – part 18: DC EV supply equipment monitoring device
IEC 61557-19 ED1	Electrical safety in low voltage distribution systems up to 1.000 V AC and 1.500 V DC - Equipment for testing, monitoring or measuring the protective measures in energy distribution system - part 19: Monitoring device for earthing impedance in IT-systems
IEC 62586-1 ED3	Power quality measurement in power supply systems - Part 1: Power quality instruments (PQI)
IEC 62586-2 ED3	Power quality measurement in power supply systems - Part 2: Functional tests and uncertainty requirements
IEC TS 62586-3 ED1	Power quality measurement in power supply systems - Part 3: Maintenance tests, calibration
IEC 62792 ED2	Measurement method for the output of electroshock weapons
IEC 63297 ED1	Sensing devices for non-intrusive load monitoring (NILM) systems
IEC 63580 ED1	Measuring equipment for electrical and electromagnetic quantities - Environmental aspects

Table 36. Standards from ISO/TC 164.

Reference	Title
ISO/TTA 5:2007	Code of practice for creep/fatigue testing of cracked components
ISO 148-1:2016	Metallic materials — Charpy pendulum impact test — Part 1: Test method
ISO 148-2:2016	Metallic materials — Charpy pendulum impact test — Part 2: Verification of testing machines
ISO 148-3:2016	Metallic materials — Charpy pendulum impact test — Part 3: Preparation and characterization of Charpy V-notch test pieces for indirect verification of pendulum impact machines
ISO 204:2023	Metallic materials — Uniaxial creep testing in tension — Method of test
ISO 376:2011	Metallic materials — Calibration of force-proving instruments used for the verification of uniaxial testing machines
ISO 1099:2017	Metallic materials — Fatigue testing — Axial force-controlled method
ISO 1143:2021	Metallic materials — Rotating bar bending fatigue testing
ISO 1352:2021	Metallic materials — Torque-controlled fatigue testing
ISO 3785:2023	Metallic materials — Designation of test specimen axes in relation to product texture
ISO 4545-1:2023	Metallic materials — Knoop hardness test — Part 1: Test method
ISO 4545-2:2017	Metallic materials — Knoop hardness test — Part 2: Verification and calibration of testing machines
ISO 4545-3:2017	Metallic materials — Knoop hardness test — Part 3: Calibration of reference blocks
ISO 4545-4:2017	Metallic materials — Knoop hardness test — Part 4: Table of hardness values

ISO 4965-1:2012	Metallic materials — Dynamic force calibration for uniaxial fatigue testing — Part 1: Testing systems
ISO 4965-2:2012	Metallic materials — Dynamic force calibration for uniaxial fatigue testing — Part 2: Dynamic calibration device (DCD) instrumentation
ISO 6506-1:2014	Metallic materials — Brinell hardness test — Part 1: Test method
ISO 6506-2:2017	Metallic materials — Brinell hardness test — Part 2: Verification and calibration of testing machines
ISO 6506-3:2014	Metallic materials — Brinell hardness test — Part 3: Calibration of reference blocks
ISO 6506-4:2014	Metallic materials — Brinell hardness test — Part 4: Table of hardness values
ISO 6507-1:2023	Metallic materials — Vickers hardness test — Part 1: Test method
ISO 6507-2:2018	Metallic materials — Vickers hardness test — Part 2: Verification and calibration of testing machines
ISO 6507-3:2018	Metallic materials — Vickers hardness test — Part 3: Calibration of reference blocks
ISO 6507-4:2018	Metallic materials — Vickers hardness test — Part 4: Tables of hardness values
ISO 6508-1:2023	Metallic materials — Rockwell hardness test — Part 1: Test method
ISO 6508-2:2023	Metallic materials — Rockwell hardness test — Part 2: Verification and calibration of testing machines and indenters
ISO 6508-3:2023	Metallic materials — Rockwell hardness test — Part 3: Calibration of reference blocks
ISO 6892-1:2019	Metallic materials — Tensile testing — Part 1: Method of test at room temperature
ISO 6892-2:2018	Metallic materials — Tensile testing — Part 2: Method of test at elevated temperature
ISO 6892-3:2015	Metallic materials — Tensile testing — Part 3: Method of test at low temperature
ISO 6892-4:2015	Metallic materials — Tensile testing — Part 4: Method of test in liquid helium
ISO/TS 6892-5:2025	Metallic materials — Tensile testing — Part 5: Specification for testing miniaturised test pieces
ISO 7039:2024	Metallic materials — Tensile testing — Method for evaluating the susceptibility of materials to the effects of high-pressure gas within hollow test pieces
ISO 7438:2020	Metallic materials — Bend test
ISO 7500-1:2018	Metallic materials — Calibration and verification of static uniaxial testing machines — Part 1: Tension/compression testing machines — Calibration and verification of the force-measuring system
ISO 7500-2:2006	Metallic materials — Verification of static uniaxial testing machines — Part 2: Tension creep testing machines — Verification of the applied force
ISO 7799:1985	Metallic materials — Sheet and strip 3 mm thick or less — Reverse bend test
ISO 7800:2012	Metallic materials — Wire — Simple torsion test
ISO 7801:2024	Metallic materials — Wire — Reverse bend test
ISO 7802:2013	Metallic materials — Wire — Wrapping test
ISO 8491:1998	Metallic materials — Tube (in full section) — Bend test
ISO 8492:2013	Metallic materials — Tube — Flattening test
ISO 8493:1998	Metallic materials — Tube — Drift-expanding test
ISO 8494:2013	Metallic materials — Tube — Flanging test
ISO 8495:2013	Metallic materials — Tube — Ring-expanding test
ISO 8496:2013	Metallic materials — Tube — Ring tensile test
ISO 9513:2012	Metallic materials — Calibration of extensometer systems used in uniaxial testing
ISO 9513:2012/Cor 1:2013	Metallic materials — Calibration of extensometer systems used in uniaxial testing — Technical Corrigendum 1
ISO 9649:2023	Metallic materials — Wire — Reverse torsion test
ISO 10113:2020	Metallic materials — Sheet and strip — Determination of plastic strain ratio
ISO 10275:2020	Metallic materials — Sheet and strip — Determination of tensile strain hardening exponent
ISO 11531:2022	Metallic materials — Sheet and strip — Earing test
ISO 12004-1:2020	Metallic materials — Determination of forming-limit curves for sheet and strip — Part 1: Measurement and application of forming-limit diagrams in the press shop
ISO 12004-2:2021	Metallic materials — Determination of forming-limit curves for sheet and strip — Part 2: Determination of forming-limit curves in the laboratory
ISO 12106:2017	Metallic materials — Fatigue testing — Axial-strain-controlled method
ISO 12107:2012	Metallic materials — Fatigue testing — Statistical planning and analysis of data
ISO 12108:2018	Metallic materials — Fatigue testing — Fatigue crack growth method
ISO 12110-1:2013	Metallic materials — Fatigue testing — Variable amplitude fatigue testing — Part 1: General principles, test method and reporting requirements
ISO 12110-2:2013	Metallic materials — Fatigue testing — Variable amplitude fatigue testing — Part 2: Cycle counting and related data reduction methods
ISO 12111:2011	Metallic materials — Fatigue testing — Strain-controlled thermomechanical fatigue testing method

ISO/TR 12112:2018	Metallic materials — Principles and designs for multiaxial fatigue testing
ISO 12135:2021	Metallic materials — Unified method of test for the determination of quasistatic fracture toughness
ISO 13314:2011	Mechanical testing of metals — Ductility testing — Compression test for porous and cellular metals
ISO 14556:2023	Metallic materials — Charpy V-notch pendulum impact test — Instrumented test method
ISO 14577-1:2015	Metallic materials — Instrumented indentation test for hardness and materials parameters — Part 1: Test method
ISO 14577-2:2015	Metallic materials — Instrumented indentation test for hardness and materials parameters — Part 2: Verification and calibration of testing machines
ISO 14577-3:2015	Metallic materials — Instrumented indentation test for hardness and materials parameters — Part 3: Calibration of reference blocks
ISO 14577-4:2016	Metallic materials — Instrumented indentation test for hardness and materials parameters — Part 4: Test method for metallic and non-metallic coatings
ISO 14577-5:2022	Metallic materials — Instrumented indentation test for hardness and materials parameters — Part 5: Linear elastic dynamic instrumented indentation testing (DIIT)
ISO/TR 15263:2024	Measurement uncertainties in mechanical tests on metallic materials — The evaluation of uncertainties in tensile testing
ISO 15363:2017	Metallic materials — Tube ring hydraulic pressure test
ISO 15653:2018	Metallic materials — Method of test for the determination of quasistatic fracture toughness of welds
ISO 16630:2017	Metallic materials — Sheet and strip — Hole expanding test
ISO 16808:2022	Metallic materials — Sheet and strip — Determination of biaxial stress-strain curve by means of bulge test with optical measuring systems
ISO 16842:2021	Metallic materials — Sheet and strip — Biaxial tensile testing method using a cruciform test piece
ISO 16859-1:2015	Metallic materials — Leeb hardness test — Part 1: Test method
ISO 16859-2:2015	Metallic materials — Leeb hardness test — Part 2: Verification and calibration of the testing devices
ISO 16859-3:2015	Metallic materials — Leeb hardness test — Part 3: Calibration of reference test blocks
ISO 17340:2020	Metallic materials — Ductility testing — High speed compression test for porous and cellular metals
ISO 18265:2013	Metallic materials — Conversion of hardness values
ISO 18338:2021	Metallic materials — Torsion test at room temperature
ISO/TS 19096:2023	Metallic materials — Instrumented indentation test for hardness and materials parameters — Evaluation of stress change using indentation force differences
ISO 20032:2013	Method for evaluation of tensile properties of metallic superplastic materials
ISO 20064:2019	Metallic materials — Steel — Method of test for the determination of brittle crack arrest toughness, Kca
ISO 20482:2013	Metallic materials — Sheet and strip — Erichsen cupping test
ISO/TS 21913:2022	Temperature verification method applied to dynamic fatigue testing
ISO 22407:2021	Metallic materials — Fatigue testing — Axial plane bending method
ISO 22889:2013	Metallic materials — Method of test for the determination of resistance to stable crack extension using specimens of low constraint
ISO 23296:2022	Metallic materials — Fatigue testing — Force controlled thermo-mechanical fatigue testing method
ISO 23718:2007	Metallic materials — Mechanical testing — Vocabulary
ISO 23788:2012	Metallic materials — Verification of the alignment of fatigue testing machines
ISO 23838:2022	Metallic materials — High strain rate torsion test at room temperature
ISO 24213:2017	Metallic materials — Sheet and strip — Method for springback evaluation in stretch bending
ISO 26203-1:2018	Metallic materials — Tensile testing at high strain rates — Part 1: Elastic-bar-type systems
ISO 26203-2:2011	Metallic materials — Tensile testing at high strain rates — Part 2: Servo-hydraulic and other test systems
ISO 26843:2015	Metallic materials — Measurement of fracture toughness at impact loading rates using precracked Charpy-type test pieces
ISO 27306:2016	Metallic materials — Method of constraint loss correction of CTOD fracture toughness for fracture assessment of steel components
ISO/TR 29381:2008	Metallic materials — Measurement of mechanical properties by an instrumented indentation test — Indentation tensile properties

Table 37. ISO/TC 164 Projects under development.

Project Reference	Title
ISO/CD 148-1	Metallic materials — Charpy pendulum impact test — Part 1: Test method
ISO/CD 148-2	Metallic materials — Charpy pendulum impact test — Part 2: Verification of testing machines
ISO/CD 148-3	Metallic materials — Charpy pendulum impact test — Part 3: Preparation and characterization of Charpy V-notch test pieces for indirect verification of pendulum impact machines
ISO/DIS 148-4	Metallic materials — Charpy pendulum impact test — Part 4: Part 4: Testing of miniature Charpy - type V-notch test pieces
ISO/PWI 376	Metallic materials — Calibration of force-proving instruments used for the verification of uniaxial testing machines
ISO/CD 1099.2	Metallic materials — Fatigue testing — Axial force-controlled method
ISO/PWI 4545-1	Metallic materials — Knoop hardness test — Part 1: Test method
ISO/PWI 4545-2	Metallic materials — Knoop hardness test — Part 2: Verification and calibration of testing machines
ISO/PWI 4545-3	Metallic materials — Knoop hardness test — Part 3: Calibration of reference blocks
ISO/WD TS 4596	Metallic materials — High temperature creep/fatigue crack growth testing method
ISO/DIS 6506-1	Metallic materials — Brinell hardness test — Part 1: Test method
ISO/DIS 6506-2	Metallic materials — Brinell hardness test — Part 2: Verification and calibration of testing machines
ISO/DIS 6506-3	Metallic materials — Brinell hardness test — Part 3: Calibration of reference blocks
ISO/PWI 6507-1	Metallic materials — Vickers hardness test — Part 1: Test method
ISO/PWI 6507-2	Metallic materials — Vickers hardness test — Part 2: Verification and calibration of testing machines
ISO/PWI 6507-3	Metallic materials — Vickers hardness test — Part 3: Calibration of reference blocks
ISO/DIS 6892-2	Metallic materials — Tensile testing — Part 2: Method of test at elevated temperature
ISO/AWI 6892-6	Metallic materials — Tensile testing — Part 6: Tensile test on foils and strips of metals with a nominal thickness less than 0,200 mm by using computer-controlled testing machines
ISO/PWI 7500-1	Metallic materials — Calibration and verification of static uniaxial testing machines — Part 1: Tension/compression testing machines — Calibration and verification of the force-measuring system
ISO/CD 7799	Metallic materials — Sheet and strip 3 mm thick or less — Reverse bend test
ISO/CD TR 8463	Metallic materials — Strategy for a common framework to determine measurement uncertainty in mechanical testing
ISO/CD TR 12105	Metallic materials — Fatigue testing — General principles
ISO/CD 12106	Metallic materials — Fatigue testing — Axial-strain-controlled method
ISO/AWI 12107	Metallic materials — Fatigue testing — Statistical planning and analysis of data
ISO/CD 12108	Metallic materials — Fatigue testing — Fatigue crack growth method
ISO/CD 12111	Metallic materials — Fatigue testing — Strain-controlled thermomechanical fatigue testing method
ISO/DIS 14577-1	Metallic materials — Instrumented indentation test for hardness and materials parameters — Part 1: Test method
ISO/DIS 14577-2	Metallic materials — Instrumented indentation test for hardness and materials parameters — Part 2: Verification and calibration of testing machines
ISO/DIS 14577-3	Metallic materials — Instrumented indentation test for hardness and materials parameters — Part 3: Calibration of reference blocks
ISO/DIS 14577-6	Metallic materials — Instrumented indentation test for hardness and materials parameters — Part 6: Instrumented indentation test at elevated temperature
ISO/CD TR 15262	Mechanical tests on metallic materials — Uncertainty in low-cycle fatigue
ISO/AWI TR 15264	Mechanical tests on metallic materials - Evaluation of uncertainties in creep testing
ISO/CD 15653	Metallic materials — Method of test for the determination of quasistatic fracture toughness of welds
ISO/DIS 16630	Metallic materials — Sheet and strip — Hole expanding test
ISO/DIS 20198	Metallic materials — Steel — Method of test for the determination of brittle crack arrest temperature (CAT)
ISO/CD 20482	Metallic materials — Sheet and strip — Erichsen cupping test
ISO/DIS 23296	Metallic materials — Fatigue testing — Force controlled thermo-mechanical fatigue testing method
ISO/CD TS 23718	Metallic materials — Mechanical testing — Vocabulary
ISO/NP 24270.2	Metallic materials — Sheet and strip — Secondary work embrittlement test method
ISO/PWI TS 25444	Metallic Materials - Instrumented indentation test for hardness and materials parameters - Instrumented indentation test at elevated temperature for systems with passive tip heating and without tip temperature sensor

ISO/AWI 25586	Metallic materials — Sheet and strip — Biaxial bulge test method for sheet metals
ISO/DIS 26203-1	Metallic materials — Tensile testing at high strain rates — Part 1: Elastic-bar-type systems
ISO/AWI 26203-3	Metallic materials — Tensile testing at high strain rates — Part 3: Test method at elevated temperature
ISO/CD 26843	Metallic materials — Measurement of fracture toughness at impact loading rates using precracked Charpy-type test pieces

Table 38. Standards from ISO/TC 156.

Reference	Title
ISO 3079:2022	Two-electrode method using acetic acid to measure pitting potential of aluminium and aluminium alloys in chloride solutions
ISO 3651-1:1998	Determination of resistance to intergranular corrosion of stainless steels — Part 1: Austenitic and ferritic-austenitic (duplex) stainless steels — Corrosion test in nitric acid medium by measurement of loss in mass (Huey test)
ISO 3651-2:1998	Determination of resistance to intergranular corrosion of stainless steels — Part 2: Ferritic, austenitic and ferritic-austenitic (duplex) stainless steels — Corrosion test in media containing sulfuric acid
ISO 3651-3:2017	Determination of resistance to intergranular corrosion of stainless steels — Part 3: Corrosion test for low-Cr ferritic stainless steels
ISO 4212:2023	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Method of oxalic acid etching test for intergranular corrosion of austenitic stainless steel
ISO 4215:2022	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Test method for high-temperature corrosion testing of metallic materials by thermogravimetry under isothermal or cyclic conditions
ISO 4631:2023	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Measurement of the electrochemical critical localized corrosion potential (E-CLCP) for Ti alloys fabricated via additive manufacturing method in simulated biomedical solutions
ISO 4680:2022	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Uniaxial constant-load test method for evaluating susceptibility of metals and alloys to stress corrosion cracking in high-purity water at high temperatures
ISO 4905:2023	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Electrochemical test methods for high-temperature corrosion testing of metallic materials in molten salts
ISO 5156:2022	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Corrosion test method for disinfectant — Total immersion method
ISO 5668:2023	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Guidelines and requirements for corrosion testing in simulated environment of deep-sea water
ISO 6509-1:2014	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Determination of dezincification resistance of copper alloys with zinc — Part 1: Test method
ISO 6509-2:2017	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Determination of dezincification resistance of copper alloys with zinc — Part 2: Assessment criteria
ISO 7054:2024	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Wiping method for measurements of gases and particles on real structures and equipment
ISO 7384:1986	Corrosion tests in artificial atmosphere — General requirements
ISO 7441:2015	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Determination of bimetallic corrosion in atmospheric exposure corrosion tests
ISO 7539-1:2012	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Stress corrosion testing — Part 1: General guidance on testing procedures
ISO 7539-2:1989	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Stress corrosion testing — Part 2: Preparation and use of bent-beam specimens
ISO 7539-3:1989	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Stress corrosion testing — Part 3: Preparation and use of U-bend specimens
ISO 7539-4:1989	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Stress corrosion testing — Part 4: Preparation and use of uniaxially loaded tension specimens
ISO 7539-5:1989	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Stress corrosion testing — Part 5: Preparation and use of C-ring specimens
ISO 7539-6:2018/Amd 1:2024	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Stress corrosion testing — Part 6: Preparation and use of precracked specimens for tests under constant load or constant displacement — Amendment 1
ISO 7539-6:2018	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Stress corrosion testing — Part 6: Preparation and use of precracked specimens for tests under constant load or constant displacement
ISO 7539-7:2005	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Stress corrosion testing — Part 7: Method for slow strain rate testing

ISO 7539-8:2000	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Stress corrosion testing — Part 8: Preparation and use of specimens to evaluate weldments
ISO 7539-9:2021	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Stress corrosion testing — Part 9: Preparation and use of pre-cracked specimens for tests under rising load or rising displacement
ISO 7539-10:2020	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Stress corrosion testing — Part 10: Reverse U-bend method
ISO 7539-11:2013	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Stress corrosion testing — Part 11: Guidelines for testing the resistance of metals and alloys to hydrogen embrittlement and hydrogen-assisted cracking
ISO 7539-12:2023	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Stress corrosion testing — Part 12: Requirements for atmospheric stress corrosion cracking testing
ISO/TR 7655:2022	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Overview of metal corrosion protection when using disinfectants
ISO 8044:2024	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Vocabulary
ISO 8407:2021/Amd 1:2025	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Removal of corrosion products from corrosion test specimens — Amendment 1
ISO 8407:2021	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Removal of corrosion products from corrosion test specimens
ISO/TR 8547:2024	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Exposure test results in the Asian Monsoon region
ISO 8565:2011	Metals and alloys — Atmospheric corrosion testing — General requirements
ISO 9223:2012	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Corrosivity of atmospheres — Classification, determination and estimation
ISO 9224:2012	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Corrosivity of atmospheres — Guiding values for the corrosivity categories
ISO 9225:2012	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Corrosivity of atmospheres — Measurement of environmental parameters affecting corrosivity of atmospheres
ISO 9226:2012	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Corrosivity of atmospheres — Determination of corrosion rate of standard specimens for the evaluation of corrosivity
ISO 9227:2022/Amd 1:2024	Corrosion tests in artificial atmospheres — Salt spray tests — Amendment 1: Footnote of Warning
ISO 9227:2022	Corrosion tests in artificial atmospheres — Salt spray tests
ISO 9351:2025	Galvanic anodes for cathodic protection in seawater and saline sediments
ISO 9400:1990	Nickel-based alloys — Determination of resistance to intergranular corrosion
ISO 9591:2004	Corrosion of aluminium alloys — Determination of resistance to stress corrosion cracking
ISO 9812:2024	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Corrosion test method for disinfectant — Spray test method
ISO 9813:2023	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Performance test method for corrosion inhibitors used in chemical cleaning of industry equipment
ISO 10062:2022	Corrosion tests in artificial atmosphere at very low concentrations of polluting gas(es)
ISO 10062:2022/Amd 1:2024	Corrosion tests in artificial atmosphere at very low concentrations of polluting gas(es) — Amendment 1: Footnote of Warning
ISO 10270:2022	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Aqueous corrosion testing of zirconium alloys for use in nuclear power reactors
ISO 11130:2017	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Alternate immersion test in salt solution
ISO 11303:2002	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Guidelines for selection of protection methods against atmospheric corrosion
ISO 11306:1998	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Guidelines for exposing and evaluating metals and alloys in surface sea water
ISO 11463:2020	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Guidelines for the evaluation of pitting corrosion
ISO 11474:1998	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Corrosion tests in artificial atmosphere — Accelerated outdoor test by intermittent spraying of a salt solution (Scab test)
ISO 11782-1:1998	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Corrosion fatigue testing — Part 1: Cycles to failure testing
ISO 11782-2:1998/Amd 1:2024	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Corrosion fatigue testing — Part 2: Crack propagation testing using precracked specimens — Amendment 1
ISO 11782-2:1998	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Corrosion fatigue testing — Part 2: Crack propagation testing using precracked specimens
ISO 11844-1:2020	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Classification of low corrosivity of indoor atmospheres — Part 1: Determination and estimation of indoor corrosivity
ISO 11844-2:2020	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Classification of low corrosivity of indoor atmospheres — Part 2: Determination of corrosion attack in indoor atmospheres
ISO 11844-3:2020	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Classification of low corrosivity of indoor atmospheres — Part 3: Measurement of environmental parameters affecting indoor corrosivity
ISO 11845:2020	Corrosion of metals and alloys — General principles for corrosion testing
ISO 11846:1995	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Determination of resistance to intergranular corrosion of solution heat-treatable aluminium alloys

ISO 11881:1999	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Exfoliation corrosion testing of aluminium alloys
ISO 11881:1999/Cor 1:1999	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Exfoliation corrosion testing of aluminium alloys — Technical Corrigendum 1
ISO 12473:2017	General principles of cathodic protection in seawater
ISO 12696:2022	Cathodic protection of steel in concrete
ISO 12732:2006	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Electrochemical potentiokinetic reactivation measurement using the double loop method (based on Cihal's method)
ISO 13174:2012	Cathodic protection of harbour installations
ISO 13573:2012	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Test method for thermal-cycling exposure testing under high-temperature corrosion conditions for metallic materials
ISO 14802:2012	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Guidelines for applying statistics to analysis of corrosion data
ISO 14993:2018	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Accelerated testing involving cyclic exposure to salt mist, dry and wet conditions
ISO 15158:2014	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Method of measuring the pitting potential for stainless steels by potentiodynamic control in sodium chloride solution
ISO 15257:2017	Cathodic protection — Competence levels of cathodic protection persons — Basis for a certification scheme
ISO 15324:2000	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Evaluation of stress corrosion cracking by the drop evaporation test
ISO 15329:2006	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Anodic test for evaluation of intergranular corrosion susceptibility of heat-treatable aluminium alloys
ISO 16151:2018	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Accelerated cyclic test with exposure to acidified salt spray, dry and wet conditions
ISO/TR 16203:2023	Overview of methods available for particle-free erosion corrosion testing in flowing liquids
ISO/TR 16208:2014	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Test method for corrosion of materials by electrochemical impedance measurements
ISO/TR 16335:2013	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Corrosion tests in artificial atmospheres — Guidelines for selection of accelerated corrosion test for product qualification
ISO 16539:2013	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Accelerated cyclic corrosion tests with exposure to synthetic ocean water salt-deposition process — "Dry" and "wet" conditions at constant absolute humidity
ISO 16540:2015	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Methodology for determining the resistance of metals to stress corrosion cracking using the four-point bend method
ISO 16701:2015	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Corrosion in artificial atmosphere — Accelerated corrosion test involving exposure under controlled conditions of humidity cycling and intermittent spraying of a salt solution
ISO 16784-1:2024	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Corrosion and fouling in industrial cooling water systems — Part 1: Guidelines and requirements for conducting pilot-scale evaluation of corrosion and fouling control additives for open recirculating cooling water systems
ISO 16784-2:2024	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Corrosion and fouling in industrial cooling water systems — Part 2: Evaluation of the performance of cooling water treatment programmes using a pilot-scale test rig
ISO 17081:2014	Method of measurement of hydrogen permeation and determination of hydrogen uptake and transport in metals by an electrochemical technique
ISO 17093:2015	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Guidelines for corrosion test by electrochemical noise measurements
ISO 17224:2015	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Test method for high temperature corrosion testing of metallic materials by application of a deposit of salt, ash, or other substances
ISO 17245:2015	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Test method for high temperature corrosion testing of metallic materials by immersing in molten salt or other liquids under static conditions
ISO 17248:2015	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Test method for high temperature corrosion testing of metallic materials by embedding in salt, ash, or other solids
ISO 17474:2012	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Conventions applicable to electrochemical measurements in corrosion testing
ISO 17475:2005	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Electrochemical test methods — Guidelines for conducting potentiostatic and potentiodynamic polarization measurements
ISO 17475:2005/Cor 1:2006	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Electrochemical test methods — Guidelines for conducting potentiostatic and potentiodynamic polarization measurements — Technical Corrigendum 1
ISO 17752:2012	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Procedures to determine and estimate runoff rates of metals from materials as a result of atmospheric corrosion
ISO 17864:2005	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Determination of the critical pitting temperature under potentiostatic control

ISO 17918:2015	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Evaluation of selective corrosion of Cu alloys and grey cast iron for power plant components by visual inspection and hardness measurement
ISO 18069:2015	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Method for determination of the uniform corrosion rate of stainless steels and nickel based alloys in liquids
ISO 18070:2015	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Crevice corrosion formers with disc springs for flat specimens or tubes made from stainless steel
ISO 18086:2019	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Determination of AC corrosion — Protection criteria
ISO 18089:2015	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Determination of the critical crevice temperature (CCT) for stainless steels under potentiostatic control
ISO 19097-1:2018	Accelerated life test method of mixed metal oxide anodes for cathodic protection — Part 1: Application in concrete
ISO 19097-2:2018	Accelerated life test method of mixed metal oxide anodes for cathodic protection — Part 2: Application in soils and natural waters
ISO 19280:2017	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Measurement of critical crevice temperature for cylindrical crevice geometries in ferric chloride solution
ISO 19735:2023	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Corrosivity of atmospheres — Mapping areas of increased risk of corrosion
ISO 20728:2018	Corrosion of metal and alloys — Determination of resistance of magnesium alloys to stress corrosion cracking
ISO 21062:2020	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Determination of the corrosion rates of embedded steel reinforcement in concrete exposed to simulated marine environments
ISO 21153:2018	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Measurement of environmentally assisted small crack growth rate
ISO 21207:2025	Corrosion tests in artificial atmospheres — Accelerated corrosion tests involving alternate exposure to corrosion-promoting gases, neutral salt-spray and drying
ISO 21601:2013	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Guidelines for assessing the significance of stress corrosion cracks detected in service
ISO 21608:2012	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Test method for isothermal-exposure oxidation testing under high-temperature corrosion conditions for metallic materials
ISO 21610:2009	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Accelerated corrosion test for intergranular corrosion susceptibility of austenitic stainless steels
ISO 22410:2020	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Electrochemical measurement of ion transfer resistance to characterize the protective rust layer on weathering steel
ISO 22426:2020	Assessment of the effectiveness of cathodic protection based on coupon measurements
ISO 22479:2019	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Sulfur dioxide test in a humid atmosphere (fixed gas method)
ISO 22848:2021	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Test method for measuring the stress corrosion crack growth rate of steels and alloys under static-load conditions in high-temperature water
ISO 22858:2020	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Electrochemical measurements — Test method for monitoring atmospheric corrosion
ISO 22910:2020	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Measurement of the electrochemical critical localized corrosion temperature (E-CLCT) for Ti alloys fabricated via the additive manufacturing method
ISO 23123:2020	Corrosion control engineering life cycle — General requirements
ISO 23221:2020	Pipeline corrosion control engineering life cycle — General requirements
ISO 23222:2020	Corrosion control engineering life cycle — Risk assessment
ISO 23226:2020	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Guidelines for the corrosion testing of metals and alloys exposed in deep-sea water
ISO 23449:2020	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Multielectrode arrays for corrosion measurement
ISO 23669:2022	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Requirements for localised corrosion and environmentally assisted cracking testing of additively manufactured metals and alloys
ISO 23721:2022	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Rating method by appearance of rust and stains of atmospheric corrosion for stainless steels
ISO 24020:2022	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Standard test method for particle-free erosion corrosion of metallic materials by jet-in-slit
ISO 24239:2022	Corrosion control engineering life cycle in fossil fuel power plants — General requirements
ISO 24656:2022	Cathodic protection of offshore wind structures
ISO 26146:2025	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Method for metallographic examination of samples after exposure to high-temperature corrosive environments

Table 39. ISO/TC 156 Projects under development.

Project Reference	Title
ISO/DPAS 5929	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Test and evaluation method for the corrosion of steel bar embedded in concrete structure exposed to total corrosion zones in marine environments
ISO/AWI TR 8564	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Reference data for ISO 16539:2013, Method B
ISO/AWI 8702	Professional technical supervision of corrosion control life cycle engineering
ISO/PWI 8786.2	Corrosion Control Engineering Life Cycle-- Vocabulary
ISO/CD 9225	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Corrosivity of atmospheres — Measurement of environmental parameters affecting corrosivity of atmospheres
ISO/FDIS 9350	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Testing method of corrosion resistance for hafnium at high temperature and pressure
ISO/PWI TR 11303	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Guidelines for selection of protection methods against atmospheric corrosion
ISO/DIS 14993	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Accelerated testing involving cyclic exposure to salt mist, dry and wet conditions
ISO/DIS 16364	Corrosion of Metals and Alloys - Guidelines for Galvanic Corrosion Control
ISO/PWI 16606	Intelligent Corrosion Control Engineering Life Cycle — General Requirements
ISO 16674	Corrosion control engineering life cycle of power transmission and transformation systems — General requirements
ISO 16701	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Corrosion in artificial atmosphere — Accelerated corrosion test involving exposure under controlled conditions of humidity cycling and intermittent spraying of a salt solution
ISO/CD 18717-1	Corrosion of metals and alloys--Performance test method for volatile corrosion inhibitor materials — Part 1: Vapor inhibiting ability
ISO/PWI 18970	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Test method for particle-free erosion corrosion of metallic materials in flowing liquids by rotating disk with specimens on periphery
ISO/DIS 18971	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Monitoring method for corrosion states of stainless steel in industrial cooling water
ISO/PWI 18978	Corrosion of metals and alloys--Guidelines of marine environment zonation for the corrosion of embedded steel reinforcement in concrete
ISO/DIS 19691	Measurement method of corrosion for weathering steel structures
ISO/DIS 21055	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Test method for microbiologically influenced corrosion of oil and gas transmission pipelines
ISO/CD TR 22801	Corrosion of metals and alloys – Testing methods for corrosion of conducting alloys in AC electric current condition
ISO/DTR 22861	Guidelines of marine environment zonation for steel corrosion embedded in concrete
ISO/FDIS 23225	Corrosion control engineering life cycle in nuclear power plants — General requirements
ISO/CD TR 23583	Sulfur corrosion test method of copper winding in electric field for power equipment
ISO/PWI 24017	Corrosion control engineering life cycle of wind power system in marine environment --General requirements
ISO/NP 24922	Guidelines for Construction and Engineering Application of Standardization System of Corrosion Control Engineering Life Cycle
ISO/NP 24927	Guidelines for Construction and Engineering Application of Standardization System of Corrosion Control Engineering Life Cycle
ISO/PWI 24928.2	Guidelines for Construction and Engineering Application of Standardization System of Corrosion Control Engineering Life Cycle
ISO/PWI 25015	Corrosion Corrosion of metals and alloys --- Method for high temperature oxidation test of metallic materials in water vapor containing atmosphere
ISO/DIS 25018	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Determination of resistance to stress corrosion cracking of copper and copper-zinc alloys in ammonia vapour
ISO/DIS 25072	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Guidelines for drawing regional corrosion map — Detailed measurements of corrosion and interpolation method
ISO/AWI 25276	Corrosion of metals and alloys --Electrochemistry test method in high temperature water for metallic materials used in nuclear power plants of PWR systems
ISO/AWI 25453	Corrosion control engineering full life cycle — Corrosion sources
ISO/PWI 25454	Steel-plastic Composite Corrosion-resistant Pipeline Installations Engineering Life Cycle- General Requirements
ISO/PWI 25633-1	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Classification of soil corrosivity — Part 1: Burial procedures of standard specimens and testing methods of soil corrosivity
ISO/AWI 25634	Guidelines of Data Science Application for Evaluating Atmospheric Corrosion Reliability on Steel Structures for Industrial Infrastructure

ISO/PWI 25635	Corrosion of metals and alloys--Preparation method for corrosion specimen of zirconium and zirconium alloys used in nuclear power
ISO/AWI 25686	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Accelerated cyclic corrosion tests for galvanic corrosion in deicing salt environment with “dry” and “wet” conditions at constant absolute humidity
ISO/NP 25713	Corrosion of metals and alloys--Test method for the corrosion of nuclear fuel cladding tubes in high temperature water with zinc injection
ISO/NP 25715	Corrosion of metals and alloys — Fracture toughness testing in gaseous hydrogen environment

Table 40. Standards from ISO/TC 199.

Reference	Title
ISO Guide 78:2012	Safety of machinery — Rules for drafting and presentation of safety standards
ISO 11161:2007	Safety of machinery — Integrated manufacturing systems — Basic requirements
ISO 11161:2007/Amd 1:2010	Safety of machinery — Integrated manufacturing systems — Basic requirements — Amendment 1
ISO 12100:2010	Safety of machinery — General principles for design — Risk assessment and risk reduction
ISO 13849-1:2023	Safety of machinery — Safety-related parts of control systems — Part 1: General principles for design
ISO 13849-2:2012	Safety of machinery — Safety-related parts of control systems — Part 2: Validation
ISO 13850:2015	Safety of machinery — Emergency stop function — Principles for design
ISO 13851:2019	Safety of machinery — Two-hand control devices — Principles for design and selection
ISO 13854:2017	Safety of machinery — Minimum gaps to avoid crushing of parts of the human body
ISO 13855:2024	Safety of machinery — Positioning of safeguards with respect to the approach of the human body
ISO 13856-1:2013	Safety of machinery — Pressure-sensitive protective devices — Part 1: General principles for design and testing of pressure-sensitive mats and pressure-sensitive floors
ISO 13856-2:2013	Safety of machinery — Pressure-sensitive protective devices — Part 2: General principles for design and testing of pressure-sensitive edges and pressure-sensitive bars
ISO 13856-3:2013	Safety of machinery — Pressure-sensitive protective devices — Part 3: General principles for design and testing of pressure-sensitive bumpers, plates, wires and similar devices
ISO 13857:2019	Safety of machinery — Safety distances to prevent hazard zones being reached by upper and lower limbs
ISO 14118:2017	Safety of machinery — Prevention of unexpected start-up
ISO 14119:2024	Safety of machinery — Interlocking devices associated with guards — Principles for design and selection
ISO 14120:2015	Safety of machinery — Guards — General requirements for the design and construction of fixed and movable guards
ISO/TR 14121-2:2012	Safety of machinery — Risk assessment — Part 2: Practical guidance and examples of methods
ISO 14122-1:2016	Safety of machinery — Permanent means of access to machinery — Part 1: Choice of fixed means and general requirements of access
ISO 14122-2:2016	Safety of machinery — Permanent means of access to machinery — Part 2: Working platforms and walkways
ISO 14122-3:2016	Safety of machinery — Permanent means of access to machinery — Part 3: Stairs, stepladders and guard-rails
ISO 14122-4:2016	Safety of machinery — Permanent means of access to machinery — Part 4: Fixed ladders
ISO 14123-1:2015	Safety of machinery — Reduction of risks to health resulting from hazardous substances emitted by machinery — Part 1: Principles and specifications for machinery manufacturers
ISO 14123-2:2015	Safety of machinery — Reduction of risks to health resulting from hazardous substances emitted by machinery — Part 2: Methodology leading to verification procedures
ISO 14159:2002	Safety of machinery — Hygiene requirements for the design of machinery
ISO 19353:2019	Safety of machinery — Fire prevention and fire protection
ISO 20607:2019	Safety of machinery — Instruction handbook — General drafting principles
ISO 21469:2006	Safety of machinery — Lubricants with incidental product contact — Hygiene requirements
ISO/TR 22053:2021	Safety of machinery — Safeguarding supportive system
ISO/TR 22100-1:2021	Safety of machinery — Relationship with ISO 12100 — Part 1: How ISO 12100 relates to type-B and type-C standards
ISO/TR 22100-2:2013	Safety of machinery — Relationship with ISO 12100 — Part 2: How ISO 12100 relates to ISO 13849-1
ISO/TR 22100-3:2016	Safety of machinery — Relationship with ISO 12100 — Part 3: Implementation of ergonomic principles in safety standards

ISO/TR 22100-4:2018	Safety of machinery — Relationship with ISO 12100 — Part 4: Guidance to machinery manufacturers for consideration of related IT-security (cyber security) aspects
ISO/TR 22100-5:2021	Safety of machinery — Relationship with ISO 12100 — Part 5: Implications of artificial intelligence machine learning
ISO/TR 24119:2015	Safety of machinery — Evaluation of fault masking serial connection of interlocking devices associated with guards with potential free contacts
ISO 29042-1:2008	Safety of machinery — Evaluation of the emission of airborne hazardous substances — Part 1: Selection of test methods
ISO 29042-2:2009	Safety of machinery — Evaluation of the emission of airborne hazardous substances — Part 2: Tracer gas method for the measurement of the emission rate of a given pollutant
ISO 29042-3:2009	Safety of machinery — Evaluation of the emission of airborne hazardous substances — Part 3: Test bench method for the measurement of the emission rate of a given pollutant
ISO 29042-4:2009	Safety of machinery — Evaluation of the emission of airborne hazardous substances — Part 4: Tracer method for the measurement of the capture efficiency of an exhaust system
ISO 29042-5:2010	Safety of machinery — Evaluation of the emission of airborne hazardous substances — Part 5: Test bench method for the measurement of the separation efficiency by mass of air cleaning systems with unducted outlet
ISO 29042-6:2010	Safety of machinery — Evaluation of the emission of airborne hazardous substances — Part 6: Test bench method for the measurement of the separation efficiency by mass of air cleaning systems with ducted outlet
ISO 29042-7:2010	Safety of machinery — Evaluation of the emission of airborne hazardous substances — Part 7: Test bench method for the measurement of the pollutant concentration parameter
ISO 29042-8:2011	Safety of machinery — Evaluation of the emission of airborne hazardous substances — Part 8: Room method for the measurement of the pollutant concentration parameter
ISO 29042-9:2011	Safety of machinery — Evaluation of the emission of airborne hazardous substances — Part 9: Decontamination index

Table 41. ISO/TC 199 Projects under development.

Project Reference	Title
ISO/DIS 11161	Safety of machinery — Integration of machinery into a system — Basic requirements
ISO/DIS 12100	Safety of machinery — General principles for design — Risk assessment and risk reduction
ISO/DIS 12895.2	Safety of machinery — Identification of whole body access and prevention of associated risk(s)
ISO/CD 13849-2.2	Safety of machinery — Safety-related parts of control systems — Part 2: Application of principles for the design and validation
ISO/AWI TR 13849-3	Safety of machinery — Safety-related parts of control systems — Part 3: Markov model-based PFH calculation
ISO/AWI 14122	Safety of machinery — Permanent means of access to machinery
ISO/AWI 14159	Safety of machinery — Hygiene requirements for the design of machinery
ISO 19353:2019/PWI Amd 1	Safety of machinery — Fire prevention and fire protection — Amendment 1
ISO/DIS 20607	Safety of machinery — Instruction handbook — General drafting principles
ISO/CD TR 21260	Safety of machinery — Mechanical limit determination for physical contacts from moving parts of machinery to persons

Table 42. Standards from CEN/TC 114.

Reference	Title
EN 1088:1995+A2:2008	Safety of machinery - Interlocking devices associated with guards - Principles for design and selection
EN 1093-1:2008	Safety of machinery - Evaluation of the emission of airborne hazardous substances - Part 1: Selection of test methods
EN 1093-2:2006+A1:2008	Safety of machinery - Evaluation of the emission of airborne hazardous substances - Part 2: Tracer gas method for the measurement of the emission rate of a given pollutant
EN 1093-3:2006+A1:2008	Safety of machinery - Evaluation of the emission of airborne hazardous substances - Part 3: Test bench method for the measurement of the emission rate of a given pollutant
EN 1093-4:1996+A1:2008	Safety of machinery - Evaluation of the emission of airborne hazardous substances - Part 4: Capture efficiency of an exhaust system - Tracer method

EN 1093-6:1998+A1:2008	Safety of machinery - Evaluation of the emission of airborne hazardous substances - Part 6: Separation efficiency by mass, unducted outlet
EN 1093-7:1998+A1:2008	Safety of machinery - Evaluation of the emission of airborne hazardous substances - Part 7: Separation efficiency by mass, ducted outlet
EN 1093-8:1998+A1:2008	Safety of machinery - Evaluation of the emission of airborne hazardous substances - Part 8: Pollutant concentration parameter, test bench method
EN 1093-9:1998+A1:2008	Safety of machinery - Evaluation of the emission of airborne hazardous substances - Part 9: Pollutant concentration parameter, room method
EN 1093-11:2001+A1:2008	Safety of machinery - Evaluation of the emission of airborne hazardous substances - Part 11: Decontamination index
EN ISO 4413:2010	Hydraulic fluid power - General rules and safety requirements for systems and their components (ISO 4413:2010)
EN ISO 4414:2010	Pneumatic fluid power - General rules and safety requirements for systems and their components (ISO 4414:2010)
EN ISO 11161:2007/A1:2010	Safety of machinery - Integrated manufacturing systems - Basic requirements - Amendment 1 (ISO 11161:2007/Amd 1:2010)
EN ISO 11161:2007	Safety of machinery - Integrated manufacturing systems - Basic requirements (ISO 11161:2007)
EN ISO 12100:2010	Safety of machinery - General principles for design - Risk assessment and risk reduction (ISO 12100:2010)
EN 12198-1:2000+A1:2008	Safety of machinery - Assessment and reduction of risks arising from radiation emitted by machinery - Part 1: General principles
EN 12198-2:2002+A1:2008	Safety of machinery - Assessment and reduction of risks arising from radiation emitted by machinery - Part 2: Radiation emission measurement procedure
EN 12198-3:2002+A1:2008	Safety of machinery - Assessment and reduction of risks arising from radiation emitted by machinery - Part 3: Reduction of radiation by attenuation or screening
EN ISO 13849-1:2023	Safety of machinery - Safety-related parts of control systems - Part 1: General principles for design (ISO 13849-1:2023)
EN ISO 13849-2:2012	Safety of machinery - Safety-related parts of control systems - Part 2: Validation (ISO 13849-2:2012)
EN ISO 13850:2015	Safety of machinery - Emergency stop function - Principles for design (ISO 13850:2015)
EN ISO 13851:2019	Safety of machinery - Two-hand control devices - Principles for design and selection (ISO 13851:2019)
EN ISO 13854:2019	Safety of machinery - Minimum gaps to avoid crushing of parts of the human body (ISO 13854:2019)
EN ISO 13855:2024	Safety of machinery - Positioning of safeguards with respect to the approach of the human body (ISO 13855:2024)
EN ISO 13856-1:2013	Safety of machinery - Pressure-sensitive protective devices - Part 1: General principles for design and testing of pressure-sensitive mats and pressure-sensitive floors (ISO 13856-1:2013)
EN ISO 13856-2:2013	Safety of machinery - Pressure-sensitive protective devices - Part 2: General principles for design and testing of pressure-sensitive edges and pressure-sensitive bars (ISO 13856-2:2013)
EN ISO 13856-3:2013	Safety of machinery - Pressure-sensitive protective devices - Part 3: General principles for design and testing of pressure-sensitive bumpers, plates, wires and similar devices (ISO 13856-3:2013)
EN ISO 13857:2019	Safety of machinery - Safety distances to prevent hazard zones being reached by upper and lower limbs (ISO 13857:2019)
EN ISO 14118:2018	Safety of machinery - Prevention of unexpected start-up (ISO 14118:2018)
EN ISO 14119:2025	Safety of machinery - Interlocking devices associated with guards - Principles for design and selection (ISO 14119:2025)
EN ISO 14120:2015	Safety of machinery - Guards - General requirements for the design and construction of fixed and movable guards (ISO 14120:2015)
EN ISO 14122-1:2016	Safety of machinery - Permanent means of access to machinery - Part 1: Choice of fixed means and general requirements of access (ISO 14122-1:2016)
EN ISO 14122-2:2016	Safety of machinery - Permanent means of access to machinery - Part 2: Working platforms and walkways (ISO 14122-2:2016)
EN ISO 14122-3:2016	Safety of machinery - Permanent means of access to machinery - Part 3: Stairs, stepladders and guard-rails (ISO 14122-3:2016)
EN ISO 14122-4:2016	Safety of machinery - Permanent means of access to machinery - Part 4: Fixed ladders (ISO 14122-4:2016)
EN ISO 14123-1:2015	Safety of machinery - Reduction of risks to health resulting from hazardous substances emitted by machinery - Part 1: Principles and specifications for machinery manufacturers (ISO 14123-1:2015)
EN ISO 14123-2:2015	Safety of machinery - Reduction of risks to health resulting from hazardous substances emitted by machinery - Part 2: Methodology leading to verification procedures (ISO 14123-2:2015)

EN ISO 14159:2008	Safety of machinery - Hygiene requirements for the design of machinery (ISO 14159:2002)
CEN/TR 14715:2004	Safety of machinery - Ionizing radiation emitted by machinery - Guidance for the application of technical standards in the design of machinery in order to comply with legislative requirements
EN ISO 19353:2019	Safety of machinery - Fire prevention and fire protection (ISO 19353:2019)
EN ISO 20607:2019	Safety of machinery - Instruction handbook - General drafting principles (ISO 20607:2019)
EN ISO 21469:2006	Safety of machinery - Lubricants with incidental product contact - Hygiene requirements (ISO 21469:2006)
CEN ISO/TR 22100-1:2021	Safety of machinery - Relationship with ISO 12100 - Part 1: How ISO 12100 relates to type-B and type-C standards (ISO/TR 22100-1:2021)
CEN ISO/TR 22100-4:2020	Safety of machinery - Relationship with ISO 12100 - Part 4: Guidance to machinery manufacturers for consideration of related IT-security (cyber security) aspects (ISO/TR 22100-4:2018)
CEN ISO/TR 22100-5:2022	Safety of machinery - Relationship with ISO 12100 - Part 5: Implications of artificial intelligence machine learning (ISO/TR 22100-5:2021)

Table 43. CEN/TC 114 Projects under development.

Project Reference	Title
EN 349:1993/prA1	Safety of machinery - Minimum gaps to avoid crushing of parts of the human body
EN 574:1996/prA1	Safety of machinery - Two-hand control devices - Functional aspects - Principles for design
EN 626-1:1994/prA1	Safety of machinery - Reduction of risks to health from hazardous substances emitted by machinery - Part 1: Principles and specifications for machinery manufacturers
EN 626-2:1996/prA1	Safety of machinery - Reduction of risk to health from hazardous substances emitted by machinery - Part 2: Methodology leading to verification procedures
EN 953:1997/prA1	Safety of machinery - Guards - General requirements for the design and construction of fixed and movable guards
EN 982:1996/prA1	Safety of machinery - Safety requirements for fluid power systems and their components - Hydraulics
EN 983:1996/prA1	Safety of machinery - Safety requirements for fluid power systems and their components - Pneumatics
EN 999:1998/prA1	Safety of machinery - The positioning of protective equipment in respect of approach speeds of parts of the human body
EN 1037:1995/prA1	Safety of machinery - Prevention of unexpected start-up
EN 1760-1:1997/prA1	Safety of machinery - Pressure sensitive protective devices - Part 1: General principles for the design and testing of pressure sensitive mats and pressure sensitive floors
EN 1760-2:2001/prA1	Safety of machinery - Pressure sensitive protective devices - Part 2: General principles for the design and testing of pressure sensitive edges and pressure sensitive bars
EN 1760-3:2004/prA1	Safety of machinery - Pressure sensitive protective devices - Part 3: General principles for the design and testing of pressure sensitive bumpers, plates, wires and similar devices
prEN ISO 11161	Safety of machinery - Integration of machinery into a system - Basic requirements (ISO/DIS 11161:2024)
prEN ISO 12100	Safety of machinery - General principles for design - Risk assessment and risk reduction (ISO/DIS 12100:2024)
prEN ISO 12895	Safety of machinery - Identification of whole body access and prevention of associated risk(s) (ISO/DIS 12895:2025)
EN 13478:2001/prA1	Safety of machinery - Fire prevention and protection
prEN ISO 13849-2 rev	Safety of machinery — Safety-related parts of control systems — Part 2: Validation
prEN ISO 14122 rev	Safety of machinery — Permanent means of access to machinery — Part 1: Choice of fixed means of access between two levels
prEN ISO 14159 rev	Safety of machinery — Hygiene requirements for the design of machinery
prEN ISO 20607	Safety of machinery - Instruction handbook - General drafting principles (ISO/DIS 20607:2025)

Table 44. Standards from CEN/TC 305.

Reference	Title
EN 1127-1:2019	Explosive atmospheres - Explosion prevention and protection - Part 1: Basic concepts and methodology
EN 1127-2:2014	Explosive atmospheres - Explosion prevention and protection - Part 2: Basic concepts and methodology for mining

EN 1839:2017	Determination of the explosion limits and the limiting oxygen concentration(LOC) for flammable gases and vapours
EN 13237:2024	Potentially explosive atmospheres - Terms and definitions for equipment and protective systems intended for use in potentially explosive atmospheres
EN 14034-1:2004+A1:2011	Determination of explosion characteristics of dust clouds - Part 1: Determination of the maximum explosion pressure p _{max} of dust clouds
EN 14034-2:2006+A1:2011	Determination of explosion characteristics of dust clouds - Part 2: Determination of the maximum rate of explosion pressure rise (dp/dt) _{max} of dust clouds
EN 14034-3:2006+A1:2011	Determination of explosion characteristics of dust clouds - Part 3: Determination of the lower explosion limit LEL of dust clouds
EN 14034-4:2004+A1:2011	Determination of explosion characteristics of dust clouds - Part 4: Determination of the limiting oxygen concentration LOC of dust clouds
EN 14373:2021+A1:2025	Explosion suppression systems
EN 14460:2018	Explosion resistant equipment
EN 14491:2012	Dust explosion venting protective systems
EN 14591-1:2004	Explosion prevention and protection in underground mines - Protective systems - Part 1: 2-bar explosion proof ventilation structure
EN 14591-1:2004/AC:2006	Explosion prevention and protection in underground mines - Protective systems - Part 1: 2-bar explosion proof ventilation structure
EN 14591-2:2007	Explosion prevention and protection in underground mines - Protective systems - Part 2: Passive water trough barriers
EN 14591-2:2007/AC:2008	Explosion prevention and protection in underground mines - Protective systems - Part 2: Passive water trough barriers
EN 14591-4:2007	Explosion prevention and protection in underground mines - Protective systems - Part 4: Automatic extinguishing systems for road headers
EN 14591-4:2007/AC:2008	Explosion prevention and protection in underground mines - Protective systems - Part 4: Automatic extinguishing systems for road headers
EN 14797:2006	Explosion venting devices
EN 14983:2024	Explosion prevention and protection in underground mines - Equipment and protective systems for firedamp drainage
EN 14986:2024	Design of fans working in potentially explosive atmospheres
EN 14994:2007	Gas explosion venting protective systems
EN 15089:2009	Explosion Isolation Systems
EN 15188:2020	Determination of the spontaneous ignition behaviour of dust accumulations
EN 15198:2007	Methodology for the risk assessment of non-electrical equipment and components for intended use in potentially explosive atmospheres
EN 15233:2007	Methodology for functional safety assessment of protective systems for potentially explosive atmospheres
CEN/TR 15281:2022	Potentially explosive atmospheres - Explosion prevention and protection - Guidance on inerting for the prevention of explosions
EN 15794:2009	Determination of explosion points of flammable liquids
EN 15967:2022	Determination of maximum explosion pressure and the maximum rate of pressure rise of gases and vapours
EN 16009:2011	Flameless explosion venting devices
EN 16020:2011	Explosion diverters
EN 16447:2014	Explosion isolation flap valves
CEN/TR 16793:2016	Guide for the selection, application and use of flame arresters
CEN/TR 16829:2016+AC:2019	Fire and explosion prevention and protection for bucket elevators
EN 17077:2018	Determination of burning behaviour of dust layers
EN 17348:2022	Requirements for design and testing of vacuum cleaners for use in potentially explosive atmospheres
EN 17624:2022	Determination of explosion limits of gases and vapours at elevated pressures, elevated temperatures or with oxidizers other than air
CEN/TR 17838:2022	Use of plugs of bulk material in screw conveyors and product receivers for explosion isolation
EN ISO/IEC 80079-20-1:2019	Explosive atmospheres - Part 20-1: Material characteristics for gas and vapour classification - Test methods and data (ISO/IEC 80079-20-1:2017, including Cor 1:2018)
EN ISO/IEC 80079-20-2:2016/AC:2017	Explosive atmospheres - Part 20-2: Material characteristics - Combustible dusts test methods - Technical Corrigendum 1 (ISO/IEC 80079-20-2:2016/Cor 1:2017)
EN ISO/IEC 80079-20-2:2016	Explosive atmospheres - Part 20-2: Material characteristics - Combustible dusts test methods (ISO/IEC 80079-20-2:2016)

EN ISO/IEC 80079-34:2020	Explosive atmospheres - Part 34: Application of quality management systems for Ex Product manufacture (ISO/IEC 80079-34:2018)
EN ISO 80079-36:2016/AC:2019	Explosive atmospheres - Part 36: Non-electrical equipment for explosive atmospheres - Basic method and requirements - Technical Corrigendum 1 (ISO 80079-36:2016/Cor 1:2019)
EN ISO 80079-36:2016	Explosive atmospheres - Part 36: Non-electrical equipment for explosive atmospheres - Basic method and requirements (ISO 80079-36:2016)
EN ISO 80079-37:2016	Explosive atmospheres - Part 37: Non-electrical equipment for explosive atmospheres - Non-electrical type of protection constructional safety "c", control of ignition sources "b", liquid immersion "k" (ISO 80079-37:2016)
EN ISO/IEC 80079-38:2016/A1:2018	Explosive atmospheres - Part 38: Equipment and components in explosive atmospheres in underground mines (ISO/IEC 80079-38:2016)
EN ISO/IEC 80079-38:2016	Explosive atmospheres - Part 38: Equipment and components in explosive atmospheres in underground mines (ISO/IEC 80079-38:2016)
EN ISO/IEC 80079-49:2024	Explosive atmospheres - Part 49: Flame arresters - Performance requirements, test methods and limits for use (ISO/IEC 80079-49:2024)

Table 45. CEN/TC 305 Projects under development.

Project Reference	Title
prEN 1127-1	Explosive atmospheres - Explosion prevention and protection - Part 1: Basic concepts, methodology and design
EN 1127-1:2019/prA1	Explosive atmospheres - Explosion prevention and protection - Part 1: Basic concepts and methodology
EN 1127-2:2002/prA1	Explosive atmospheres - Explosion prevention and protection - Part 2: Basic concepts and methodology for mining
prEN 1127-2 rev	Explosive atmospheres - Explosion prevention and protection - Part 2: Basic concepts and methodology for mining
EN 1710:2005/prA1	Equipment and components intended for use in potentially explosive atmospheres in underground mines
prEN 14994 rev	Gas explosion venting protective systems
prEN 15089	Explosion isolation systems
prEN 15198 rev	Methodology for the risk assessment of non-electrical equipment and components for intended use in potentially explosive atmospheres
prEN 16447	Explosion isolation flap valves
prCEN/TR 16793 rev	Guide for the selection, application and use of flame arresters
prEN ISO/IEC 80079-20-1 rev	Explosive atmospheres — Part 20-1: Material characteristics for gas and vapour classification — Test methods and data
prEN ISO/IEC 80079-34 rev	Explosive atmospheres — Part 34: Application of quality management systems for Ex Product manufacture
prEN ISO 80079-36 rev	Explosive atmospheres — Part 36: Non-electrical equipment for explosive atmospheres — Basic method and requirements
prEN ISO 80079-37 rev	Explosive atmospheres — Part 37: Non-electrical equipment for explosive atmospheres — Non-electrical type of protection constructional safety "c", control of ignition sources "b", liquid immersion "k"
prEN ISO 80079-38	Explosive atmospheres - Part 38: Equipment and components in explosive atmospheres in underground mines (ISO/IEC DIS 80079-38:2025)
prEN ISO/IEC 80079-41	Explosive atmospheres - Part 41: Reciprocating internal combustion engines (ISO/IEC DIS 80079-41:2025)
prEN ISO/IEC 80079-50	Explosion venting devices

Table 46. Standards from IEC/TC 31.

Reference	Title
IEC 60079-0:2017	Explosive atmospheres - Part 0: Equipment - General requirements
IEC 60079-0:2017/ISH1:2019	Interpretation Sheet 1 - Explosive atmospheres - Part 0: Equipment - General requirements
IEC 60079-0:2017/ISH2:2019	Interpretation Sheet 2 - Explosive atmospheres - Part 0: Equipment - General requirements

IEC 0:2017/COR1:2020	60079-	Corrigendum 1 - Explosive atmospheres - Part 0: Equipment - General requirements
IEC 60079-1:2014		Explosive atmospheres - Part 1: Equipment protection by flameproof enclosures "d"
IEC 1:2014/ISH1:2020	60079-	Interpretation sheet 1 - Explosive atmospheres - Part 1: Equipment protection by flameproof enclosures "d"
IEC 1:2014/COR1:2018	60079-	Corrigendum 1 - Explosive atmospheres - Part 1: Equipment protection by flameproof enclosures "d"
IEC 60079-2:2014		Explosive atmospheres - Part 2: Equipment protection by pressurized enclosure "p"
IEC 2:2014/COR1:2015	60079-	Corrigendum 1 - Explosive atmospheres - Part 2: Equipment protection by pressurized enclosure "p"
IEC 60079-5:2015		Explosive atmospheres - Part 5: Equipment protection by powder filling "q"
IEC 5:2015/AMD1:2022	60079-	Amendment 1 - Explosive atmospheres - Part 5: Equipment protection by powder filling "q"
IEC 60079-6:2015		Explosive atmospheres - Part 6: Equipment protection by liquid immersion "o"
IEC 6:2015/AMD1:2020	60079-	Amendment 1 - Explosive atmospheres - Part 6: Equipment protection by liquid immersion "o"
IEC 60079-7:2015		Explosive atmospheres - Part 7: Equipment protection by increased safety "e"
IEC 7:2015/ISH1:2016	60079-	Interpretation sheet 1 - Explosive atmospheres - Part 7: Equipment protection by increased safety "e"
IEC 7:2015/AMD1:2017	60079-	Amendment 1 - Explosive atmospheres - Part 7: Equipment protection by increased safety "e"
IEC 60079-15:2017		Explosive atmospheres - Part 15: Equipment protection by type of protection "n"
IEC 60079-18:2014		Explosive atmospheres - Part 18: Equipment protection by encapsulation "m"
IEC 18:2014/COR1:2018	60079-	Corrigendum 1 - Explosive atmospheres - Part 18: Equipment protection by encapsulation "m"
IEC 18:2014/AMD1:2017	60079-	Amendment 1 - Explosive atmospheres - Part 18: Equipment protection by encapsulation "m"
IEC 60079-26:2021		Explosive atmospheres - Part 26: Equipment with Separation Elements or combined Levels of Protection
IEC 60079-28:2015		Explosive atmospheres - Part 28: Protection of equipment and transmission systems using optical radiation
IEC 28:2015/ISH1:2019	60079-	Interpretation Sheet 1 - Explosive atmospheres - Part 28: Protection of equipment and transmission systems using optical radiation
IEC 60079-29-1:2016		Explosive atmospheres - Part 29-1: Gas detectors - Performance requirements of detectors for flammable gases
IEC 1:2016/ISH1:2019	60079-29-	Interpretation Sheet 1 - Explosive atmospheres - Part 29-1: Gas detectors - Performance requirements of detectors for flammable gases
IEC 1:2016/ISH2:2019	60079-29-	Interpretation Sheet 2 - Explosive atmospheres - Part 29-1: Gas detectors - Performance requirements of detectors for flammable gases
IEC 1:2016/AMD1:2020	60079-29-	Amendment 1 - Explosive atmospheres - Part 29-1: Gas detectors - Performance requirements of detectors for flammable gases
IEC 60079-29-2:2015		Explosive atmospheres - Part 29-2: Gas detectors - Selection, installation, use and maintenance of detectors for flammable gases and oxygen
IEC 60079-29-3:2014		Explosive atmospheres - Part 29-3: Gas detectors - Guidance on functional safety of fixed gas detection systems
IEC 60079-29-4:2009		Explosive atmospheres - Part 29-4: Gas detectors - Performance requirements of open path detectors for flammable gases
IEC 4:2009/COR1:2010	60079-29-	Corrigendum 1 - Explosive atmospheres - Part 29-4: Gas detectors - Performance requirements of open path detectors for flammable gases
IEC/IEEE 60079-30-1:2015		Explosive atmospheres - Part 30-1: Electrical resistance trace heating - General and testing requirements
IEC/IEEE 60079-30-2:2015		Explosive atmospheres - Part 30-2: Electrical resistance trace heating - Application guide for design, installation and maintenance
IEC 60079-31:2022		Explosive atmospheres - Part 31: Equipment dust ignition protection by enclosure "t"
IEC 31:2022/COR1:2023	60079-	Corrigendum 1 - Explosive atmospheres - Part 31: Equipment dust ignition protection by enclosure "t"
IEC TS 60079-32-1:2013		Explosive atmospheres - Part 32-1: Electrostatic hazards, guidance
IEC 1:2013/AMD1:2017	TS 60079-32-	Amendment 1 - Explosive atmospheres - Part 32-1: Electrostatic hazards, guidance
IEC 60079-32-2:2015		Explosive atmospheres - Part 32-2: Electrostatics hazards - Tests
IEC 60079-33:2012		Explosive atmospheres - Part 33: Equipment protection by special protection 's'

IEC 60079-35-1:2011	Explosive atmospheres - Part 35-1: Caplights for use in mines susceptible to firedamp - General requirements - Construction and testing in relation to the risk of explosion
IEC 60079-35-2:2011	Explosive atmospheres - Part 35-2: Caplights for use in mines susceptible to firedamp - Performance and other safety-related matters
IEC TS 60079-40:2015	Explosive atmospheres - Part 40: Requirements for process sealing between flammable process fluids and electrical systems
IEC TS 60079-42:2019	Explosive atmospheres - Part 42: Electrical safety devices for the control of potential ignition sources for Ex-Equipment
IEC TS 60079-43:2017	Explosive atmospheres - Part 43: Equipment in adverse service conditions
IEC TS 60079-44:2023	Explosive atmospheres - Part 44: Personal competence
IEC TS 60079-46:2017	Explosive atmospheres - Part 46: Equipment assemblies
IEC 62990-1:2019	Workplace atmospheres - Part 1: Gas detectors - Performance requirements of detectors for toxic gases
IEC 62990-1:2019/COR1:2019	Corrigendum 1 - Workplace atmospheres - Part 1: Gas detectors - Performance requirements of detectors for toxic gases
IEC 62990-2:2021	Workplace atmospheres - Part 2: Gas detectors - Selection, installation, use and maintenance of detectors for toxic gases and vapours

Table 47. IEC/TC 31 Projects under development.

Project Reference	Title
IEC 60079-0 ED8	Explosive atmospheres - Part 0: Equipment - General requirements
IEC 60079-1 ED8	Explosive atmospheres - Part 1: Equipment protection by flameproof enclosures "d"
IEC 60079-2 ED7	Explosive atmospheres - Part 2: Equipment protection by pressurized enclosure "p"
IEC 60079-15 ED6	Explosive atmospheres - Part 15: Equipment protection by type of protection "n"
IEC 60079-18 ED5	Explosive atmospheres - Part 18: Equipment protection by encapsulation "m"
IEC 60079-26 ED5	Explosive atmospheres - Part 26: Equipment with Separation Elements or combined Levels of Protection
IEC 60079-28 ED3	Explosive atmospheres - Part 28: Protection of equipment and transmission systems using optical radiation
IEC 60079-29-0 ED1	Explosive atmospheres - Part 29-0: Gas detectors - General requirements and test methods, and possible supplementary parts.
IEC 60079-29-3 ED2	Explosive atmospheres - Part 29-3: Gas detectors - Guidance on functional safety of fixed gas detection systems
IEC/IEEE 60079-30-1 ED2	Explosive atmospheres - Part 30-1: Electrical resistance trace heating - General and testing requirements
IEC/IEEE 60079-30-2 ED2	Explosive atmospheres – Part 30-2: Electrical resistance trace heating – Guidance on application for design, installation and maintenance
IEC 60079-33 ED2	Explosive atmospheres - Part 33: Equipment protection by special protection 's'
IEC 60079-42 ED1	Explosive atmospheres - Part 42: Electrical safety devices for the control of potential ignition sources for Ex-Equipment
IEC 60079-45 ED1	Explosive atmospheres - Part 45 - Electrical Ignition Systems for Internal Combustion Engines
IEC 60079-46 ED1	Explosive atmospheres - Part 46: Equipment assemblies
IEC 60079-101 ED1	Explosive atmosphere – Part 101: Principles of explosion protection
IEC 60079-0 ED8	Explosive atmospheres - Part 0: Equipment - General requirements

Table 48. Standards from IEC/TC 106.

Reference	Title
IEC 61786-1:2013	Measurement of DC magnetic, AC magnetic and AC electric fields from 1 Hz to 100 kHz with regard to exposure of human beings - Part 1: Requirements for measuring instruments
IEC 61786-1:2013/AMD1:2024	Amendment 1 - Measurement of DC magnetic, AC magnetic and AC electric fields from 1 Hz to 100 kHz with regard to exposure of human beings - Part 1: Requirements for measuring instruments
IEC 61786-2:2014	Measurement of DC magnetic, AC magnetic and AC electric fields from 1 Hz to 100 kHz with regard to exposure of human beings - Part 2: Basic standard for measurements
IEC 62110:2009	Electric and magnetic field levels generated by AC power systems - Measurement procedures with regard to public exposure

IEC 62110:2009/COR1:2015	Corrigendum 1 - Electric and magnetic field levels generated by AC power systems - Measurement procedures with regard to public exposure
IEC 62209-3:2019	Measurement procedure for the assessment of specific absorption rate of human exposure to radio frequency fields from hand-held and body-mounted wireless communication devices - Part 3: Vector measurement-based systems (Frequency range of 600 MHz to 6 GHz)
IEC/IEEE 62209-1528:2020	Measurement procedure for the assessment of specific absorption rate of human exposure to radio frequency fields from hand-held and body-worn wireless communication devices - Human models, instrumentation and procedures (Frequency range of 4 MHz to 10 GHz)
IEC 62226-1:2004	Exposure to electric or magnetic fields in the low and intermediate frequency range - Methods for calculating the current density and internal electric field induced in the human body - Part 1: General
IEC 62226-2-1:2004	Exposure to electric or magnetic fields in the low and intermediate frequency range - Methods for calculating the current density and internal electric field induced in the human body - Part 2-1: Exposure to magnetic fields - 2D models
IEC 62226-3-1:2007	Exposure to electric or magnetic fields in the low and intermediate frequency range - Methods for calculating the current density and internal electric field induced in the human body - Part 3-1: Exposure to electric fields - Analytical and 2D numerical models
IEC 62226-3-1:2007/AMD1:2016	Amendment 1 - Exposure to electric or magnetic fields in the low and intermediate frequency range - Methods for calculating the current density and internal electric field induced in the human body - Part 3-1: Exposure to electric fields - Analytical and 2D numerical models
IEC 62232:2025	Determination of RF field strength, power density and SAR in the vicinity of base stations for the purpose of evaluating human exposure
IEC 62233:2005	Measurement methods for electromagnetic fields of household appliances and similar apparatus with regard to human exposure
IEC 62311:2019	Assessment of electronic and electrical equipment related to human exposure restrictions for electromagnetic fields (0 Hz to 300 GHz)
IEC 62369-1:2008	Evaluation of human exposure to electromagnetic fields from short range devices (SRDs) in various applications over the frequency range 0 GHz to 300 GHz - Part 1: Fields produced by devices used for electronic article surveillance, radio frequency identification and similar systems
IEC 62479:2010	Assessment of the compliance of low-power electronic and electrical equipment with the basic restrictions related to human exposure to electromagnetic fields (10 MHz to 300 GHz)
IEC 62577:2009	Evaluation of human exposure to electromagnetic fields from a stand-alone broadcast transmitter (30 MHz - 40 GHz)
IEC TR 62630:2010	Guidance for evaluating exposure from multiple electromagnetic sources
IEC TR 62669:2019	Case studies supporting IEC 62232 - Determination of RF field strength, power density and SAR in the vicinity of radiocommunication base stations for the purpose of evaluating human exposure
IEC/IEEE 62704-1:2017	Determining the peak spatial-average specific absorption rate (SAR) in the human body from wireless communications devices, 30 MHz to 6 GHz - Part 1: General requirements for using the finite difference time-domain (FDTD) method for SAR calculations
IEC/IEEE 62704-2:2017	Determining the peak spatial-average specific absorption rate (SAR) in the human body from wireless communications devices, 30 MHz to 6 GHz - Part 2: Specific requirements for finite difference time domain (FDTD) modelling of exposure from vehicle mounted antennas
IEC/IEEE 62704-3:2017	Determining the peak spatial-average specific absorption rate (SAR) in the human body from wireless communications devices, 30 MHz to 6 GHz - Part 3: Specific requirements for using the finite difference time domain (FDTD) method for SAR calculations of mobile phones
IEC/IEEE 62704-4:2020	Determining the peak spatial-average specific absorption rate (SAR) in the human body from wireless communication devices, 30 MHz to 6 GHz - Part 4: General requirements for using the finite element method for SAR calculations
IEC 62764-1:2022	Measurement procedures of magnetic field levels generated by electronic and electrical equipment in the automotive environment with respect to human exposure - Part 1: Low-frequency magnetic fields
IEC TR 62905:2018	Exposure assessment methods for wireless power transfer systems
IEC TR 63167:2024	Assessment of contact current related to human exposure to electric, magnetic and electromagnetic fields
IEC/IEEE 63184:2025	Assessment methods of the human exposure to electric and magnetic fields from wireless power transfer systems – Models, instrumentation, measurement and computational methods and procedures (frequency range of 3 kHz to 30 MHz)
IEC/IEEE 63195-1:2022	Assessment of power density of human exposure to radio frequency fields from wireless devices in close proximity to the head and body (frequency range of 6 GHz to 300 GHz) - Part 1: Measurement procedure

IEC/IEEE 63195-2:2022	Assessment of power density of human exposure to radio frequency fields from wireless devices in close proximity to the head and body (frequency range of 6 GHz to 300 GHz) - Part 2: Computational procedure
IEC TR 63377:2022	Procedures for the assessment of human exposure to electromagnetic fields from radiative wireless power transfer systems – Measurement and computational methods (frequency range of 30 MHz to 300 GHz)
IEC TR 63424-1:2024	Validation of dynamic power control and exposure time-averaging algorithms - Part 1: Cellular network implementations for SAR at frequencies up to 6 GHz
IEC PAS 63446:2022	Conversion method of specific absorption rate to absorbed power density for the assessment of human exposure to radio frequency electromagnetic fields from wireless devices in close proximity to the head and body - Frequency range of 6 GHz to 10 GHz

Table 49. IEC/TC 106 Projects under development.

Project Reference	Title
IEC/IEEE 62209-3 ED2	Measurement procedure for the assessment of specific absorption rate of human exposure to radio frequency fields from hand-held and body-mounted wireless communication devices - Part 3: Vector measurement-based systems (Frequency range of 600 MHz to 6 GHz)
IEC/IEEE PAS 62209-5 ED1	Methods for validation of SAR measurement systems for hand-held and body-mounted wireless communication devices (Frequency range of 4 MHz to 10 GHz)
IEC/IEEE 62209-1528/AMD1 ED1	Amendment 1 - Measurement procedure for the assessment of specific absorption rate of human exposure to radio frequency fields from hand-held and body-worn wireless communication devices - Human models, instrumentation and procedures (Frequency range of 4 MHz to 10 GHz)
IEC TR 62669 ED3	Case studies supporting IEC 62232 - Determination of RF field strength, power density and SAR in the vicinity of radiocommunication base stations for the purpose of evaluating human exposure
IEC/IEEE 62704-1 ED2	Determining the peak spatial-average specific absorption rate (SAR) in the human body from wireless communications devices, 100 kHz to 10 GHz - Part 1: General requirements for using the finite-difference time-domain (FDTD) method for SAR calculations
IEC/IEEE 62704-2/AMD1 ED1	Amendment 1 - Determining the peak spatial-average specific absorption rate (SAR) in the human body from wireless communications devices, 30 MHz to 6 GHz – Part 2: Specific requirements for finite difference time domain (FDTD) modelling of exposure from vehicle mounted antennas
IEC/IEEE 62704-3 ED2	Determining the peak spatial-average specific absorption rate (SAR) in the human body from wireless communications devices, 30 MHz to 6 GHz - Part 3: Specific requirements for using the finite difference time domain (FDTD) method for SAR calculations of mobile phones
IEC/IEEE 62704-4 ED2	Determining the peak spatial-average specific absorption rate (SAR) in the human body from wireless communication devices, 30 MHz to 6 GHz - Part 4: General requirements for using the finite element method for SAR calculations
IEC/IEEE 63195-1 ED2	Assessment of power density of human exposure to radio frequency fields from wireless devices in close proximity to the head and body (frequency range of 6 GHz to 300 GHz) - Part 1: Measurement procedure FOR INCIDENT POWER DENSITY
IEC/IEEE 63195-2 ED2	Assessment of power density of human exposure to radio frequency fields from wireless devices in close proximity to the head and body (frequency range of 6 GHz to 300 GHz) - Part 2: Computational procedure for incident power density
IEC/IEEE 63195-3 ED1	Assessment of power density of human exposure to radio frequency fields from wireless devices in close proximity to the head and body (frequency range of 6 GHz to 300 GHz) - Part 3: Measurement procedure for absorbed power density
IEC/IEEE 63195-4 ED1	Assessment of power density of human exposure to radio frequency fields from wireless devices in close proximity to the head and body (frequency range of 6 GHz to 300 GHz) - Part 4: Computational procedure for absorbed power density
IEC/IEEE 63480 ED1	Assessment of Human Exposure to Electromagnetic Fields from Radiative Wireless Power Transfer Systems: Measurement and Computational Methods (Frequency Range of 30 MHz to 300 GHz)
IEC/IEEE TR 63572 ED1	Evaluation of Absorbed Power Density Related to Human Exposure to Radio Frequency Fields from Wireless Communication Devices Operating between 6 GHz and 300 GHz.
IEC/IEEE 62209-3 ED2	Measurement procedure for the assessment of specific absorption rate of human exposure to radio frequency fields from hand-held and body-mounted wireless communication devices - Part 3: Vector measurement-based systems (Frequency range of 600 MHz to 6 GHz)
IEC/IEEE PAS 62209-5 ED1	Methods for validation of SAR measurement systems for hand-held and body-mounted wireless communication devices (Frequency range of 4 MHz to 10 GHz)

IEC/IEEE 1528/AMD1 ED1	62209-	Amendment 1 - Measurement procedure for the assessment of specific absorption rate of human exposure to radio frequency fields from hand-held and body-worn wireless communication devices - Human models, instrumentation and procedures (Frequency range of 4 MHz to 10 GHz)
IEC TR 62669 ED3		Case studies supporting IEC 62232 - Determination of RF field strength, power density and SAR in the vicinity of radiocommunication base stations for the purpose of evaluating human exposure
IEC/IEEE 62704-1 ED2		Determining the peak spatial-average specific absorption rate (SAR) in the human body from wireless communications devices, 100 kHz to 10 GHz - Part 1: General requirements for using the finite-difference time-domain (FDTD) method for SAR calculations
IEC/IEEE 62704-2/AMD1 ED1		Amendment 1 - Determining the peak spatial-average specific absorption rate (SAR) in the human body from wireless communications devices, 30 MHz to 6 GHz – Part 2: Specific requirements for finite difference time domain (FDTD) modelling of exposure from vehicle mounted antennas
IEC/IEEE 62704-3 ED2		Determining the peak spatial-average specific absorption rate (SAR) in the human body from wireless communications devices, 30 MHz to 6 GHz - Part 3: Specific requirements for using the finite difference time domain (FDTD) method for SAR calculations of mobile phones
IEC/IEEE 62704-4 ED2		Determining the peak spatial-average specific absorption rate (SAR) in the human body from wireless communication devices, 30 MHz to 6 GHz - Part 4: General requirements for using the finite element method for SAR calculations
IEC/IEEE 63195-1 ED2		Assessment of power density of human exposure to radio frequency fields from wireless devices in close proximity to the head and body (frequency range of 6 GHz to 300 GHz) - Part 1: Measurement procedure FOR INCIDENT POWER DENSITY
IEC/IEEE 63195-2 ED2		Assessment of power density of human exposure to radio frequency fields from wireless devices in close proximity to the head and body (frequency range of 6 GHz to 300 GHz) - Part 2: Computational procedure for incident power density
IEC/IEEE 63195-3 ED1		Assessment of power density of human exposure to radio frequency fields from wireless devices in close proximity to the head and body (frequency range of 6 GHz to 300 GHz) - Part 3: Measurement procedure for absorbed power density
IEC/IEEE 63195-4 ED1		Assessment of power density of human exposure to radio frequency fields from wireless devices in close proximity to the head and body (frequency range of 6 GHz to 300 GHz) - Part 4: Computational procedure for absorbed power density
IEC/IEEE 63480 ED1		Assessment of Human Exposure to Electromagnetic Fields from Radiative Wireless Power Transfer Systems: Measurement and Computational Methods (Frequency Range of 30 MHz to 300 GHz)
IEC/IEEE TR 63572 ED1		Evaluation of Absorbed Power Density Related to Human Exposure to Radio Frequency Fields from Wireless Communication Devices Operating between 6 GHz and 300 GHz.

Table 50. Standards from CEN/TC 186.

Reference	Title
EN 746-1:1997+A1:2009	Industrial thermoprocessing equipment - Part 1: Common safety requirements for industrial thermoprocessing equipment
EN 746-3:2021	Industrial thermoprocessing equipment - Part 3: Safety requirements for the generation and use of atmosphere gases
EN 746-4:2000	Industrial thermoprocessing equipment - Part 4: Particular safety requirements for hot dip galvanising thermoprocessing equipment
EN 746-5:2000	Industrial thermoprocessing equipment - Part 5: Particular safety requirements for salt bath thermoprocessing equipment
EN 746-8:2000	Industrial thermoprocessing equipment - Part 8: Particular safety requirements for quenching equipment
EN ISO 13577-2:2023	Industrial furnaces and associated processing equipment - Safety - Part 2: Combustion and fuel handling systems (ISO 13577-2:2023)
EN ISO 13577-4:2022	Industrial furnaces and associated processing equipment - Safety - Part 4: Protective systems (ISO 13577-4:2022)

Table 51. CEN/TC 186 Projects under development.

Project Reference	Title
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EN 746-3:1997/prA1	Industrial thermoprocessing equipment - Part 3: Safety requirements for the generation and use of atmosphere gases
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Table 52. Standards from IEC/TC 51.

Reference	Title
IEC 60205:2016	Calculation of the effective parameters of magnetic piece parts
IEC 60205:2016/COR1:2018	Corrigendum 1 - Calculation of the effective parameters of magnetic piece parts
IEC 60329:1984	Strip-wound cut cores of grain oriented silicon-iron alloy, used for electronic and telecommunication equipment
IEC 60392:1972	Guide for the drafting of specifications for microwave ferrites
IEC 60401-1:2020	Terms and nomenclature for cores made of magnetically soft ferrites - Part 1: Terms used for physical irregularities and reference of dimensions
IEC 60401-3:2015	Terms and nomenclature for cores made of magnetically soft ferrites - Part 3: Guidelines on the format of data appearing in manufacturers catalogues of transformer and inductor cores
IEC 60556:2006	Gyromagnetic materials intended for application at microwave frequencies - Measuring methods for properties
IEC 60556:2006/AMD1:2016	Amendment 1 - Gyromagnetic materials intended for application at microwave frequencies - Measuring methods for properties
IEC 60635:1978	Toroidal strip-wound cores made of magnetically soft material
IEC 60635:1978/AMD1:1997	Amendment 1 - Toroidal strip-wound cores made of magnetically soft material
IEC 60732:1982	Measuring methods for cylinder cores, tube cores and screw cores of magnetic oxides
IEC 60740-1:2005	Laminations for transformers and inductors - Part 1: Mechanical and electrical characteristics
IEC 60740-2:1993	Laminations for transformers and inductors for use in telecommunication and electronic equipment - Part 2: Specification for the minimum permeabilities of laminations made of soft magnetic metallic materials
IEC 60852-1:1986	Outline dimensions of transformers and inductors for use in telecommunication and electronic equipment - Part 1: Transformers and inductors using YEI-1 laminations
IEC 60852-2:1992	Outline dimensions of transformers and inductors for use in telecommunication and electronic equipment - Part 2: Transformers and inductors using YEx-2 laminations for printed wiring board mounting
IEC 60852-3:1992	Outline dimensions of transformers and inductors for use in telecommunication and electronic equipment - Part 3: Transformers and inductors using YUI-1 laminations
IEC 60852-4:1996	Outline dimensions of transformers and inductors for use in telecommunication and electronic equipment - Part 4: Transformers and inductors using YUI-2 laminations
IEC 60852-5:1994	Outline dimensions of transformers and inductors for use in telecommunication and electronic equipment - Part 5: Transformers and inductors using the series Q of C-cores
IEC 61007:2020	Transformers and inductors for use in electronic and telecommunication equipment - Measuring methods and test procedures
IEC 61007:2020/COR1:2021	Corrigendum 1 - Transformers and inductors for use in electronic and telecommunication equipment - Measuring methods and test procedures
IEC 61021-1:1990	Laminated core packages for transformers and inductors used in telecommunication and electronic equipment - Part 1: Dimensions
IEC 61021-2:1995	Laminated core packages for transformers and inductors for use in telecommunication and electronic equipment - Part 2: Electrical characteristics for cores using YEE2 laminations
IEC 61248-1:1996	Transformers and inductors for use in electronic and telecommunication equipment - Part 1: Generic specification
IEC 61248-2:1996	Transformers and inductors for use in electronic and telecommunication equipment - Part 2: Sectional specification for signal transformers on the basis of the capability approval procedure
IEC 61248-3:1996	Transformers and inductors for use in electronic and telecommunication equipment - Part 3: Sectional specification for power transformers on the basis of the capability approval procedure
IEC 61248-4:1996	Transformers and inductors for use in electronic and telecommunication equipment - Part 4: Sectional specification for power transformers for switched mode power supplies (SMPS) on the basis of the capability approval procedure
IEC 61248-5:1996	Transformers and inductors for use in electronic and telecommunication equipment - Part 5: Sectional specification for pulse transformers on the basis of the capability approval procedure
IEC 61248-6:1996	Transformers and inductors for use in electronic and telecommunication equipment - Part 6: Sectional specification for inductors on the basis of the capability approval procedure

IEC 61248-7:1997	Transformers and inductors for use in electronic and telecommunication equipment - Part 7: Sectional specification for high-frequency inductors and intermediate frequency transformers on the basis of the capability approval procedure
IEC 61332:2016	Soft ferrite material classification
IEC 61333:2019	Marking on ferrite cores
IEC 61605:2016	Fixed inductors for use in electronic and telecommunication equipment - Marking codes
IEC 61609:1996	Microwave ferrite components - Guide for the drafting of specifications
IEC 61631:2020	Test method for the mechanical strength of cores made of magnetic oxides
IEC 61797-1:1996	Transformers and inductors for use in telecommunication and electronic equipment - Main dimensions of coil formers - Part 1: Coil formers for laminated cores
IEC 61843:1997	Measuring method for the level of intermodulation products generated in a gyromagnetic device
IEC 62024-1:2024	High frequency inductive components - Electrical characteristics and measuring methods - Part 1: Nanohenry range chip inductor
IEC 62024-2:2024	High frequency inductive components - Electrical characteristics and measuring methods - Part 2: Rated current of inductors for DC-to-DC converters
IEC 62025-2:2019	High frequency inductive components - Non-electrical characteristics and measuring methods - Part 2: Test methods for non-electrical characteristics
IEC 62044-1:2002	Cores made of soft magnetic materials - Measuring methods - Part 1: Generic specification
IEC 62044-2:2005	Cores made of soft magnetic materials - Measuring methods - Part 2: Magnetic properties at low excitation level
IEC 62044-2:2005/COR1:2021	Corrigendum 1 - Cores made of soft magnetic materials - Measuring methods - Part 2: Magnetic properties at low excitation level
IEC 62044-3:2023	Cores made of soft magnetic materials - Measuring methods - Part 3: Magnetic properties at high excitation level
IEC 62211:2017	Inductive components - Reliability management
IEC 62333-1:2006	Noise suppression sheet for digital devices and equipment - Part 1: Definitions and general properties
IEC 62333-2:2006	Noise suppression sheet for digital devices and equipment - Part 2: Measuring methods
IEC 62333-2:2006/AMD1:2015	Amendment 1 - Noise suppression sheet for digital devices and equipment - Part 2: Measuring methods
IEC 62333-3:2010	Noise suppression sheet for digital devices and equipment - Part 3: Characterization of parameters of noise suppression sheet
IEC 62358:2012	Ferrite cores - Standard inductance factor for gapped cores and its tolerance
IEC TS 62398:2004	Ferrite cores - Technology approval schedule (TAS)
IEC 62674-1:2012	High frequency inductive components - Part 1: Fixed surface mount inductors for use in electronic and telecommunication equipment
IEC TR 63090:2017	Dimensional tolerances of ferrite cores
IEC 63093-1:2020	Ferrite cores - Guidelines on dimensions and the limits of surface irregularities - Part 1: General specification
IEC 63093-2:2020	Ferrite cores - Guidelines on dimensions and the limits of surface irregularities - Part 2: Pot-cores for use in telecommunications, power supply, and filter applications
IEC 63093-3:2020	Ferrite cores - Guidelines on dimensions and the limits of surface irregularities - Part 3: Half pot-cores made of ferrite for inductive proximity switches
IEC 63093-4:2019	Ferrite cores - Guidelines on dimensions and the limits of surface irregularities - Part 4: RM-cores
IEC 63093-5:2018	Ferrite cores - Guidelines on dimensions and the limits of surface irregularities - Part 5: EP-cores and associated parts for use in inductors and transformers
IEC 63093-6:2018	Ferrite cores - Guidelines on dimensions and the limits of surface irregularities - Part 6: ETD-cores for use in power supplies
IEC 63093-7:2018	Ferrite cores - Guidelines on dimensions and the limits of surface irregularities - Part 7: EER-cores
IEC 63093-8:2018	Ferrite cores - Guidelines on dimensions and the limits of surface irregularities - Part 8: E-cores
IEC 63093-9:2020	Ferrite cores - Guidelines on dimensions and the limits of surface irregularities - Part 9: Planar cores
IEC 63093-10:2022	Ferrite cores - Guidelines on dimensions and the limits of surface irregularities - Part 10: PM-cores and associated parts
IEC 63093-11:2018	Ferrite cores - Guidelines on dimensions and the limits of surface irregularities - Part 11: EC-cores for use in power supply applications
IEC 63093-12:2019	Ferrite cores - Guidelines on dimensions and the limits of surface irregularities - Part 12: Ring-cores
IEC 63093-13:2019	Ferrite cores - Guidelines on dimensions and the limits of surface irregularities - Part 13: PQ-cores
IEC 63093-13:2019/COR1:2024	Corrigendum 1 - Ferrite cores - Guidelines on dimensions and the limits of surface irregularities - Part 13: PQ-cores
IEC 63093-14:2019	Ferrite cores - Guidelines on dimensions and the limits of surface irregularities - Part 14: EFD-cores
IEC 63182-1:2020	Magnetic powder cores - Guidelines on dimensions and the limits of surface irregularities - Part 1: General specification

IEC 63182-2:2020	Magnetic powder cores - Guidelines on dimensions and the limits of surface irregularities - Part 2: Ring-cores
IEC 63182-3:2021	Magnetic powder cores - Guidelines on dimensions and the limits of surface irregularities - Part 3: E-cores
IEC 63182-4:2021	Magnetic powder cores - Guidelines on dimensions and the limits of surface irregularities - Part 4: Block-cores
IEC 63182-5:2021	Magnetic powder cores - Guidelines on dimensions and the limits of surface irregularities - Part 5: Cylinder-cores
IEC 63299:2022	Classification of magnetic powder cores
IEC 63300:2023	Test methods for electrical and magnetic properties of magnetic powder cores
IEC TR 63307:2020	Measurement methods of the complex relative permeability and permittivity of noise suppression sheet

Table 53. IEC/TC 51 Projects under development.

Project Reference	Title
PWI 51-1	Inductors - Near Magnetic and Electric Field Characterization
IEC 60205 ED5	Calculation of the effective parameters of magnetic piece parts
IEC/IEEE 61007-389 ED1	Transformers and inductors for use in electronic and telecommunication equipment - Measuring methods and test procedures
IEC 61332 ED4	Soft ferrite material classification
IEC 62024-3 ED1	High frequency inductive components - Electrical characteristics and measuring methods - Part 3: AC loss measured by sinusoidal wave of inductors for DC-to-DC converters
IEC 62358 ED3	Ferrite cores - Standard inductance factor for gapped cores and its tolerance
IEC 62674-1 ED2	High frequency inductive components - Part 1: Fixed surface mount inductors for use in electronic and telecommunication equipment
IEC 63093-2 ED2	Ferrite cores - Guidelines on dimensions and the limits of surface irregularities - Part 2: Pot-cores for use in telecommunications, power supply, and filter applications
IEC 63093-4 ED2	Ferrite cores - Guidelines on dimensions and the limits of surface irregularities - Part 4: RM-cores
IEC 63093-5 ED2	Ferrite cores - Guidelines on dimensions and the limits of surface irregularities - Part 5: EP-cores and associated parts for use in inductors and transformers
IEC 63093-9 ED2	Ferrite cores - Guidelines on dimensions and the limits of surface irregularities - Part 9: Planar cores
IEC 63093-10 ED2	Ferrite cores - Guidelines on dimensions and the limits of surface irregularities - Part 10: PM-cores and associated parts
IEC 63093-15 ED1	Ferrite cores - Guidelines on dimensions and the limits of surface irregularities - Part 15: U-cores
IEC 63182-6 ED1	Magnetic powder cores - Guidelines on dimensions and the limits of surface irregularities - Part 6: EQ - cores
IEC 63182-7 ED1	Magnetic powder cores - Guidelines on dimensions and the limits of surface irregularities - Part 7: EER - cores
IEC 63182-8 ED1	Magnetic powder cores - Guidelines on dimensions and the limits of surface irregularities - Part 8: U-cores
IEC 63182-9 ED1	Magnetic powder cores - Guidelines on dimensions and the limits of surface irregularities - Part 9: Ellipse-cores
IEC TR 63307 ED2	Measurement methods of the complex relative permeability and permittivity of noise suppression sheet

Table 54. Standards from ISO/TC 211.

Reference	Title
ISO 6709:2022	Standard representation of geographic point location by coordinates
ISO 19101-1:2014	Geographic information — Reference model — Part 1: Fundamentals
ISO 19101-2:2018	Geographic information — Reference model — Part 2: Imagery
ISO 19103:2024	Geographic information — Conceptual schema language
ISO 19104:2016	Geographic information — Terminology
ISO 19105:2022	Geographic information — Conformance and testing
ISO 19106:2004	Geographic information — Profiles
ISO 19107:2019	Geographic information — Spatial schema

ISO 19108:2002	Geographic information — Temporal schema
ISO 19108:2002/Cor 1:2006	Geographic information — Temporal schema — Technical Corrigendum 1
ISO 19109:2015	Geographic information — Rules for application schema
ISO 19110:2016	Geographic information — Methodology for feature cataloguing
ISO 19111:2019	Geographic information — Referencing by coordinates
ISO 19111:2019/Amd 2:2023	Geographic information — Referencing by coordinates — Amendment 2
ISO 19111:2019/Amd 1:2021	Geographic information — Referencing by coordinates — Amendment 1
ISO 19112:2019	Geographic information — Spatial referencing by geographic identifiers
ISO 19115-1:2014	Geographic information — Metadata — Part 1: Fundamentals
ISO 19115-1:2014/Amd 2:2020	Geographic information — Metadata — Part 1: Fundamentals — Amendment 2
ISO 19115-1:2014/Amd 1:2018	Geographic information — Metadata — Part 1: Fundamentals — Amendment 1
ISO 19115-2:2019	Geographic information — Metadata — Part 2: Extensions for acquisition and processing
ISO 19115-2:2019/Amd 1:2022	Geographic information — Metadata — Part 2: Extensions for acquisition and processing — Amendment 1
ISO 19115-3:2023	Geographic information — Metadata — Part 3: XML schema implementation for fundamental concepts
ISO 19116:2025	Geographic information — Positioning services
ISO 19117:2012	Geographic information — Portrayal
ISO 19118:2011	Geographic information — Encoding
ISO 19119:2016	Geographic information — Services
ISO/TR 19121:2000	Geographic information — Imagery and gridded data
ISO 19123-1:2023	Geographic information — Schema for coverage geometry and functions — Part 1: Fundamentals
ISO 19123-2:2018	Geographic information — Schema for coverage geometry and functions — Part 2: Coverage implementation schema
ISO 19123-3:2023	Geographic information — Schema for coverage geometry and functions — Part 3: Processing fundamentals
ISO/TS 19124-1:2023	Geographic information — Calibration and validation of remote sensing data and derived products — Part 1: Fundamentals
ISO 19125-1:2004	Geographic information — Simple feature access — Part 1: Common architecture
ISO 19126:2021	Geographic information — Feature concept dictionaries and registers
ISO 19127:2019	Geographic information — Geodetic register
ISO 19128:2005	Geographic information — Web map server interface
ISO/TS 19129:2009	Geographic information — Imagery, gridded and coverage data framework
ISO 19130-1:2018	Geographic information — Imagery sensor models for geopositioning — Part 1: Fundamentals
ISO/TS 19130-2:2014	Geographic information — Imagery sensor models for geopositioning — Part 2: SAR, InSAR, lidar and sonar
ISO/TS 19130-3:2022	Geographic information — Imagery sensor models for geopositioning — Part 3: Implementation schema
ISO 19131:2022	Geographic information — Data product specifications
ISO 19132:2007	Geographic information — Location-based services — Reference model
ISO 19133:2005	Geographic information — Location-based services — Tracking and navigation
ISO 19134:2007	Geographic information — Location-based services — Multimodal routing and navigation
ISO 19135-1:2015	Geographic information — Procedures for item registration — Part 1: Fundamentals
ISO 19135-1:2015/Amd 1:2021	Geographic information — Procedures for item registration — Part 1: Fundamentals — Amendment 1
ISO 19136-1:2020	Geographic information — Geography Markup Language (GML) — Part 1: Fundamentals
ISO 19136-2:2015	Geographic information — Geography Markup Language (GML) — Part 2: Extended schemas and encoding rules
ISO 19137:2007	Geographic information — Core profile of the spatial schema
ISO/TS 19139-1:2019	Geographic information — XML schema implementation — Part 1: Encoding rules
ISO 19141:2008	Geographic information — Schema for moving features
ISO 19142:2010	Geographic information — Web Feature Service
ISO 19143:2010	Geographic information — Filter encoding
ISO 19144-1:2009	Geographic information — Classification systems — Part 1: Classification system structure
ISO 19144-1:2009/Cor 1:2012	Geographic information — Classification systems — Part 1: Classification system structure — Technical Corrigendum 1
ISO 19144-2:2023	Geographic information — Classification systems — Part 2: Land Cover Meta Language (LCML)

ISO/TS 19144-3:2024	Geographic information — Classification systems — Part 3: Land Use Meta Language (LUML)
ISO 19145:2013	Geographic information — Registry of representations of geographic point location
ISO 19146:2018	Geographic information — Cross-domain vocabularies
ISO 19147:2015	Geographic information — Transfer Nodes
ISO 19148:2021	Geographic information — Linear referencing
ISO/TS 19150-1:2012	Geographic information — Ontology — Part 1: Framework
ISO 19150-2:2015	Geographic information — Ontology — Part 2: Rules for developing ontologies in the Web Ontology Language (OWL)
ISO 19150-2:2015/Amd 1:2019	Geographic information — Ontology — Part 2: Rules for developing ontologies in the Web Ontology Language (OWL) — Amendment 1
ISO 19150-4:2019	Geographic information — Ontology — Part 4: Service ontology
ISO 19150-6:2023	Geographic information — Ontology — Part 6: Service ontology register
ISO 19152:2012	Geographic information — Land Administration Domain Model (LADM)
ISO 19152-1:2024	Geographic information — Land Administration Domain Model (LADM) — Part 1: Generic conceptual model
ISO 19152-2:2025	Geographic information — Land Administration Domain Model (LADM) — Part 2: Land registration
ISO 19152-3:2024	Geographic information — Land Administration Domain Model (LADM) — Part 3: Marine georegulation
ISO 19154:2014	Geographic information — Ubiquitous public access — Reference model
ISO 19155:2012	Geographic information — Place Identifier (PI) architecture
ISO 19155-2:2017	Geographic information — Place Identifier (PI) architecture — Part 2: Place Identifier (PI) linking
ISO 19156:2023	Geographic information — Observations, measurements and samples
ISO 19157:2013	Geographic information — Data quality
ISO 19157:2013/Amd 1:2018	Geographic information — Data quality — Amendment 1: Describing data quality using coverages
ISO 19157-1:2023	Geographic information — Data quality — Part 1: General requirements
ISO/TS 19157-2:2016	Geographic information — Data quality — Part 2: XML schema implementation
ISO/TS 19158:2012	Geographic information — Quality assurance of data supply
ISO/TS 19159-1:2014	Geographic information — Calibration and validation of remote sensing imagery sensors and data — Part 1: Optical sensors
ISO/TS 19159-2:2016	Geographic information — Calibration and validation of remote sensing imagery sensors and data — Part 2: Lidar
ISO/TS 19159-3:2018	Geographic information — Calibration and validation of remote sensing imagery sensors and data — Part 3: SAR/InSAR
ISO/TS 19159-4:2022	Geographic information — Calibration and validation of remote sensing imagery sensors and data — Part 4: Space-borne passive microwave radiometers
ISO 19160-1:2015	Addressing — Part 1: Conceptual model
ISO 19160-2:2023	Addressing — Part 2: Assigning and maintaining addresses for objects in the physical world
ISO 19160-3:2020	Addressing — Part 3: Address data quality
ISO 19160-4:2023	Addressing — Part 4: International postal address components and template language
ISO 19161-1:2020	Geographic information — Geodetic references — Part 1: International terrestrial reference system (ITRS)
ISO 19162:2019	Geographic information — Well-known text representation of coordinate reference systems
ISO 19162:2019/Amd 1:2023	Geographic information — Well-known text representation of coordinate reference systems — Amendment 1
ISO/TS 19163-1:2016	Geographic information — Content components and encoding rules for imagery and gridded data — Part 1: Content model
ISO/TS 19163-2:2020	Geographic information — Content components and encoding rules for imagery and gridded data — Part 2: Implementation schema
ISO 19164:2024	Geographic information — Indoor feature model
ISO 19165-1:2018	Geographic information — Preservation of digital data and metadata — Part 1: Fundamentals
ISO 19165-2:2020	Geographic information — Preservation of digital data and metadata — Part 2: Content specifications for Earth observation data and derived digital products
ISO/TS 19166:2021	Geographic information — BIM to GIS conceptual mapping (B2GM)
ISO/TR 19167:2019	Application of ubiquitous public access to-geographic information to an air quality information service
ISO 19168-1:2025	Geographic information — Geospatial API for features — Part 1: Core
ISO 19168-2:2022	Geographic information — Geospatial API for features — Part 2: Coordinate Reference Systems by Reference

ISO/TR 19169:2021	Geographic Information — Gap-analysis: mapping and describing the differences between the current GDF and ISO/TC 211 conceptual models to suggest ways to harmonize and resolve conflicting issues
ISO 19170-1:2021	Geographic information — Discrete Global Grid Systems Specifications — Part 1: Core Reference System and Operations, and Equal Area Earth Reference System
ISO/TR 19174:2025	Geographic information — Securing interoperability among heterogeneous city domain information models
ISO 19178-1:2025	Geographic information — Training data markup language for artificial intelligence — Part 1: Conceptual model
ISO 6709:2022	Standard representation of geographic point location by coordinates
ISO 19101-1:2014	Geographic information — Reference model — Part 1: Fundamentals
ISO 19101-2:2018	Geographic information — Reference model — Part 2: Imagery
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ISO 19104:2016	Geographic information — Terminology
ISO 19105:2022	Geographic information — Conformance and testing
ISO 19106:2004	Geographic information — Profiles
ISO 19107:2019	Geographic information — Spatial schema
ISO 19108:2002	Geographic information — Temporal schema
ISO 19108:2002/Cor 1:2006	Geographic information — Temporal schema — Technical Corrigendum 1
ISO 19109:2015	Geographic information — Rules for application schema
ISO 19110:2016	Geographic information — Methodology for feature cataloguing
ISO 19111:2019	Geographic information — Referencing by coordinates
ISO 19111:2019/Amd 2:2023	Geographic information — Referencing by coordinates — Amendment 2
ISO 19111:2019/Amd 1:2021	Geographic information — Referencing by coordinates — Amendment 1
ISO 19112:2019	Geographic information — Spatial referencing by geographic identifiers
ISO 19115-1:2014	Geographic information — Metadata — Part 1: Fundamentals
ISO 19115-1:2014/Amd 2:2020	Geographic information — Metadata — Part 1: Fundamentals — Amendment 2
ISO 19115-1:2014/Amd 1:2018	Geographic information — Metadata — Part 1: Fundamentals — Amendment 1
ISO 19115-2:2019	Geographic information — Metadata — Part 2: Extensions for acquisition and processing
ISO 19115-2:2019/Amd 1:2022	Geographic information — Metadata — Part 2: Extensions for acquisition and processing — Amendment 1
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ISO 19119:2016	Geographic information — Services
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ISO 19123-2:2018	Geographic information — Schema for coverage geometry and functions — Part 2: Coverage implementation schema
ISO 19123-3:2023	Geographic information — Schema for coverage geometry and functions — Part 3: Processing fundamentals
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ISO/TS 19130-2:2014	Geographic information — Imagery sensor models for geopositioning — Part 2: SAR, InSAR, lidar and sonar
ISO/TS 19130-3:2022	Geographic information — Imagery sensor models for geopositioning — Part 3: Implementation schema
ISO 19131:2022	Geographic information — Data product specifications
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ISO 19135-1:2015/Amd 1:2021	Geographic information — Procedures for item registration — Part 1: Fundamentals — Amendment 1
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ISO 19144-1:2009/Cor 1:2012	Geographic information — Classification systems — Part 1: Classification system structure — Technical Corrigendum 1
ISO 19144-2:2023	Geographic information — Classification systems — Part 2: Land Cover Meta Language (LCML)
ISO/TS 19144-3:2024	Geographic information — Classification systems — Part 3: Land Use Meta Language (LUML)
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ISO 19146:2018	Geographic information — Cross-domain vocabularies
ISO 19147:2015	Geographic information — Transfer Nodes
ISO 19148:2021	Geographic information — Linear referencing
ISO/TS 19150-1:2012	Geographic information — Ontology — Part 1: Framework
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ISO 19150-2:2015/Amd 1:2019	Geographic information — Ontology — Part 2: Rules for developing ontologies in the Web Ontology Language (OWL) — Amendment 1
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ISO 19150-6:2023	Geographic information — Ontology — Part 6: Service ontology register
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ISO 19152-2:2025	Geographic information — Land Administration Domain Model (LADM) — Part 2: Land registration
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ISO 19154:2014	Geographic information — Ubiquitous public access — Reference model
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ISO 19155-2:2017	Geographic information — Place Identifier (PI) architecture — Part 2: Place Identifier (PI) linking
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ISO 19157:2013	Geographic information — Data quality
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ISO 19157-1:2023	Geographic information — Data quality — Part 1: General requirements
ISO/TS 19157-2:2016	Geographic information — Data quality — Part 2: XML schema implementation
ISO/TS 19158:2012	Geographic information — Quality assurance of data supply
ISO/TS 19159-1:2014	Geographic information — Calibration and validation of remote sensing imagery sensors and data — Part 1: Optical sensors
ISO/TS 19159-2:2016	Geographic information — Calibration and validation of remote sensing imagery sensors and data — Part 2: Lidar
ISO/TS 19159-3:2018	Geographic information — Calibration and validation of remote sensing imagery sensors and data — Part 3: SAR/InSAR
ISO/TS 19159-4:2022	Geographic information — Calibration and validation of remote sensing imagery sensors and data — Part 4: Space-borne passive microwave radiometers
ISO 19160-1:2015	Addressing — Part 1: Conceptual model
ISO 19160-2:2023	Addressing — Part 2: Assigning and maintaining addresses for objects in the physical world
ISO 19160-3:2020	Addressing — Part 3: Address data quality
ISO 19160-4:2023	Addressing — Part 4: International postal address components and template language
ISO 19161-1:2020	Geographic information — Geodetic references — Part 1: International terrestrial reference system (ITRS)
ISO 19162:2019	Geographic information — Well-known text representation of coordinate reference systems

ISO 19162:2019/Amd 1:2023	Geographic information — Well-known text representation of coordinate reference systems — Amendment 1
ISO/TS 19163-1:2016	Geographic information — Content components and encoding rules for imagery and gridded data — Part 1: Content model
ISO/TS 19163-2:2020	Geographic information — Content components and encoding rules for imagery and gridded data — Part 2: Implementation schema
ISO 19164:2024	Geographic information — Indoor feature model
ISO 19165-1:2018	Geographic information — Preservation of digital data and metadata — Part 1: Fundamentals
ISO 19165-2:2020	Geographic information — Preservation of digital data and metadata — Part 2: Content specifications for Earth observation data and derived digital products
ISO/TS 19166:2021	Geographic information — BIM to GIS conceptual mapping (B2GM)
ISO/TR 19167:2019	Application of ubiquitous public access to-geographic information to an air quality information service
ISO 19168-1:2025	Geographic information — Geospatial API for features — Part 1: Core
ISO 19168-2:2022	Geographic information — Geospatial API for features — Part 2: Coordinate Reference Systems by Reference
ISO/TR 19169:2021	Geographic Information — Gap-analysis: mapping and describing the differences between the current GDF and ISO/TC 211 conceptual models to suggest ways to harmonize and resolve conflicting issues
ISO 19170-1:2021	Geographic information — Discrete Global Grid Systems Specifications — Part 1: Core Reference System and Operations, and Equal Area Earth Reference System
ISO/TR 19174:2025	Geographic information — Securing interoperability among heterogeneous city domain information models
ISO 19178-1:2025	Geographic information — Training data markup language for artificial intelligence — Part 1: Conceptual model
ISO/TR 19167:2019	Application of ubiquitous public access to-geographic information to an air quality information service
ISO 19168-1:2025	Geographic information — Geospatial API for features — Part 1: Core
ISO/TR 19167:2019	Application of ubiquitous public access to-geographic information to an air quality information service
ISO 19168-1:2025	Geographic information — Geospatial API for features — Part 1: Core

Table 55. ISO/TC 211 Projects under development.

Project reference	Title
ISO/PWI 5974	Evolution and revision formation for Geographic Data Files (GDF)
ISO 19109	Geographic information — General feature model and rules for application schema
ISO/AWI 19111	Geographic information — Referencing by coordinates
ISO/AWI 19115-1	Geographic information — Metadata — Part 1: Fundamentals
ISO/CD TR 19115-4	Geographic information — Metadata — Part 4: JSON schema implementation of metadata fundamentals
ISO/AWI TS 19115-5	Geographic information — Metadata — Part 5: DCAT mapping
ISO/AWI 19119	Geographic information — Services
ISO/AWI TR 19121	Geographic information — Imagery and gridded data
ISO/CD 19123-2	Geographic information — Schema for coverage geometry and functions — Part 2: Coverage implementation schema
ISO/CD TS 19123-4	Geographic information — Schema for coverage geometry and functions — Part 4: Tiling Schema
ISO/DTS 19124-2	Geographic information — Calibration and validation of remote sensing data and derived products — Part 2: SAR
ISO/AWI TS 19124-3	Geographic information — Calibration and validation of remote sensing data and derived products — Part 3: Optical sensors
ISO/AWI TS 19124-4	Geographic information — Calibration and validation of remote sensing data and derived products — Part 4: Lidar
ISO/DIS 19127	Geographic information — Geodetic register
ISO/CD TS 19130-2	Geographic information — Imagery sensor models for geopositioning — Part 2: SAR, InSAR, lidar and sonar
ISO/DIS 19135	Geographic information — Registration and register governance
ISO/AWI TS 19144-4	Geographic information — Classification systems — Part 4: Registration and implementation aspects

ISO 19152-4	Geographic information — Land Administration Domain Model (LADM) — Part 4: Valuation information
ISO 19152-5	Geographic information — Land Administration Domain Model (LADM) — Part 5: Spatial plan information
ISO/PWI 19152-6	Geographic information — Land Administration Domain Model (LADM) — Part 6: Part 6: Implementation aspects
ISO/DIS 19157-3	Geographic information — Data quality — Part 3: Data quality measures register
ISO/AWI 19158	Geographic information — Quality assurance of data supply
ISO/AWI 19161-2	Geographic information — Geodetic references — Part 2: Unique identification of geodetic ground stations
ISO/AWI 19163-2	Geographic information — Content components and encoding rules for imagery and gridded data — Part 2: Implementation schema
ISO/DTS 19166	Geographic information — Building information modelling (BIM) to geographic information systems (GIS) conceptual mapping (B2GM)
ISO/PWI 19170-2	Geographic information — Discrete Global Grid Systems Specifications — Part 2: Three-dimensional and Equi-volume DGGs RS
ISO/PWI 19170-3	Geographic information — Discrete Global Grid Systems Specifications — Part 3: Spatio-temporal DGGs RS
ISO/PWI 19170-4	Geographic information — Discrete Global Grid Systems Specifications — Part 4: Axis-aligned DGGs RS
ISO/PWI 19173	SMART Terminology for geographic information
ISO/TR 19175	Geographic information — Gap analysis of geospatial standards for indoor-outdoor seamless navigation
ISO/PWI 19176-1	Geographic information — Analysis ready data — Part 1: Framework and fundamentals
ISO/DIS 19177-1	Geographic information — Geospatial API for tiles — Part 1: Core
ISO/AWI TR 19179	Geographic Information - ESG Assessment in Geospatial Standards
ISO/AWI TR 19180	Geographic Information — Guidelines for incorporating gender sensitivity in geospatial standards
ISO/AWI TR 19181	Geographic information — Maintenance and management of common classifiers and their implementation artifacts
ISO/PWI TR 20366	Geographic Information – Gap analysis of geospatial standards for indoor-outdoor seamless navigation

Table 56. Standards from CEN/TC 287.

Reference	Title
EN ISO 6709:2022	Standard representation of geographic point location by coordinates (ISO 6709:2022)
CEN/TR 15449-1:2012	Geographic information - Spatial data infrastructures - Part 1: Reference model
CEN/TR 15449-2:2012	Geographic information - Spatial data infrastructures - Part 2: Best practices
CEN/TR 15449-3:2012	Geographic information - Spatial data infrastructures - Part 3: Data centric view
CEN/TR 15449-4:2013	Geographic information - Spatial Data Infrastructure - Part 4: Service centric view
CEN/TR 15449-5:2015	Geographic information - Spatial data infrastructures - Part 5: Validation and testing
EN ISO 19101-1:2014	Geographic information - Reference model - Part 1: Fundamentals (ISO 19101-1:2014)
EN ISO 19103:2024	Geographic information - Conceptual schema language (ISO 19103:2024)
EN ISO 19105:2022	Geographic information - Conformance and testing (ISO 19105:2022)
EN ISO 19106:2006	Geographic information - Profiles (ISO 19106:2004)
EN ISO 19107:2019	Geographic information - Spatial schema (ISO 19107:2019)
EN ISO 19108:2005/AC:2008	Geographic information - Temporal schema (ISO 19108:2002/Cor 1:2006)
EN ISO 19108:2005	Geographic information - Temporal schema (ISO 19108:2002)
EN ISO 19109:2015	Geographic information - Rules for application schema (ISO 19109:2015)
EN ISO 19110:2016	Geographic information - Methodology for feature cataloguing (ISO 19110:2016)
EN ISO 19111:2020/A2:2023	Geographic information - Referencing by coordinates - Amendment 2 (ISO 19111:2019/Amd 2:2023)
EN ISO 19111:2020/A1:2021	Geographic information - Referencing by coordinates - Amendment 1 (ISO 19111:2019/Amd 1:2021)
EN ISO 19111:2020	Geographic information - Referencing by coordinates (ISO 19111:2019)
EN ISO 19112:2019	Geographic information - Spatial referencing by geographic identifiers (ISO 19112:2019)

EN ISO 19115-1:2014/A2:2020	Geographic information - Metadata - Part 1: Fundamentals - Amendment 2 (ISO 19115-1:2014/Amd 2:2020)
EN ISO 19115-1:2014/A1:2018	Geographic information - Metadata - Part 1: Fundamentals - Amendment 1 (ISO 19115-1:2014/Amd 1:2018)
EN ISO 19115-1:2014	Geographic information - Metadata - Part 1: Fundamentals (ISO 19115-1:2014)
EN ISO 19115-2:2019/A1:2022	Geographic information - Metadata - Part 2: Extensions for acquisition and processing - Amendment 1 (ISO 19115-2:2019/Amd 1:2022)
EN ISO 19115-2:2019	Geographic information - Metadata - Part 2: Extensions for acquisition and processing (ISO 19115-2:2019)
EN ISO 19115-3:2023	Geographic information - Metadata - Part 3: XML schema implementation for fundamental concepts (ISO 19115-3:2023)
EN ISO 19116:2025	Geographic information - Positioning services (ISO 19116:2025)
EN ISO 19117:2014	Geographic information - Portrayal (ISO 19117:2012)
EN ISO 19118:2011	Geographic information - Encoding (ISO 19118:2011)
EN ISO 19119:2016	Geographic information - Services (ISO 19119:2016)
EN ISO 19123-1:2023	Geographic information - Schema for coverage geometry and functions - Part 1: Fundamentals (ISO 19123-1:2023)
EN ISO 19123-3:2023	Geographic information - Schema for coverage geometry and functions - Part 3: Processing fundamentals (ISO 19123-3:2023, Corrected version 2023-11)
EN ISO 19125-1:2006	Geographic information - Simple feature access - Part 1: Common architecture (ISO 19125-1:2004)
EN ISO 19126:2021	Geographic information - Feature concept dictionaries and registers (ISO 19126:2021)
EN ISO 19128:2008	Geographic information - Web map server interface (ISO 19128:2005)
EN ISO 19131:2022	Geographic information - Data product specifications (ISO 19131:2022)
EN ISO 19132:2008	Geographic information - Location-based services - Reference model (ISO 19132:2007)
EN ISO 19133:2007	Geographic information - Location-based services - Tracking and navigation (ISO 19133:2005)
EN ISO 19134:2008	Geographic information - Location-based services - Multimodal routing and navigation (ISO 19134:2007)
EN ISO 19135-1:2015/A1:2021	Geographic information - Procedures for item registration - Part 1: Fundamentals - Amendment 1 (ISO 19135-1:2015/Amd 1:2021)
EN ISO 19135-1:2015	Geographic information - Procedures for item registration - Part 1: Fundamentals (ISO 19135-1:2015)
EN ISO 19136-1:2020	Geographic information - Geography Markup Language (GML) - Part 1: Fundamentals (ISO 19136-1:2020)
EN ISO 19136-2:2018	Geographic information - Geography Markup Language (GML) - Part 2: Extended schemas and encoding rules (ISO 19136-2:2015)
EN ISO 19137:2008	Geographic information - Core profile of the spatial schema (ISO 19137:2007)
CEN ISO/TS 19139-1:2019	Geographic information - XML schema implementation - Part 1: Encoding rules (ISO/TS 19139-1:2019)
EN ISO 19141:2009	Geographic information - Schema for moving features (ISO 19141:2008)
EN ISO 19142:2010	Geographic information - Web Feature Service (ISO 19142:2010)
EN ISO 19143:2012	Geographic information - Filter encoding (ISO 19143:2010)
EN ISO 19144-1:2012/AC:2012	Geographic information - Classification systems - Part 1: Classification system structure - Technical Corrigendum 1 (ISO 19144-1:2009/Cor 1:2012)
EN ISO 19144-1:2012	Geographic information - Classification systems - Part 1: Classification system structure (ISO 19144-1:2009)
EN ISO 19144-2:2023	Geoinformation - Klassifizierungssysteme - Teil 2: Meta-Beschreibungssprache für Landbedeckung (ISO 19144-2:2023)
CEN ISO/TS 19144-3:2024	Geographic information - Classification systems - Part 3: Land Use Meta Language (LUML) (ISO/TS 19144-3:2024)
EN ISO 19146:2018	Geographic information - Cross-domain vocabularies (ISO 19146:2018)
EN ISO 19148:2021	Geographic information - Linear referencing (ISO 19148:2021)
EN ISO 19150-6:2023	Geographic information - Ontology - Part 6: Service ontology register (ISO 19150-6:2023)
EN ISO 19152-1:2024	Geographic information - Land Administration Domain Model (LADM) - Part 1: Generic conceptual model (ISO 19152-1:2024)
EN ISO 19152-2:2025	Geographic information - Land Administration Domain Model (LADM) - Part 2: Land registration (ISO 19152-2:2025)
EN ISO 19152-3:2024	Geographic information - Land Administration Domain Model (LADM) - Part 3: Marine georegulation (ISO 19152-3:2024)
EN ISO 19156:2023	Geographic information - Observations, measurements and samples (ISO 19156:2023)
EN ISO 19157-1:2023	Geographic information - Data quality - Part 1: General requirements (ISO 19157-1:2023)

EN ISO 19160-2:2023	Adressierung - Teil 2: Zuweisen und Verwalten von Adressen für Objekte in der physischen Welt (ISO 19160-2:2023)
EN ISO 19164:2024	Geographic information - Indoor feature model (ISO 19164:2024)
EN ISO 19168-1:2025	Geographic information - Geospatial API for features - Part 1: Core (ISO 19168-1:2025)
EN ISO 19168-2:2022	Geographic information - Geospatial API for features - Part 2: Coordinate Reference Systems by Reference (ISO 19168-2:2022)
CEN ISO/TR 19174:2025	Geographic information - Securing interoperability among heterogeneous city domain information models (ISO/TR 19174:2025)
EN ISO 19178-1:2025	Geographic information - Training data markup language for artificial intelligence - Part 1: Conceptual model (ISO 19178-1:2025)
EN ISO 6709:2022	Standard representation of geographic point location by coordinates (ISO 6709:2022)
CEN/TR 15449-1:2012	Geographic information - Spatial data infrastructures - Part 1: Reference model
CEN/TR 15449-2:2012	Geographic information - Spatial data infrastructures - Part 2: Best practices
CEN/TR 15449-3:2012	Geographic information - Spatial data infrastructures - Part 3: Data centric view
CEN/TR 15449-4:2013	Geographic information - Spatial Data Infrastructure - Part 4: Service centric view
CEN/TR 15449-5:2015	Geographic information - Spatial data infrastructures - Part 5: Validation and testing
EN ISO 19101-1:2014	Geographic information - Reference model - Part 1: Fundamentals (ISO 19101-1:2014)
EN ISO 19103:2024	Geographic information - Conceptual schema language (ISO 19103:2024)
EN ISO 19105:2022	Geographic information - Conformance and testing (ISO 19105:2022)
EN ISO 19106:2006	Geographic information - Profiles (ISO 19106:2004)
EN ISO 19107:2019	Geographic information - Spatial schema (ISO 19107:2019)
EN ISO 19108:2005/AC:2008	Geographic information - Temporal schema (ISO 19108:2002/Cor 1:2006)
EN ISO 19108:2005	Geographic information - Temporal schema (ISO 19108:2002)
EN ISO 19109:2015	Geographic information - Rules for application schema (ISO 19109:2015)
EN ISO 19110:2016	Geographic information - Methodology for feature cataloguing (ISO 19110:2016)
EN ISO 19111:2020/A2:2023	Geographic information - Referencing by coordinates - Amendment 2 (ISO 19111:2019/Amd 2:2023)
EN ISO 19111:2020/A1:2021	Geographic information - Referencing by coordinates - Amendment 1 (ISO 19111:2019/Amd 1:2021)
EN ISO 19111:2020	Geographic information - Referencing by coordinates (ISO 19111:2019)
EN ISO 19112:2019	Geographic information - Spatial referencing by geographic identifiers (ISO 19112:2019)
EN ISO 19115-1:2014/A2:2020	Geographic information - Metadata - Part 1: Fundamentals - Amendment 2 (ISO 19115-1:2014/Amd 2:2020)
EN ISO 19115-1:2014/A1:2018	Geographic information - Metadata - Part 1: Fundamentals - Amendment 1 (ISO 19115-1:2014/Amd 1:2018)
EN ISO 19115-1:2014	Geographic information - Metadata - Part 1: Fundamentals (ISO 19115-1:2014)
EN ISO 19115-2:2019/A1:2022	Geographic information - Metadata - Part 2: Extensions for acquisition and processing - Amendment 1 (ISO 19115-2:2019/Amd 1:2022)
EN ISO 19115-2:2019	Geographic information - Metadata - Part 2: Extensions for acquisition and processing (ISO 19115-2:2019)
EN ISO 19115-3:2023	Geographic information - Metadata - Part 3: XML schema implementation for fundamental concepts (ISO 19115-3:2023)
EN ISO 19116:2025	Geographic information - Positioning services (ISO 19116:2025)
EN ISO 19117:2014	Geographic information - Portrayal (ISO 19117:2012)
EN ISO 19118:2011	Geographic information - Encoding (ISO 19118:2011)
EN ISO 19119:2016	Geographic information - Services (ISO 19119:2016)
EN ISO 19123-1:2023	Geographic information - Schema for coverage geometry and functions - Part 1: Fundamentals (ISO 19123-1:2023)
EN ISO 19123-3:2023	Geographic information - Schema for coverage geometry and functions - Part 3: Processing fundamentals (ISO 19123-3:2023, Corrected version 2023-11)
EN ISO 19125-1:2006	Geographic information - Simple feature access - Part 1: Common architecture (ISO 19125-1:2004)
EN ISO 19126:2021	Geographic information - Feature concept dictionaries and registers (ISO 19126:2021)
EN ISO 19128:2008	Geographic information - Web map server interface (ISO 19128:2005)
EN ISO 19131:2022	Geographic information - Data product specifications (ISO 19131:2022)
EN ISO 19132:2008	Geographic information - Location-based services - Reference model (ISO 19132:2007)
EN ISO 19133:2007	Geographic information - Location-based services - Tracking and navigation (ISO 19133:2005)
EN ISO 19134:2008	Geographic information - Location-based services - Multimodal routing and navigation (ISO 19134:2007)
EN ISO 19135-1:2015/A1:2021	Geographic information - Procedures for item registration - Part 1: Fundamentals - Amendment 1 (ISO 19135-1:2015/Amd 1:2021)

EN ISO 19135-1:2015	Geographic information - Procedures for item registration - Part 1: Fundamentals (ISO 19135-1:2015)
EN ISO 19136-1:2020	Geographic information - Geography Markup Language (GML) - Part 1: Fundamentals (ISO 19136-1:2020)
EN ISO 19136-2:2018	Geographic information - Geography Markup Language (GML) - Part 2: Extended schemas and encoding rules (ISO 19136-2:2015)
EN ISO 19137:2008	Geographic information - Core profile of the spatial schema (ISO 19137:2007)
CEN ISO/TS 19139-1:2019	Geographic information - XML schema implementation - Part 1: Encoding rules (ISO/TS 19139-1:2019)
EN ISO 19141:2009	Geographic information - Schema for moving features (ISO 19141:2008)
EN ISO 19142:2010	Geographic information - Web Feature Service (ISO 19142:2010)
EN ISO 19143:2012	Geographic information - Filter encoding (ISO 19143:2010)
EN ISO 19144-1:2012/AC:2012	Geographic information - Classification systems - Part 1: Classification system structure - Technical Corrigendum 1 (ISO 19144-1:2009/Cor 1:2012)
EN ISO 19144-1:2012	Geographic information - Classification systems - Part 1: Classification system structure (ISO 19144-1:2009)
EN ISO 19144-2:2023	Geoinformation - Klassifizierungssysteme - Teil 2: Meta-Beschreibungssprache für Landbedeckung (ISO 19144-2:2023)
CEN ISO/TS 19144-3:2024	Geographic information - Classification systems - Part 3: Land Use Meta Language (LUML) (ISO/TS 19144-3:2024)
EN ISO 19146:2018	Geographic information - Cross-domain vocabularies (ISO 19146:2018)
EN ISO 19148:2021	Geographic information - Linear referencing (ISO 19148:2021)
EN ISO 19150-6:2023	Geographic information - Ontology - Part 6: Service ontology register (ISO 19150-6:2023)
EN ISO 19152-1:2024	Geographic information - Land Administration Domain Model (LADM) - Part 1: Generic conceptual model (ISO 19152-1:2024)
EN ISO 19152-2:2025	Geographic information - Land Administration Domain Model (LADM) - Part 2: Land registration (ISO 19152-2:2025)
EN ISO 19152-3:2024	Geographic information - Land Administration Domain Model (LADM) - Part 3: Marine georegulation (ISO 19152-3:2024)
EN ISO 19156:2023	Geographic information - Observations, measurements and samples (ISO 19156:2023)
EN ISO 19157-1:2023	Geographic information - Data quality - Part 1: General requirements (ISO 19157-1:2023)
EN ISO 19160-2:2023	Adressierung - Teil 2: Zuweisen und Verwalten von Adressen für Objekte in der physischen Welt (ISO 19160-2:2023)
EN ISO 19164:2024	Geographic information - Indoor feature model (ISO 19164:2024)
EN ISO 19168-1:2025	Geographic information - Geospatial API for features - Part 1: Core (ISO 19168-1:2025)
EN ISO 19168-2:2022	Geographic information - Geospatial API for features - Part 2: Coordinate Reference Systems by Reference (ISO 19168-2:2022)
CEN ISO/TR 19174:2025	Geographic information - Securing interoperability among heterogeneous city domain information models (ISO/TR 19174:2025)
EN ISO 19178-1:2025	Geographic information - Training data markup language for artificial intelligence - Part 1: Conceptual model (ISO 19178-1:2025)

Table 57. CEN/TC 287 Projects under development.

Project reference	Title
FprEN ISO 19109	Geographic information - General feature model and rules for application schema (ISO/FDIS 19109:2025)
prEN ISO 19111 rev	Geographic information — Referencing by coordinates
prEN ISO 19115-1 rev	Geographic information — Metadata — Part 1: Fundamentals
prCEN ISO/TR 19115-4	ISO/AWI TR 19115-4 Geographic information — Metadata — Part 4: JSON schema implementation of metadata fundamentals
prEN ISO 19119 rev	Geographic information — Services
prCEN ISO/TR 19121	Geographic information — Imagery and gridded data
prEN ISO 19123-2	EN ISO/AWI 19123-2 Geographic information — Schema for coverage geometry and functions — Part 2: Coverage implementation schema
prCEN ISO/TS 19123-4	ISO/AWI TS 19123-4 Geographic information — Schema for coverage geometry and functions — Part 4: Tiling Schema
prCEN ISO/TS 19124-2	Geographic information -- Calibration and validation of remote sensing data and derived products -- Part 2: SAR

prCEN ISO/TS 19124-3	ISO/AWI TS 19124-3 - Geographic information — Calibration and validation of remote sensing data and derived products — Part 3: Optical sensors
prCEN ISO/TS 19124-4	ISO/AWI TS 19124-4 - Geographic information — Calibration and validation of remote sensing data and derived products — Part 4: Lidar
prEN ISO 19127	ISO/AWI 19127 Geographic information — Geodetic register
prCEN ISO/TS 19130-2	ISO/AWI TS 19130-2 Geographic information — Imagery sensor models for geopositioning — Part 2: SAR, InSAR, lidar and sonar
prEN ISO 19135	Geographic information - Registration and register governance (ISO/DIS 19135:2024)
prCEN ISO/TS 19144-4	Geographic information — Classification systems — Part 4: Registration and implementation aspects
FprEN ISO 19152-4	Geographic information - Land Administration Domain Model (LADM) - Part 4: Valuation information (ISO/FDIS 19152-4:2025)
FprEN ISO 19152-5	Geographic information - Land Administration Domain Model (LADM) - Part 5: Spatial plan information (ISO/FDIS 19152-5:2025)
prEN ISO 19157-3	ISO/AWI 19157-3 restart Geographic information — Data quality — Part 3: Data quality measures register
prEN ISO 19158	ISO/AWI 19158 restart Geographic information — Quality assurance of data supply
prEN ISO 19161-2	ISO/AWI 19161-2 - Geographic information — Geodetic references — Part 2: Unique identification of geodetic ground stations
prEN ISO 19163-2	EN ISO/AWI TS 19163-2 Geographic information — Content components and encoding rules for imagery and gridded data — Part 2: Implementation schema
prCEN ISO/TS 19166	ISO/CD TS 19166 - Geographic information — BIM to GIS conceptual mapping (B2GM)
FprCEN ISO/TR 19175	Geographic information - Gap analysis of geospatial standards for indoor-outdoor seamless navigation (ISO/DTR 19175:2025)
prCEN ISO/TS 19176-1	ISO/AWI TS 19176-1 Geographic information — Analysis ready data — Part 1: Framework and fundamentals
prEN ISO 19177-1	Geographic information - Geospatial API for tiles - Part 1: Core (ISO/DIS 19177-1:2024)
prCEN ISO/TS 19179	Geographic Information - ESG Assessment in Geospatial Standards
prCEN ISO/TR 19180	Geographic Information — Guidelines for incorporating gender sensitivity in geospatial standards
prCEN ISO/TR 19181	Geographic information — Maintenance and management of common classifiers and their implementation artefacts

Table 58. CEN/CLC/JTC 25 Projects under development.

Project reference	Title
prEN 18235-1	Trusted Data Transactions - Part 1: Terminology, concepts and mechanisms
	Trusted Data Transactions - Part 2: Trustworthiness requirements

Table 59. Standards from ISO/TC 46/SC 11.

Reference	Title
ISO/TS 7538:2024	Functional requirements for disposition of records
ISO/TR 8344:2024	Information and documentation — Issues and considerations for managing records in structured data environments
ISO 13008:2022	Information and documentation — Digital records conversion and migration process
ISO/TR 13028:2010	Information and documentation - Implementation guidelines for digitization of records
ISO 15489-1:2016	Information and documentation — Records management — Part 1: Concepts and principles
ISO 16175-1:2020	Information and documentation — Processes and functional requirements for software for managing records — Part 1: Functional requirements and associated guidance for any applications that manage digital records
ISO/TS 16175-2:2020	Information and documentation — Processes and functional requirements for software for managing records — Part 2: Guidance for selecting, designing, implementing and maintaining software for managing records
ISO 17068:2017	Information and documentation — Trusted third party repository for digital records
ISO 18128:2024	Information and documentation — Records risks — Risk assessment for records management
ISO/TR 21946:2018	Information and documentation — Appraisal for managing records
ISO/TR 21965:2019	Information and documentation — Records management in enterprise architecture

ISO 22310:2006	Information and documentation — Guidelines for standards drafters for stating records management requirements in standards
ISO/TR 22428-1:2020	Managing records in cloud computing environments — Part 1: Issues and concerns
ISO 23081-1:2017	Information and documentation — Records management processes — Metadata for records — Part 1: Principles
ISO 23081-2:2021	Information and documentation — Metadata for managing records — Part 2: Conceptual and implementation issues
ISO/TR 23081-3:2011	Information and documentation — Managing metadata for records — Part 3: Self-assessment method
ISO/TR 24332:2025	Information and documentation — Blockchain and distributed ledger technology (DLT) in relation to authoritative records, records systems and records management
ISO/TR 26122:2008/Cor 1:2009	Information and documentation — Work process analysis for records — Technical Corrigendum 1
ISO/TR 26122:2008	Information and documentation — Work process analysis for records
ISO 30300:2020	Information and documentation — Records management — Core concepts and vocabulary
ISO 30301:2019	Information and documentation — Management systems for records — Requirements
ISO 30301:2019/Amd 1:2024	Information and documentation — Management systems for records — Requirements — Amendment 1: Climate action changes
ISO 30302:2022/Amd 1:2025	Information and documentation — Management systems for records — Guidelines for implementation — Amendment 1: Non conformities, corrective actions and climate change requirements
ISO 30302:2022	Information and documentation — Management systems for records — Guidelines for implementation

Table 60. ISO/TC 46/SC 11 Projects under development.

Project reference	Title
ISO/NP 18965	Information and documentation — Records risks — Risk assessment for records management
ISO/CD TR 23081-4	Information and documentation — Metadata for Records — Part 4: Report on metadata element sets
ISO/AWI TR 24086	Digital legacies
ISO/AWI TS 25174	Information and documentation — Records management capability assessment model
ISO/PWI TS 25280	Records management and AI - Principles and Considerations
ISO/PWI 25951	Information and documentation — Requirements on Blockchain and DLT to be used for authoritative records, records systems, and records management
ISO/PWI 25952	Records management awareness and capability development in organisations
ISO/AWI 30301	Information and documentation — Management systems for records — Requirements

Table 61. Standards from ISO/TC 20/SC 13.

Reference	Title
ISO 10537:2016	Space data and information transfer systems — Encapsulation service
ISO 11104:2011	Space data and information transfer systems — Time code formats
ISO 12175:1994	Space data and information transfer systems — Standard formatted data units — Structure and construction rules
ISO 12175:1994/Amd 1:2015	Space data and information transfer systems — Standard formatted data units — Structure and construction rules — Amendment 1
ISO 13526:2010	Space data and information transfer systems — Tracking data message
ISO 13526:2010/Amd 1:2015	Space data and information transfer systems — Tracking data message — Amendment 1
ISO 13527:2010	Space data and information transfer systems — XML formatted data unit (XFDU) structure and construction rules
ISO 13537:2010	Space data and information transfer systems — Reference architecture for space data systems
ISO 13541:2021	Space data and information transfer systems — Attitude data messages
ISO 13764:1996	Space data and information transfer systems — Standard formatted data units — Control authority procedures
ISO 14721:2025	Space Data System Practices — Reference model for an open archival information system (OAIS)
ISO 14961:2002	Space data and information transfer systems — Parameter value language specification

ISO 14962:1997	Space data and information transfer systems — ASCII encoded English
ISO 15395:1998	Space data and information transfer systems — Standard formatted data units — Control authority data structures
ISO 15396:2007	Space data and information transfer systems — Cross support reference model — Space link extension services
ISO 15887:2013	Space data and information transfer systems — Lossless data compression
ISO 15888:2000	Space data and information transfer systems — Standard formatted data units — Referencing environment
ISO 15889:2011	Space data and information transfer systems — The data description language EAST specification
ISO 15893:2010	Space data and information transfer systems — Space communications protocol specification (SCPS) — Transport protocol (SCPS-TP)
ISO 16363:2025	Space data and information transfer systems — Audit and certification of trustworthy digital repositories
ISO 16919:2025	Space data and information transfer systems — Requirements for bodies providing audit and certification of candidate trustworthy digital repositories
ISO 17107:2011	Space data and information transfer systems — XML specification for navigation data messages
ISO 17355:2007	Space data and information transfer systems — CCSDS file delivery protocol
ISO 17807:2013	Space data and information transfer systems - Asynchronous message service
ISO 17808:2014	Space data and information transfer systems — Telemetry (TM) channel coding profiles
ISO 17809:2014	Space data and information transfer systems - Delta-differential one-way ranging (Delta-DOR) operations
ISO 17810:2014	Space data and information transfer systems — Data transmission and pseudo-random noise (PN) ranging for 2 GHz code division multiple access (CDMA) link via data relay satellite
ISO 17854:2013	Space data and information transfer systems — Flexible advanced coding and modulation scheme for high rate telemetry applications
ISO 18201:2013	Space data and information transfer systems — Mission operations reference model
ISO 18202:2015	Space data and information transfer systems — Mission operations message abstraction layer
ISO 18381:2013	Space data and information transfer systems — Lossless multispectral and hyperspectral image compression
ISO 18382:2013	Space data and information transfer systems — Spacecraft onboard interface services — RFID-based inventory management systems
ISO 18423:2015	Space data and information transfer systems — Pseudo-Noise (PN) Ranging Systems
ISO 18424:2013	Space data and information transfer systems — XML Telemetric and Command Exchange (XTCE)
ISO 18425:2013	Space data and information transfer systems — Spacecraft Onboard Interface Services — Subnetwork Packet Service
ISO 18426:2013	Space data and information transfer systems — Spacecraft Onboard Interface Services — Subnetwork Memory Access Service
ISO 18427:2013	Space data and information transfer systems — Spacecraft Onboard Interface Services — Subnetwork Synchronization Service
ISO 18428:2013	Space data and information transfer systems — Spacecraft Onboard Interface Services — Subnetwork Device Discovery Service
ISO 18438:2013	Space data and information transfer systems — Spacecraft Onboard Interface Services — Subnetwork Test Service
ISO 18440:2016	Space data and information transfer systems — Space link extension — Internet protocol for transfer services
ISO 18441:2021	Space data and information transfer systems — Space link extension — Application program interface for transfer services — Core specification
ISO 18442:2016	Space data and information transfer systems — Space link extension — Application program interface for return all frames service
ISO 18443:2016	Space data and information transfer systems — Space link extension — Application program interface for return channel frames service
ISO 18444:2016	Space data and information transfer systems — Space link extension — Application program interface for return operational control fields service
ISO 18445:2016	Space data and information transfer systems — Space link extension — Application program interface for the forward CLTU service
ISO 18446:2016	Space data and information transfer systems — Space link extension — Application program interface for the forward space packet service
ISO 19389:2014	Space data and information transfer systems — Conjunction data message
ISO 20104:2015	Space data and information transfer systems — Producer-Archive Interface Specification (PAIS)
ISO 20105:2015	Space data and information transfer systems — Operation of CFDP over encapsulation service
ISO 20106:2015	Space data and information transfer systems — Mission operations common object model

ISO 20205:2015	Space data and information transfer systems — Spacecraft Onboard Interface Systems — Low Data-Rate Wireless Communications for Spacecraft Monitoring and Control
ISO 20206:2015	Space data and information transfer systems — IP over CCSDS space links
ISO 20207:2015	Space data and information transfer systems — CCSDS Space Link Protocols over ETSI DVB-S2 Standard
ISO 20208:2015	Space data and information transfer systems — Delta-DOR Raw Data Exchange Format
ISO 20210:2015	Space data and information transfer systems — Mission Operations Message Abstraction Layer - JAVA API
ISO 20214:2015	Space data and information transfer systems — Security architecture for space data systems
ISO 20215:2015	Space data and information transfer systems — CCSDS cryptographic algorithms
ISO 20652:2006	Space data and information transfer systems — Producer-archive interface — Methodology abstract standard
ISO 21076:2016	Space data and information transfer systems — Space communications cross support — Architecture requirements document
ISO 21077:2021	Space data and information transfer systems — Digital motion imagery
ISO 21080:2016	Space data and information transfer systems — Licklider transmission protocol (LTP) for CCSDS
ISO 21082:2016	Mission operations — MAL space packet transport binding and binary encoding
ISO 21323:2016	Space data and information transfer systems — CCSDS Bundle protocol specification
ISO 21324:2016	Space data and information transfer systems — Space data link security protocol
ISO 21459:2015	Space data and information transfer systems — Proximity-1 space link protocol — Coding and synchronization sublayer
ISO 21460:2015	Space data and information transfer systems — Proximity-1 space link protocol — Physical layer
ISO 21961:2003	Space data and information transfer systems — Data entity dictionary specification language (DEDSL) — Abstract syntax
ISO 21962:2003	Space data and information transfer systems — Data entity dictionary specification language (DEDSL) — PVL syntax
ISO 22641:2012	Space data and information transfer systems — TM (telemetry) synchronization and channel coding
ISO 22642:2015	Space data and information transfer systems — TC synchronization and channel coding
ISO 22643:2003	Space data and information transfer systems — Data entity dictionary specification language (DEDSL) — XML/DTD Syntax
ISO 22645:2016	Space data and information transfer systems — TM (telemetry) space data link protocol
ISO 22646:2005	Space data and information transfer systems — Space packet protocol
ISO 22646:2005/Amd 1:2015	Space data and information transfer systems — Space packet protocol — Amendment 1
ISO 22663:2015	Space data and information transfer systems — Proximity-1 space link protocol — Data link layer
ISO 22664:2016	Space data and information transfer systems — TC (telecommand) space data link protocol
ISO 22666:2016	Space data and information transfer systems — AOS (advanced orbiting systems) space data link protocol
ISO 22667:2013	Space data and information transfer systems — Communications operation procedure-1
ISO 22669:2021	Space data and information transfer systems — Space link extension (SLE) — Return-all-frames service specification
ISO 22670:2021	Space data and information transfer systems — Space link extension (SLE) — Return-channel-frames service specification
ISO 22671:2021	Space data and information transfer systems — Space link extension (SLE) — Forward communications link transmission unit (CLTU) service specification
ISO 22672:2021	Space data and information transfer systems — Space link extension (SLE) — Forward space packet service specification
ISO 23103:2020	Space link extension — Cross support transfer service — Specification framework
ISO 23104:2020	Space link extension — Cross support transfer service — Monitored data service
ISO 23507:2025	Space data and information transfer systems — Information preparation to enable long term use
ISO 26143:2021	Space data and information transfer systems — Space link extension (SLE) — Return operational control fields service specification
ISO 26868:2009	Space data and information transfer systems — Image data compression
ISO 10537:2016	Space data and information transfer systems — Encapsulation service
ISO 11104:2011	Space data and information transfer systems — Time code formats
ISO 12175:1994	Space data and information transfer systems — Standard formatted data units — Structure and construction rules
ISO 12175:1994/Amd 1:2015	Space data and information transfer systems — Standard formatted data units — Structure and construction rules — Amendment 1
ISO 13526:2010	Space data and information transfer systems — Tracking data message

ISO 13526:2010/Amd 1:2015	Space data and information transfer systems — Tracking data message — Amendment 1
ISO 13527:2010	Space data and information transfer systems — XML formatted data unit (XFDU) structure and construction rules
ISO 13537:2010	Space data and information transfer systems — Reference architecture for space data systems
ISO 13541:2021	Space data and information transfer systems — Attitude data messages
ISO 13764:1996	Space data and information transfer systems — Standard formatted data units — Control authority procedures
ISO 14721:2025	Space Data System Practices — Reference model for an open archival information system (OAIS)
ISO 14961:2002	Space data and information transfer systems — Parameter value language specification
ISO 14962:1997	Space data and information transfer systems — ASCII encoded English
ISO 15395:1998	Space data and information transfer systems — Standard formatted data units — Control authority data structures
ISO 15396:2007	Space data and information transfer systems — Cross support reference model — Space link extension services
ISO 15887:2013	Space data and information transfer systems — Lossless data compression
ISO 15888:2000	Space data and information transfer systems — Standard formatted data units — Referencing environment
ISO 15889:2011	Space data and information transfer systems — The data description language EAST specification
ISO 15893:2010	Space data and information transfer systems — Space communications protocol specification (SCPS) — Transport protocol (SCPS-TP)
ISO 16363:2025	Space data and information transfer systems — Audit and certification of trustworthy digital repositories
ISO 16919:2025	Space data and information transfer systems — Requirements for bodies providing audit and certification of candidate trustworthy digital repositories
ISO 17107:2011	Space data and information transfer systems — XML specification for navigation data messages
ISO 17355:2007	Space data and information transfer systems — CCSDS file delivery protocol
ISO 17807:2013	Space data and information transfer systems - Asynchronous message service
ISO 17808:2014	Space data and information transfer systems — Telemetry (TM) channel coding profiles
ISO 17809:2014	Space data and information transfer systems - Delta-differential one-way ranging (Delta-DOR) operations
ISO 17810:2014	Space data and information transfer systems — Data transmission and pseudo-random noise (PN) ranging for 2 GHz code division multiple access (CDMA) link via data relay satellite
ISO 17854:2013	Space data and information transfer systems — Flexible advanced coding and modulation scheme for high rate telemetry applications
ISO 18201:2013	Space data and information transfer systems — Mission operations reference model
ISO 18202:2015	Space data and information transfer systems — Mission operations message abstraction layer
ISO 18381:2013	Space data and information transfer systems — Lossless multispectral and hyperspectral image compression
ISO 18382:2013	Space data and information transfer systems — Spacecraft onboard interface services — RFID-based inventory management systems
ISO 18423:2015	Space data and information transfer systems — Pseudo-Noise (PN) Ranging Systems
ISO 18424:2013	Space data and information transfer systems — XML Telemetric and Command Exchange (XTCE)
ISO 18425:2013	Space data and information transfer systems — Spacecraft Onboard Interface Services — Subnetwork Packet Service
ISO 18426:2013	Space data and information transfer systems — Spacecraft Onboard Interface Services — Subnetwork Memory Access Service
ISO 18427:2013	Space data and information transfer systems — Spacecraft Onboard Interface Services — Subnetwork Synchronization Service
ISO 18428:2013	Space data and information transfer systems — Spacecraft Onboard Interface Services — Subnetwork Device Discovery Service
ISO 18438:2013	Space data and information transfer systems — Spacecraft Onboard Interface Services — Subnetwork Test Service
ISO 18440:2016	Space data and information transfer systems — Space link extension — Internet protocol for transfer services
ISO 18441:2021	Space data and information transfer systems — Space link extension — Application program interface for transfer services — Core specification
ISO 18442:2016	Space data and information transfer systems — Space link extension — Application program interface for return all frames service
ISO 18443:2016	Space data and information transfer systems — Space link extension — Application program interface for return channel frames service

ISO 18444:2016	Space data and information transfer systems — Space link extension — Application program interface for return operational control fields service
ISO 18445:2016	Space data and information transfer systems — Space link extension — Application program interface for the forward CLTU service
ISO 18446:2016	Space data and information transfer systems — Space link extension — Application program interface for the forward space packet service
ISO 19389:2014	Space data and information transfer systems — Conjunction data message
ISO 20104:2015	Space data and information transfer systems — Producer-Archive Interface Specification (PAIS)
ISO 20105:2015	Space data and information transfer systems — Operation of CDFP over encapsulation service
ISO 20106:2015	Space data and information transfer systems — Mission operations common object model
ISO 20205:2015	Space data and information transfer systems — Spacecraft Onboard Interface Systems — Low Data-Rate Wireless Communications for Spacecraft Monitoring and Control
ISO 20206:2015	Space data and information transfer systems — IP over CCSDS space links
ISO 20207:2015	Space data and information transfer systems — CCSDS Space Link Protocols over ETSI DVB-S2 Standard
ISO 20208:2015	Space data and information transfer systems — Delta-DOR Raw Data Exchange Format
ISO 20210:2015	Space data and information transfer systems — Mission Operations Message Abstraction Layer - JAVA API
ISO 20214:2015	Space data and information transfer systems — Security architecture for space data systems
ISO 20215:2015	Space data and information transfer systems — CCSDS cryptographic algorithms
ISO 20652:2006	Space data and information transfer systems — Producer-archive interface — Methodology abstract standard
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ISO 21082:2016	Mission operations — MAL space packet transport binding and binary encoding
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ISO 21324:2016	Space data and information transfer systems — Space data link security protocol
ISO 21459:2015	Space data and information transfer systems — Proximity-1 space link protocol — Coding and synchronization sublayer
ISO 21460:2015	Space data and information transfer systems — Proximity-1 space link protocol — Physical layer
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ISO 22642:2015	Space data and information transfer systems — TC synchronization and channel coding
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ISO 22645:2016	Space data and information transfer systems — TM (telemetry) space data link protocol
ISO 22646:2005	Space data and information transfer systems — Space packet protocol
ISO 22646:2005/Amd 1:2015	Space data and information transfer systems — Space packet protocol — Amendment 1
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ISO 22664:2016	Space data and information transfer systems — TC (telecommand) space data link protocol
ISO 22666:2016	Space data and information transfer systems — AOS (advanced orbiting systems) space data link protocol
ISO 22667:2013	Space data and information transfer systems — Communications operation procedure-1
ISO 22669:2021	Space data and information transfer systems — Space link extension (SLE) — Return-all-frames service specification
ISO 22670:2021	Space data and information transfer systems — Space link extension (SLE) — Return-channel-frames service specification
ISO 22671:2021	Space data and information transfer systems — Space link extension (SLE) — Forward communications link transmission unit (CLTU) service specification
ISO 22672:2021	Space data and information transfer systems — Space link extension (SLE) — Forward space packet service specification
ISO 23103:2020	Space link extension — Cross support transfer service — Specification framework
ISO 23104:2020	Space link extension — Cross support transfer service — Monitored data service
ISO 23507:2025	Space data and information transfer systems — Information preparation to enable long term use

ISO 26143:2021	Space data and information transfer systems — Space link extension (SLE) — Return operational control fields service specification
ISO 26868:2009	Space data and information transfer systems — Image data compression

Table 62. CEN/TC 471 Projects under development.

Project reference	Title
FprEN 4709-005	Aerospace series - Unmanned Aircraft Systems - Part 005: Verification method for the Geocaging function
prEN 4709-008	Aerospace series - Unmanned Aircraft Systems - Part 008: C5 Accessories kits
prEN 4709-007	Aerospace series - Unmanned Aircraft Systems - Part 007: General product requirements for UAS of classes C5 and C6
prEN 4709-006	Aerospace series - Unmanned Aircraft Systems - Part 006: Means to terminate flight, requirements, and verification
prEN 4709-001	Aerospace series - Unmanned Aircraft Systems - Part 001: Product requirements and verification
prEN 4709-004	Aerospace series - Unmanned Aircraft Systems - Part 004: Lighting requirements
prEN 4709-003	Aerospace series - Unmanned Aircraft Systems - Part 003: Geo-awareness requirements

Table 63. Standards from ISO/TC 20/SC 16.

Reference	Title
ISO 4358:2023	Test methods for civil multi-copter unmanned aircraft system
ISO 5015-2:2022	Unmanned aircraft systems — Part 2: Operation of vertiports for vertical take-off and landing (VTOL) unmanned aircraft (UA)
ISO 5109:2023	Evaluation method for the resonance frequency of the multi-copter UA (unmanned aircraft) by measurement of rotor and body frequencies
ISO 5110:2023	Test method for flight stability of a multi-copter unmanned aircraft system (UAS) under wind and rain conditions
ISO 5286:2023	Flight performance of civil small and light fixed-wing unmanned aircraft systems (UAS) — Test methods
ISO 5305:2024	Noise measurements for UAS (unmanned aircraft systems)
ISO 5309:2023	Civil small and light unmanned aircraft systems (UAS) — Vibration test methods
ISO 5312:2023	Civil small and light unmanned aircraft (UA) — Sharp injury to human body by rotor blades — Evaluation and test method
ISO 5332:2023	Civil small and light unmanned aircraft systems (UAS) under low-pressure conditions — Test methods
ISO 15964:2025	Detection and avoidance systems for uncrewed aircraft systems
ISO 21384-2:2021	Unmanned aircraft systems — Part 2: UAS components
ISO 21384-3:2023	Unmanned aircraft systems — Part 3: Operational procedures
ISO 21384-4:2020	Unmanned aircraft systems — Part 4: Vocabulary
ISO 21895:2020	Categorization and classification of civil unmanned aircraft systems
ISO/TR 23267:2024	Experiment results on test methods for detection and avoidance (DAA) systems for unmanned aircraft systems
ISO/TR 23629-1:2020	UAS traffic management (UTM) — Part 1: Survey results on UTM
ISO 23629-5:2023	UAS traffic management (UTM) — Part 5: UTM functional structure
ISO 23629-7:2021	UAS traffic management (UTM) — Part 7: Data model for spatial data
ISO 23629-8:2023	UAS traffic management (UTM) — Part 8: Remote identification
ISO 23629-9:2023	UAS traffic management (UTM) — Part 9: Interface between UTM service providers and users
ISO 23629-12:2022	UAS traffic management (UTM) — Part 12: Requirements for UTM service providers
ISO 23665:2023	Unmanned aircraft systems — Training for personnel involved in UAS operations
ISO 24352:2023	Technical requirements for small unmanned aircraft electric energy systems
ISO 24354:2023	General requirements for the payload interface of civil unmanned aircraft systems
ISO 24355:2023	Flight control system for civil small and light multicopter unmanned aircraft system (UAS) — General requirements
ISO 24356:2022	General requirements for tethered unmanned aircraft systems

Table 64. ISO/TC 20/SC 16 Projects under development.

Project reference	Title
ISO/DIS 21384-3	Unmanned aircraft systems — Part 3: Operational procedures
ISO 21384-4	Unmanned aircraft systems — Part 4: Vocabulary
ISO/CD 21895	Categorization and classification of civil unmanned aircraft systems
ISO/CD TR 23250	Survey for operational procedure for Airspace Conflict Management
ISO/DTR 23310	Uncrewed aircraft systems — UAS traffic management (UTM) — Study on functional and performance requirements for UTM systems
ISO/NP 23629-3	UAS traffic management (UTM) — Part 3: Functional and Performance Requirement for UTM systems
ISO/DIS 23665	Uncrewed aircraft systems — Training for personnel involved in UAS operations
ISO/PWI 24222	Civil small and light unmanned aircraft systems (UAS) under high-temperature and low-temperature conditions — Test methods
ISO/CD 24243	Test methods for civil small and light multi-copter unmanned aircraft dock system
ISO/CD 25009	Unmanned aircraft systems — General requirements and test methods for the hydrogen fuel gas pipes of gaseous hydrogen fuel cell powered UAV
ISO/CD 25013	Unmanned aircraft systems — General requirements and test methods for the attachable hydrogen cylinders of gaseous hydrogen fuel cell powered UAV
ISO/AWI 25132	Classification of civil unmanned aircraft system (UAS) autonomous flight control levels
ISO/WD 25172	Safety requirement for uncrewed electric vertical take-off and landing aircraft (eVTOL)
ISO/AWI 25215	Civil small and light multi-copter unmanned aircraft docking system — General requirements
ISO/AWI 25216	Categorization and classification of unmanned aircraft (UA) detection and countermeasure system
ISO/AWI 25248	Unmanned Aircraft System Type of Identifier Code and Graphical symbol
ISO/AWI 25461	Uncrewed aircraft systems — Counter UAS — Functional requirements for detection, localization, and identification
ISO/NP 25858	Uncrewed aircraft systems --Functional requirements of Flight Training Devices for the manual control of UA
ISO/NP 25909	Interface for civil small and light multi-copter uncrewed aircraft docking system — General requirements
ISO/NP 25911	Portable remote pilot station (RPS) for civil small and light uncrewed aircraft system (UAS) — General requirements
ISO/NP 25969	Uncrewed aircraft systems — External crashproof container — General requirements

Table 65. Standards from ISO/TC 323.

Reference	Title
ISO 59004:2024	Circular economy — Vocabulary, principles and guidance for implementation
ISO 59010:2024	Circular economy — Guidance on the transition of business models and value networks
ISO 59020:2024	Circular economy — Measuring and assessing circularity performance
ISO/TR 59032:2024	Circular economy — Review of existing value networks
ISO 59040:2025	Circular economy — Product circularity data sheet

Table 66. ISO/TC 323 Projects under development.

Project Reference	Title
ISO/NP 25819	Circular economy — Organizing a value network towards circularity
ISO/NP 59001	Circular economy management systems — Requirements
ISO 59004:2024	Circular economy — Vocabulary, principles and guidance for implementation
ISO 59010:2024	Circular economy — Guidance on the transition of business models and value networks
ISO 59020:2024	Circular economy — Measuring and assessing circularity performance
ISO/CD TR 59031	Circular economy – Performance-based approach – Analysis of cases studies
ISO/TR 59032:2024	Circular economy — Review of existing value networks
ISO 59040:2025	Circular economy — Product circularity data sheet
ISO/NP 25819	Circular economy — Organizing a value network towards circularity

Table 67. Standards from CEN/TC 406.

Reference	Title
EN 16524:2020	Mechanical products — Methodology for reduction of environmental impacts in product design and development
CEN/TR 17004:2016	Mechanical products — Conditions to set up environmental communication models by recognizing sectorial particularities
CEN/TR 18047:2024	Mechanical products — Order of magnitude of key environmental data

Table 68. CEN/TC 406 Projects under development.

Reference	Title
prEN 16524 rev	Mechanical products - Methodology for reduction of environmental impacts in product design and development

Table 69. Standards from IEC/TC 111.

Reference	Title
IEC 62321-1:2013	Determination of certain substances in electrotechnical products - Part 1: Introduction and overview
IEC 62321-2:2021	Determination of certain substances in electrotechnical products - Part 2: Disassembly, disjointment and mechanical sample preparation
IEC 62321-3-1:2013	Determination of certain substances in electrotechnical products - Part 3-1: Screening - Lead, mercury, cadmium, total chromium and total bromine by X-ray fluorescence spectrometry
IEC 62321-3-2:2020	Determination of certain substances in electrotechnical products - Part 3-2: Screening - Fluorine, bromine and chlorine in polymer and electronics by combustion-ion chromatography (C-IC)
IEC 62321-3-3:2021	Determination of certain substances in electrotechnical products - Part 3-3: Screening - Polybrominated biphenyls, polybrominated diphenyl ethers and phthalates in polymers by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry using a pyrolyser/thermal desorption accessory (Py/TD-GC-MS)
IEC 62321-3-4:2023	Determination of certain substances in electrotechnical products - Part 3-4: Screening - Phthalates in polymers of electrotechnical products by high performance liquid chromatography with ultraviolet detector (HPLC-UV), thin layer chromatography (TLC) and thermal desorption mass spectrometry (TD-MS)
IEC 62321-4:2013	Determination of certain substances in electrotechnical products - Part 4: Mercury in polymers, metals and electronics by CV-AAS, CV-AFS, ICP-OES and ICP-MS
IEC 62321-4:2013/AMD1:2017	Amendment 1 - Determination of certain substances in electrotechnical products - Part 4: Mercury in polymers, metals and electronics by CV-AAS, CV-AFS, ICP-OES and ICP-MS
IEC 62321-5:2013	Determination of certain substances in electrotechnical products - Part 5: Cadmium, lead and chromium in polymers and electronics and cadmium and lead in metals by AAS, AFS, ICP-OES and ICP-MS
IEC 62321-6:2015	Determination of certain substances in electrotechnical products - Part 6: Polybrominated biphenyls and polybrominated diphenyl ethers in polymers by gas chromatography -mass spectrometry (GC-MS)
IEC 62321-7-1:2015	Determination of certain substances in electrotechnical products - Part 7-1: Hexavalent chromium - Presence of hexavalent chromium (Cr(VI)) in colourless and coloured corrosion-protected coatings on metals by the colorimetric method
IEC 62321-7-2:2017	Determination of certain substances in electrotechnical products - Part 7-2: Hexavalent chromium - Determination of hexavalent chromium (Cr(VI)) in polymers and electronics by the colorimetric method
IEC 62321-8:2017	Determination of certain substances in electrotechnical products - Part 8: Phthalates in polymers by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS), gas chromatography-mass spectrometry using a pyrolyzer/thermal desorption accessory (Py-TD-GC-MS)
IEC 62321-9:2021	Determination of certain substances in electrotechnical products - Part 9: Hexabromocyclododecane in polymers by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS)

IEC 62321-10:2020	Determination of certain substances in electrotechnical products - Part 10: Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) in polymers and electronics by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS)
IEC 62321-11:2023	Determination of certain substances in electrotechnical products - Part 11: Tris(2-chloroethyl) phosphate (TCEP) in plastics by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) and liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (LC-MS)
IEC 62321-12:2023	Determination of certain substances in electrotechnical products - Part 12: Simultaneous determination – Polybrominated biphenyls, polybrominated diphenyl ethers and phthalates in polymers by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry
IEC 62430:2019	Environmentally conscious design (ECD) - Principles, requirements and guidance
IEC 62474:2018	Material declaration for products of and for the electrotechnical industry
IEC 62474:2018/AMD1:2020	Amendment 1 - Material declaration for products of and for the electrotechnical industry
IEC TS 62474-1:2022	Material declaration for products of and for the electrotechnical industry - Part 1: Guidance on the implementation of IEC 62474
IEC TR 62476:2010	Guidance for evaluation of product with respect to substance-use restrictions in electrical and electronic products
IEC 62542:2013	Environmental standardization for electrical and electronic products and systems - Glossary of terms
IEC TR 62635:2012	Guidelines for end-of-life information provided by manufacturers and recyclers and for recyclability rate calculation of electrical and electronic equipment
IEC TR 62725:2013	Analysis of quantification methodologies of greenhouse gas emissions for electrical and electronic products and systems
IEC TR 62726:2014	Guidance on quantifying greenhouse gas emission reductions from the baseline for electrical and electronic products and systems
IEC TR 62824:2016	Guidance on material efficiency considerations in environmentally conscious design of electrical and electronic products
IEC TR 62936:2016	Test method development - Guidelines for substance selection
IEC 63000:2016	Technical documentation for the assessment of electrical and electronic products with respect to the restriction of hazardous substances
IEC 63000:2016/AMD1:2022	Amendment 1 - Technical documentation for the assessment of electrical and electronic products with respect to the restriction of hazardous substances
IEC TR 63212:2020	Harmonization of environmental performance criteria for electrical and electronic products - Feasibility study
IEC 63333:2023	General method for assessing the proportion of reused components in products
IEC 63366:2025	Product category rules for life cycle assessment of electrical and electronic products and systems
IEC TS 63428:2024	Guidance on material circulation considerations in environmentally conscious design
IEC 82474-1:2025	Material declaration – Part 1: General requirements

Table 70. IEC/TC 111 Projects under development.

Project Reference	Title
PWI 111-2	IEC 62321-XX Determination of certain substances in electrotechnical products - Part XX: Benzotriazole ultraviolet absorbers in plastics by Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GCMS)
PNW 111-829 ED1	General methods for the assessment of product durability - Part 2: Ability to repair, reuse and upgrade (RRU)
IEC 62321-3-1 ED2	Determination of certain substances in electrotechnical products - Part 3-1: Screening - Lead, mercury, cadmium, total chromium total bromine, total phosphorus, total chlorine, total tin and total antimony content by X-ray fluorescence spectrometry
IEC 62321-5 ED2	Determination of certain substances in electrotechnical products - Determination of multi elements in plastics, metals and electronics by AAS, AFS, ICP-OES and ICP-MS
IEC 62321-8 ED2	Determination of certain substances in electrotechnical products - Part 8: Phthalates in polymers by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS), gas chromatography-mass spectrometry using a pyrolyzer/thermal desorption accessory (Py-TD-GC-MS)
IEC 62321-10 ED2	Determination of certain substances in electrotechnical products - Part 10: Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) in polymers and electronics by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS)
IEC 62321-13 ED1	Determination of certain substances in electrotechnical products – Part 13: Bisphenol A in plastics by liquid chromatography-diode array detection (LC-DAD), liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (LC-MS) and liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS)

IEC 62321-14 ED1	Determination of certain substances in electrotechnical products - Part 14: Determination of short-chain chlorinated paraffins (SCCPs) and medium-chain chlorinated paraffins (MCCPs) in electrotechnical products by gas chromatography-negative chemical ionization-mass spectrometry (GC-NCI-MS)
IEC 62321-15 ED1	Determination of certain substances in electrotechnical products - Part 15: Tetrabromobisphenol A (TBBPA) in plastics by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) and liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (LC-MS)
IEC 62474 ED3	Material declaration for products of and for the electrotechnical industry
IEC 62474-C00101 EDO	IEC SDB 62474: MC-2024-EL-1 updates for EU RoHS Annex III Exemption List and Annex IV Exemptions List
IEC 62474-C00103 EDO	Add six new entries based on the ECHA consultation list for REACH SVHC Candidate List that was posted on August 30, 2024.
IEC 62542 ED2	Environmental standardization for electrical and electronic products and systems - Glossary of terms
IEC 62635 ED1	Assessment of material recoverability rate of products
IEC 63333-3 ED1	Assessment of circular content in products - Part 3: Proportion of recycled materials (Proposed Horizontal Publication)
IEC 63372 ED1	Quantification and communication of Carbon FootPRINT and GHG emission reductions/avoided emissions from electric and electronic products and systems – Principles, methodologies, requirements and guidance
IEC 63395 ED1	Sustainable management of waste electrical and electronic equipment (e-waste) - Proposed Horizontal Publication

Table 71. Standards from CEN/CLC JTC10

Reference	Title
CLC/TR 45550:2020	Definitions related to material efficiency
EN 45552:2020	General method for the assessment of the durability of energy-related products
EN 45553:2020	General method for the assessment of the ability to remanufacture energy-related products
EN 45554:2020	General methods for the assessment of the ability to repair, reuse and upgrade energy-related products
EN 45555:2019	General methods for assessing the recyclability and recoverability of energy-related products
EN 45556:2019	General method for assessing the proportion of reused components in energy-related products
EN 45557:2020	General method for assessing the proportion of recycled material content in energy-related products
EN 45558:2019	General method to declare the use of critical raw materials in energy-related products
EN 45559:2019	Methods for providing information relating to material efficiency aspects of energy-related products
EN 45560:2024	Method to achieve circular designs of products

Table 72. CEN/CLC JTC10 Projects under development.

Project Reference	Title
prEN 45553	General method for assessing the ability of a product to be remanufactured or refurbished
prEN 45558 rev	General method to declare the use of critical raw materials in products

Table 73. Standards from ISO/TC 207.

Reference	Title
IWA 42:2022	Net zero guidelines
ISO 14001:2015/Amd 1:2024	Environmental management systems — Requirements with guidance for use — Amendment 1: Climate action changes
ISO 14001:2015	Environmental management systems — Requirements with guidance for use
ISO 14002-1:2019	Environmental management systems — Guidelines for using ISO 14001 to address environmental aspects and conditions within an environmental topic area — Part 1: General

ISO 14002-2:2023	Environmental management systems — Guidelines for using ISO 14001 to address environmental aspects and conditions within an environmental topic area — Part 2: Water
ISO 14004:2016	Environmental management systems — General guidelines on implementation
ISO 14005:2019	Environmental management systems — Guidelines for a flexible approach to phased implementation
ISO 14006:2020	Environmental management systems — Guidelines for incorporating ecodesign
ISO 14007:2019	Environmental management — Guidelines for determining environmental costs and benefits
ISO 14008:2019	Monetary valuation of environmental impacts and related environmental aspects
ISO 14009:2020	Environmental management systems — Guidelines for incorporating material circulation in design and development
ISO 14015:2022	Environmental management — Guidelines for environmental due diligence assessment
ISO 14016:2020	Environmental management — Guidelines on the assurance of environmental reports
ISO 14017:2022	Environmental management — Requirements with guidance for verification and validation of water statements
ISO 14020:2022	Environmental statements and programmes for products — Principles and general requirements
ISO 14021:2016	Environmental labels and declarations — Self-declared environmental claims (Type II environmental labelling)
ISO 14021:2016/Amd 1:2021	Environmental labels and declarations — Self-declared environmental claims (Type II environmental labelling) — Amendment 1: Carbon footprint, carbon neutral
ISO 14024:2018	Environmental labels and declarations — Type I environmental labelling — Principles and procedures
ISO 14025:2006	Environmental labels and declarations — Type III environmental declarations — Principles and procedures
ISO 14026:2017	Environmental labels and declarations — Principles, requirements and guidelines for communication of footprint information
ISO/TS 14027:2017	Environmental labels and declarations — Development of product category rules
ISO/TS 14029:2022	Environmental statements and programmes for products — Mutual recognition of environmental product declarations (EPDs) and footprint communication programmes
ISO 14030-1:2021	Environmental performance evaluation — Green debt instruments — Part 1: Process for green bonds
ISO 14030-2:2021	Environmental performance evaluation — Green debt instruments — Part 2: Process for green loans
ISO 14030-3:2022	Environmental performance evaluation — Green debt instruments — Part 3: Taxonomy
ISO 14030-4:2021	Environmental performance evaluation — Green debt instruments — Part 4: Verification programme requirements
ISO 14031:2021	Environmental management — Environmental performance evaluation — Guidelines
ISO 14033:2019	Environmental management — Quantitative environmental information — Guidelines and examples
ISO 14034:2016	Environmental management — Environmental technology verification (ETV)
ISO 14040:2006	Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Principles and framework
ISO 14040:2006/Amd 1:2020	Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Principles and framework — Amendment 1
ISO 14044:2006	Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Requirements and guidelines
ISO 14044:2006/Amd 2:2020	Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Requirements and guidelines — Amendment 2
ISO 14044:2006/Amd 1:2017	Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Requirements and guidelines — Amendment 1
ISO 14045:2012	Environmental management — Eco-efficiency assessment of product systems — Principles, requirements and guidelines
ISO 14046:2014	Environmental management — Water footprint — Principles, requirements and guidelines
ISO/TR 14047:2012	Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Illustrative examples on how to apply ISO 14044 to impact assessment situations
ISO/TS 14048:2002	Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Data documentation format
ISO/TR 14049:2012	Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Illustrative examples on how to apply ISO 14044 to goal and scope definition and inventory analysis
ISO 14050:2020	Environmental management — Vocabulary
ISO 14051:2011	Environmental management — Material flow cost accounting — General framework
ISO 14052:2017	Environmental management — Material flow cost accounting — Guidance for practical implementation in a supply chain
ISO 14053:2021	Environmental management — Material flow cost accounting — Guidance for phased implementation in organizations

ISO 14055-1:2017	Environmental management — Guidelines for establishing good practices for combatting land degradation and desertification — Part 1: Good practices framework
ISO/TR 14055-2:2022	Environmental management — Guidelines for establishing good practices for combatting land degradation and desertification — Part 2: Regional case studies
ISO 14063:2020	Environmental management — Environmental communication — Guidelines and examples
ISO 14064-1:2018	Greenhouse gases — Part 1: Specification with guidance at the organization level for quantification and reporting of greenhouse gas emissions and removals
ISO 14064-2:2019	Greenhouse gases — Part 2: Specification with guidance at the project level for quantification, monitoring and reporting of greenhouse gas emission reductions or removal enhancements
ISO 14064-3:2019	Greenhouse gases — Part 3: Specification with guidance for the verification and validation of greenhouse gas statements
ISO 14065:2020	General principles and requirements for bodies validating and verifying environmental information
ISO 14066:2023	Environmental information — Competence requirements for teams validating and verifying environmental information
ISO 14067:2018	Greenhouse gases — Carbon footprint of products — Requirements and guidelines for quantification
ISO 14068-1:2023	Climate change management — Transition to net zero — Part 1: Carbon neutrality
ISO/TR 14069:2013	Greenhouse gases — Quantification and reporting of greenhouse gas emissions for organizations — Guidance for the application of ISO 14064-1
ISO 14071:2024	Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Critical review processes and reviewer competencies
ISO 14072:2024	Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Requirements and guidance for organizational life cycle assessment
ISO/TR 14073:2017	Environmental management — Water footprint — Illustrative examples on how to apply ISO 14046
ISO/TS 14074:2022	Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Principles, requirements and guidelines for normalization, weighting and interpretation
ISO 14075:2024	Environmental management — Principles and framework for social life cycle assessment
ISO/TS 14076:2025	Environmental management — Environmental techno-economic assessment — Principles, requirements and guidance
ISO 14080:2018	Greenhouse gas management and related activities — Framework and principles for methodologies on climate actions
ISO 14083:2023	Greenhouse gases — Quantification and reporting of greenhouse gas emissions arising from transport chain operations
ISO 14090:2019	Adaptation to climate change — Principles, requirements and guidelines
ISO 14091:2021	Adaptation to climate change — Guidelines on vulnerability, impacts and risk assessment
ISO/TS 14092:2020	Adaptation to climate change — Requirements and guidance on adaptation planning for local governments and communities
ISO 14093:2022	Mechanism for financing local adaptation to climate change — Performance-based climate resilience grants — Requirements and guidelines
ISO 14097:2021	Greenhouse gas management and related activities — Framework including principles and requirements for assessing and reporting investments and financing activities related to climate change
ISO 14100:2022	Guidance on environmental criteria for projects, assets and activities to support the development of green finance
ISO 19694-1:2021	Stationary source emissions — Determination of greenhouse gas emissions in energy-intensive industries — Part 1: General aspects
ISO 59014:2024	Environmental management and circular economy — Sustainability and traceability of the recovery of secondary materials — Principles, requirements and guidance

Table 74. ISO/TC 207 Projects under development.

Project Reference	Title
ISO 14001:2015/DAMd 2	Environmental management systems — Requirements with guidance for use — Amendment 2
ISO/CD 14002-3.2	Environmental management systems — Guidelines for using ISO 14001 to address environmental aspects and conditions within an environmental topic area — Part 3: Climate
ISO/WD 14002-4	Environmental management systems — Guidelines for using ISO 14001 to address environmental aspects and conditions within an environmental topic area — Part 4: Resources and waste
ISO/DIS 14019-1	Sustainability information — Part 1: General principles and requirements for validation and verification

ISO/PWI 14019-1	Validation and verification of sustainability information — Part 1: General principles and requirements
ISO/DIS 14019-2	Sustainability information — Part 2: Principles and requirements for verification processes
ISO/DIS 14019-4	Sustainability information — Part 4: Principles and requirements for bodies validating and verifying sustainability information
ISO/DIS 14021	Environmental statements and programmes for products — Self-declared environmental claims
ISO/DIS 14024	Environmental statements and programmes for products — Ecolabels
ISO/DIS 14025	Environmental statements and programmes for products — Environmental product declarations (EPDs)
ISO/AWI 14050	Environmental management — Vocabulary
ISO/FDIS 14054	Natural capital accounting for organizations — Principles, requirements and guidance
ISO/WD 14060.2	Net Zero Aligned Organizations
ISO/AWI 14064-1	Greenhouse gases — Part 1: Specification with guidance at the organization level for quantification and reporting of greenhouse gas emissions and removals
ISO/WD 14064-2	Greenhouse gases — Part 2: Specification with guidance at the project level for quantification, monitoring and reporting of greenhouse gas emission reductions or removal enhancements
ISO/DTS 14064-4	Greenhouse gases — Part 4: Guidance for the application of ISO 14064-1
ISO/DIS 14064-5	Greenhouse gases — Part 5: Guidance on activities and techniques used remotely in conducting verification and validation of greenhouse gas statements
ISO/AWI 14067	Greenhouse gases — Carbon footprint of products — Requirements and guidelines for quantification
ISO/WD 14070	Greenhouse Gas (GHG) Emission Measurements in Urban Environments — Part 1: GHG Concentration Measurements in Urban Atmospheres with Surface-Based Observing Networks
ISO/WD 14077	Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Requirements and guidelines for application of Chain of Custody (CoC) approaches in Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)
ISO/AWI TR 14082	Radiative forcing management — Guidance for the quantification and reporting of radiative forcing-based climate footprints and mitigation efforts
ISO/DIS 14092	Adaptation to climate change — Requirements and guidance on adaptation planning for local governments and communities
ISO/WD 14094	Adaptation to climate change — Requirements and guidance for monitoring and evaluation
ISO/NP 21777	ISO 14021 Environmental statements and programmes for products — Self-declared claims
ISO/NP 21779	ISO 14025 Environmental statement and programmes for products — Environmental product declarations
ISO/NP 21791	ISO 14024 Environmental statements and programmes for products — Ecolabels
IEC 82474-1	Material declaration — Part 1: General requirements

Table 75. Standards from ISO/TC 225

Reference	Title
ISO 19731:2017	Digital analytics and web analyses for purposes of market, opinion and social research — Vocabulary and service requirements
ISO 20252:2019	Market, opinion and social research, including insights and data analytics — Vocabulary and service requirements

Table 76. ISO/TC 225 Projects under development.

Project Reference	Title
ISO/DIS 20252	Market, opinion and social research, including insights and data analytics — Vocabulary and service requirements

Table 77. Standards from CLC/TC 111X.

Reference	Title
EN 50419:2022	Marking of electrical and electronic equipment (EEE) in respect to separate collection of waste EEE (WEEE)
EN 50614:2020	Requirements for the preparing for re-use of waste electrical and electronic equipment
EN 50625-1:2014	Collection, logistics & Treatment requirements for WEEE - Part 1: General treatment requirements

EN 50625-2-1:2014	Collection, logistics and treatment requirements for WEEE - Part 2-1: Treatment requirements for lamps
EN 50625-2-2:2015	Collection, logistics & Treatment requirements for WEEE - Part 2-2: Treatment requirements for WEEE containing CRTs and flat panel displays
EN 50625-2-3:2017	Collection, logistics & treatment requirements for WEEE - Part 2-3: Treatment requirements for temperature exchange equipment and other WEEE containing VFC and/or VHC
EN 50625-2-4:2017	Collection, logistics & treatment requirements for WEEE - Part 2-4: Treatment requirements for photovoltaic panels
CLC/TS 50625-3-1:2015	Collection, logistics & treatment requirements for WEEE - Part 3-1: Specification for de-pollution - General
CLC/TS 50625-3-2:2016	Collection, logistics & Treatment requirements for WEEE - Part 3-2: Technical specification for de-pollution - Lamps
CLC/TS 50625-3-3:2017	Collection, logistics & treatment requirements for WEEE - Part 3-3: Specification for de-pollution - WEEE containing CRTs and flat panel displays
CLC/TS 50625-3-4:2017	Collection, logistics & treatment requirements for WEEE - Part 3-4: Specification for de-pollution - temperature exchange equipment
CLC/TS 50625-3-5:2017	Collection, logistics & Treatment requirements for WEEE - Part 3-5: Technical specification for de-pollution - Photovoltaic panels
CLC/TS 50625-4:2017	Collection, logistics & treatment requirements for WEEE - Part 4: Specification for the collection and logistics associated with WEEE
CLC/TS 50625-5:2017	Collection, logistics & Treatment requirements for WEEE - Part 5: Specification for the final treatment of WEEE fractions - Copper and precious metals
CLC/TR 50625-6:2018	Collection, logistics & treatment requirements for WEEE - Part 6: Report on the alignment between Directive 2012/19/EU and EN 50625 series standards and EN 50614
EN 50693:2019	Product category rules for life cycle assessments of electronic and electrical products and systems
EN 62321-1:2013	Determination of certain substances in electrotechnical products - Part 1: Introduction and overview
EN IEC 62321-2:2021	Determination of certain substances in electrotechnical products - Part 2: Disassembly, disjointment and mechanical sample preparation
EN 62321-3-1:2014	Determination of certain substances in electrotechnical products - Part 3-1: Screening - Lead, mercury, cadmium, total chromium and total bromine by X-ray fluorescence spectrometry
EN 62321-3-2:2014	Determination of certain substances in electrotechnical products - Part 3-2: Screening - Total bromine in polymers and electronics by Combustion - Ion Chromatography
EN IEC 62321-3-3:2021	Determination of certain substances in electrotechnical products - Part 3-3: Screening - Polybrominated biphenyls, polybrominated diphenyl ethers and phthalates in polymers by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry using a pyrolyser/thermal desorption accessory (Py/TD-GC-MS)
EN IEC 62321-3-4:2023	Determination of certain substances in electrotechnical products - Part 3-4: Screening - Phthalates in polymers of electrotechnical products by high performance liquid chromatography with ultraviolet detector (HPLC-UV), thin layer chromatography (TLC) and thermal desorption mass spectrometry (TD-MS)
EN 62321-4:2014/A1:2017	Determination of certain substances in electrotechnical products - Part 4: Mercury in polymers, metals and electronics by CV-AAS, CV-AFS, ICP-OES and ICP-MS
EN 62321-4:2014	Determination of certain substances in electrotechnical products - Part 4: Mercury in polymers, metals and electronics by CV-AAS, CV-AFS, ICP-OES and ICP-MS
EN 62321-5:2014	Determination of certain substances in electrotechnical products - Part 5: Cadmium, lead and chromium in polymers and electronics and cadmium and lead in metals by AAS, AFS, ICP-OES and ICP-MS
EN 62321-6:2015	Determination of certain substances in electrotechnical products - Part 6: Polybrominated biphenyls and polybrominated diphenyl ethers in polymers by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS)
EN 62321-7-1:2015	Determination of certain substances in electrotechnical products - Part 7-1: Determination of the presence of hexavalent chromium (Cr(VI)) in colorless and colored corrosion-protected coatings on metals by the colorimetric method
EN 62321-7-2:2017	Determination of certain substances in electrotechnical products - Part 7-2: Hexavalent chromium - Determination of hexavalent chromium (Cr(VI)) in polymers and electronics by the colorimetric method
EN 62321-8:2017	Determination of certain substances in electrotechnical products - Part 8: Phthalates in polymers by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS), gas chromatography-mass spectrometry using a pyrolyzer/thermal desorption accessory (Py/TD-GC-MS)
EN IEC 62321-9:2021	Determination of certain substances in electrotechnical products - Part 9: Hexabromocyclododecane in polymers by chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS)

EN IEC 62321-11:2024	Determination of certain substances in electrotechnical products - Part 11: Tris(2-chloroethyl) phosphate (TCEP) in plastics by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) and liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (LC-MS)
EN IEC 62321-12:2023	Determination of certain substances in electrotechnical products - Part 12: Simultaneous determination - Polybrominated biphenyls, polybrominated diphenyl ethers and phthalates in polymers by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry
EN IEC 62430:2019	Environmentally Conscious Design (ECD) - Principles, requirements and guidance
EN 62474:2019/A1:2021	IEC Material declaration for products of and for the electrotechnical industry
EN IEC 62474:2019	Material declaration for products of and for the electrotechnical industry
EN 62542:2013	Environmental standardization for electrical and electronic products and systems - Glossary of terms
EN IEC 63000:2018	Technical documentation for the assessment of electrical and electronic products with respect to the restriction of hazardous substances

Table 78. CLC/TC 111X Projects under development.

Project reference	Title
prEN 50625-1	Collection, logistics & Treatment requirements for WEEE Part 1: General treatment requirements
CLC/prTS 50625-3-1	Collection, logistics & treatment requirements for WEEE - Part 3-1: Specification for de-pollution - General
CLC/prTS 50752	Design for recycling guidelines for styrenics and polyolefins products and parts in electrical and electronic equipment, with focus on ABS, PP and PS
prEN IEC 62321-3-1	Determination of certain substances in electrotechnical products - Part 3-1: Screening - Lead, mercury, cadmium, total chromium total bromine, total phosphorus, total chlorine, total tin and total antimony content by x-ray fluorescence spectrometry
prEN IEC 62321-5	Determination of certain substances in electrotechnical products - Determination of multi elements in plastics, metals and electronics by AAS, AFS, ICP-OES and ICP-ms
prEN IEC 62321-8	Determination of certain substances in electrotechnical products - Part 8: Phthalates in polymers by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS), gas chromatography-mass spectrometry using a pyrolyzer/thermal desorption accessory (Py-TD-GC-MS)
prEN IEC 62321-10	Determination of certain substances in electrotechnical products - Part 10: Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) in polymers and electronics by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS)
prEN IEC 62321-13:2025	Determination of certain substances in electrotechnical products - Part 13: Bisphenol A in plastics by liquid chromatography-diode array detection (LC-DAD), liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (LC-MS) and liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS)
prEN IEC 62321-14:2025	Determination of certain substances in electrotechnical products - Part 14: Determination of short-chain chlorinated paraffins (SCCPs) and medium-chain chlorinated paraffins (MCCPs) in electrotechnical products by gas chromatography-negative chemical ionization-mass spectrometry (GC-NCI-MS)
prEN IEC 62321-15	Determination of certain substances in electrotechnical products — part 15: Tetrabromobisphenol a (TBBPA) in plastics by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) and liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (LC-MS)
prEN IEC 62474	Material declaration for products of and for the electrotechnical industry
prEN IEC 62542	Environmental standardization for electrical and electronic products and systems - Glossary of terms
prEN IEC 62635	Assessment of material recoverability rate of products
FprEN IEC 63366:2024	Product category rules for life cycle assessment of electrical and electronic products and systems.
prEN IEC 63372:2024	Quantification and communication of carbon footprint and ghg emission reductions/avoided emissions from electric and electronic products and systems - Principles, methodologies, requirements and guidance
prEN IEC 63395:2024	Sustainable management of waste electrical and electronic equipment (e-waste) - Proposed horizontal publication
prEN IEC 63591	Assessment of circular content in products - Part 3: Proportion of recycled materials (Proposed Horizontal Publication)
FprEN IEC 82474-1:2024	Material declaration – Part 1: General requirements
prEN 50625-1	Collection, logistics & Treatment requirements for WEEE Part 1: General treatment requirements
CLC/prTS 50625-3-1	Collection, logistics & treatment requirements for WEEE - Part 3-1: Specification for de-pollution - General

